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Agri-food and Tourism
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PROCEEDING OF BIOATLAS 2014
CONFERENCE-vol. 2

Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

15-17 May 2014
BIOATLAS 2014 CONFERENCE
International Conference on New Research in
Food and Tourism

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EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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ACADEMIC MESSAGE

at the 4th edition of BIOATLAS International Conference,
taking place at Transilvania University from Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism,
May, 15-17, 2014

The message identifies itself with a certitude of the professional prestige and of the scientific quality of excellence that this scientific event made proof of during the previous editions that took place between 2008 - 2012.

We emphasize the fact that this professional message has a triple academic meaning, as I am transmitting it on behalf of profile specialists from the Romanian Academy, from the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences and from the Academy of Scientists from Romania, having the intellectual and moral satisfaction to accomplish an honorable colleague duty towards the initiator and coordinator of this international conference, respectively Mr. Prof. Romulus Gruia, PhD, that I have met and particularly appreciated for more than three decades, as he has always been restless in seeking scientific truth and in permanent direct connection with international scientific news in the competence fields that made him known and that positively superpose with the present and of perspective complex themes approached in this volume, that I recommend with all my conviction and necessary responsibility.

Both for specialists and for consuming and beneficiary public from civil society, all news referring to alimentary safety and security, to their nutritive quality and biodisponibility, to traditional culinary diversity and to a polyvalent tourism, respectively ecologic, cultural, rural etc., are approached in this volume with high scientific and methodological accuracy at superior level of international standards, with scientific interpretations corresponding to international literature of specialty, bringing numerous and various theoretic and practical scientific contributions to the progress and development of thorough knowledge linked to agri-food biodiversity and biotechnology, gastronomic engineering, traditional foods and etno-pharmacology, agri-tourism, landscape management and development of tourism industry, IT applications and equipments corresponding to these fields.

We wish good luck to the ongoing of the scientific events of the conference.

Prof.univ.dr., Dr.HC (M) Alexandru T. BOGDAN

Correspondent Member of the Romanian Academy
Member of honour of Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences
Member of honour of Academy of Scientists from Romania

TRANSILVANIA UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF FOOD AND TOURISM

Eco-biotechnologies and Equipment
for Food and Agriculture

BIOATLAS

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
OF NEW RESEARCH IN FOOD AND TOURISM**

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SUMMARY

	Editorial	
	1	<i>Academic Message</i>
	Biodiversity	
	5	<i>General Aspects Regarding the Heat Losses in Greenhouses</i> Bodolan Ciprian, Gh. Bratucu
	10	<i>Way to Improve the Efficiency of Industrial Enterprises on the Basis of Alternative Feedstuffs</i> O. Ozhereleva, E. Kryvenko, I. Cheremushkina
	14	<i>Development of biotechnology combined food systems based on plant systems for special nutrition</i> N. Rodionova, E. Popov, M. Manukowskai, M. Popova, A. Fomitcheva, M. Maltseva
	19	<i>Development of technologies of functional foods based on the shrimp with vegetable-part food systems</i> N. Rodionova, E. Popov, M. Manukowskai, A. Skvortsova, A. Fomitcheva
	CalitaTerra	
	25	<i>Effect Of Extraction Conditions on the Yield and Quality of Oil from Sunflower Seeds</i> A. O. Arisanu, F. Rus
	33	<i>Historical Developments in Oil Extraction Methods and Present Practices of Oil Extraction</i> A. O. Arisanu
	37	<i>Analysis and Interpretation of Potato Sorting and Sizing process By Video Technique</i> F. V. Edu, C. Csatos
	41	<i>Research Regarding Rheological Properties of Cereal Grains</i> M. Lupu, V. Pădureanu, C.M. Canja
	45	<i>The aspects of vacuum packaging in food technology</i> E. Gerasimenko, E. Popov, T. Bakhtina
	Sanogeneous Food	
	49	<i>Development of Formulations Enriched Meat Products in Applying the Secondary Fractions of Grain Processing</i> T. Alekseeva, Z. Mageramova, T. Malikova, M. Zyablov
	53	<i>Development of Compounding Enriched Flour Confectionery with Application of Products of Deep Processing of Grain</i> T. Alekseeva, Y. Kalgina, A. Vesnina, M. Zyablov
	57	<i>Study regarding the possibilities to obtain functional traditional foods from whey</i> A. Dabija, I. Rebenciuc, A. Buculei
	62	<i>Innovation In The Development Of Gluten-Free Confectionery Bakery Products</i> S. Tefikova, A. Starikova

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality		
	66	<i>Diagnosis of Tourism Enterprises</i> N. Boian
	71	<i>The Multidimensionality of Tourism Phenomenon</i> D. Foris
	76	<i>Rural Tourism in Braşov County</i> M. Florea
Ideas and Concepts		
	80	<i>Research of influence of extent of hydration of biopolymers of cake of germs of wheat on rheological properties of system</i> N. Rodionova, O. Sokolova, V. Naumenko, A. Rodionov
	84	<i>Study of innovative technologies in molecular cuisine</i> J. Krasilnikova, E. Popov, E. Pozhidaeva, R. Gonharov
	88	<i>Research Regarding Passive Energy Houses In Romania</i> GH.C. SPIRCHEZ, D.C. OLA
	92	<i>Study on the Lyophilization process of Aromatic Plants</i> D. Mnerie, G.V.Mnerie
	96	<i>Styding of the compressive strength of corrugated paperboard by using fem-based computer simulations</i> D. Gospodinov
	102	<i>Some aspects of obtaining and use of germinated wheat seeds</i> V. Deineka, L. Deineka, N. Miachikova, V. Sorokopudov, J. Burmenko O. Miachikova, E. Miachikova
	106	<i>Changes in compozition of egg white during storage</i> N. Mija, A. Birca, L. Gaceu
110	<i>The influence of phenolic compounds from membrane septum on the phisical-chemical parameters of the walnut oil-enriched emulsion</i> C. Popovici, O. B. Oprea	
News		
	116	<i>Department of Eco-biotechnologies and Equipment for Food and Agriculture</i>

GENERAL ASPECTS REGARDING THE HEAT LOSSES IN GREENHOUSES

C. BODOLAN

GHE. BRĂTUCU

Abstract: *This paper approach the problem of heat losses in greenhouses, which took place in different forms through the transparent cover of the greenhouse due to the phenomenon of irradiation, greenhouse structure and soil by thermal conductivity, as well as through the construction joints leaky through convection. It is known that temperature is the most important factor in the plant growth and development, and the factor that raises production costs due to the fact that during the night or in the cold season the heat is produced by conventional means, also the main task of the thermal environment created inside the greenhouse is to provide enough heat to keep the plants optimal living processes, but also to protect them against frost or overheating.*

Keywords: *Heat loss, greenhouses, gardening*

1. Introduction

In green houses occurs complexes thermal phenomena of hot or cold air exchange, also taking place air circulation due to frequent ventilation.

Solar energy that enters in green houses suffers significant changes that occur largely with the passage of radiation through the material that covers construction. Inside the green houses, solar radiation contributes to the general exchange of heat. In determining the radiation and heat balance sheet, are participating complex phenomena to which contribute the temperature and humidity, evaporation and condensation, the plants, the soil, the construction and the heating ducts.

The air movement, the plant transpiration and the soil water evaporation are common phenomena which determine energy balance and the green house microclimate modifications.

In green houses occur losses and heat accumulation, and the frequent exchanges of air that strongly influence the microclimate.

Providing the optimal conditions of temperature in a green house requires dimensioning the heating system in such a manner that it can cover the specific heat loss of the building.

The way of heat exchanges in green houses is variable, by the fact that a particular used phenomenon or transfer mechanism of the energy which accounted in during the day contributes to the accumulation of heat, than it can become almost of the heat during the night and vice versa.

The amount of heat introduced in a green house should be at least equivalent to the amount of heat that is lost outwards (the green house effect). By raising the temperature will increase heat input, which will inevitably lead to the increase of losses, which otherwise explained by the increase of temperature gradient. In the same way if the outside air temperature is low it will increase heat loss.

These losses increase by 5-15% during the year if strong and cold winds are blowing.

Plants grown are actively participating to energy exchange with the environment, through the mechanisms of heat transfer.

Plant temperature is one of the essential elements of the heat transfer mechanisms in green houses. This can be determined by knowing the ambient temperature.

However, there is a difference between the temperature of the plant, which may be higher during the day and during the night lower than ambient temperature. Usually, the calculations take the indoor air temperature because it can be measured more easily than the plant temperature.

Heat losses occur through the transparent cover of the green house due to irradiation through the superstructure and greenhouses soil by conduction as well as through construction joint leak, by convection (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Main diagrammain of heat loss in greenhouse (Mad Seeman)

2. Heat loss by radiation

Mechanisms among heat transfer critical role plays infrared radiation, which influence temperature distribution in the green house. Heat exchange caused by this phenomenon can be written as a radiating balance. Constantly there is a radiating exchange (long wave lengths) between plants, soil in green houses, superstructure and exterior space.

Night-time conditions present a particular interest, since during that period becomes the maximum thermic deficit. During the night outside atmosphere is cooled because it constantly mits radiant heat flux.

Depending on the type of material used to build transparent green houses one can make a few observations about radiation losses:

- in the case of polyethylene the irradiation is high as this material allows during the night to pass completely the thermal radiation (infrared) emitted by the greenhouse soil and vegetal carpet;

- in the case of glass, the irradiation is approximately twice lower than in the case of polyethylene, where as the glass has the property of absorbing 12%, to reflect 19%, and to allow passage there through of an approximately 69% radiation; from the 69% it was determined that 12% is used for evaporation, 38% is absorbed by plants and 17% is spread in the air; however radiating balance remains negative;

- in the case of transparent material the ideal loss by radiation must be null.

During the day, the heat in green houses increases considerably because much of the short wave length radiation spectrum that is necessary to chlorophyll absorption will be used by plants and soil green house. During the night and day time the plants temperature also depends on the material from which the green house is built.

Irradiation losses can be calculated according to Walker's relationship, as follows:

$$Q_{rad} = 4,4 \times 10^{-8} \times S \times P (T_i^4 - T_e^4) \quad (1)$$

where:

Q_{rad} - the amount of heat lost by irradiation Kcal/h;

S - surface beneath the green house coating m^2

P - Transparency empirical factor (values: PE=0.8, Glass=0.04);

T_i - indo or temperature in $^{\circ}C$;

T_e - outside temperature in $^{\circ}C$;

In irradiation losses in the green house we find the irradiation of soil and heating pipes outward, the irradiation through transparent coating as well as the own irradiation of green house roof.

The irradiation losses are smaller than convection one, but considerably higher than the losses due to conduction through infrastructure and green house soil.

3. Heat lossby convection

A substantial contribution to green house heat loss brings the convective exchange between the internal and external atmosphere. These losses have the highest weight in the global balance equation, for which almost all sizing calculations

using formulas are taking into account only losses by convection.

For example, according to the Romanian STAS, heat loss is given by:

$$Q = K * S(T_i - T_e) \quad (2)$$

where:

Q - amount of heat lost (by convection) in Kcal/h;

K - overall heat transfer coefficient in Kcal/m²;

S - surface construction elements in m².

For individual green houses covered S_c area is determined by the relation:

$$S_c = S_{fw} + S_{ss} + S_{rs} \quad (3)$$

where:

S_{fw} - front wall surface in m²;

S_{ss} - side wall surface in m²;

S_{rs} - the surface of the roof slope angle function in m².

It is obvious that, the lower S_{ss} and S_{fw} values are at the same greenhouse surface and at the same angle of slope roof inclination, the lower is the covered surface.

For block greenhouses the S_c relationship remains the same, but the expression component terms are determined as follows:

$$S_{fw} = 2n \left(a * h + \frac{a^2 \tan \alpha}{4} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$S_{ss} = 2b * h = 2h * \frac{S_c}{a+n} \quad (5)$$

where:

S_{ca} - cultivated land area in m²;

n - number of compartments in the greenhouse block;

a - width of a compartment in m²;

b - length of the greenhouse, in m;

h - the height of the side wall, in m;

α - angle of the roofs lope in degrees.

Manescu and Giuvelea (1972) use the sealing coefficient of heat transfer greenhouses that leaks out wards:

$$K_{et} = \frac{\alpha_i + \alpha_e}{\alpha_i + \alpha_e} \quad (6)$$

And is noted:

$$\Delta L = \frac{t_i - t_e}{T_i - T_e} \quad (7)$$

However, it is considered that in the convective heat losses there is a global coefficient of heat transfer by convection that depends of the degree of sealing, wind speed and the value of the ratio ΔL:

$$K_{conv} = K_{et} [1 + \pi_n * K_{et} * \Delta L] \quad (8)$$

Valuable the K_{conv} varies between wide limits, depending on the penetration factor π_n. The variation of π_n, depends on the values of n. Between 1.7 and 2 is for greenhouses with a high

degree of sealing and between 0.10 and 0.25 for less sealing ones. Therefore, there is a formula that is similar to the one that calculates the heat loss (by convection) according to Romanian standard.

If in the expression used by standards, K has average values varying between 6.3 and 6.8 after Businger, quoted by VanWilk, Manescu and Giuvelea (1972) found values of K_{conv} that varies between 2.48 and 8.15 depending on π_n, such that the formula in standards may, in fact, take the following expression:

$$Q_{conv} = K_{conv} * S * (T_i - T_e) \quad (9)$$

Besides the heat lost through construction elements and warm air infiltration to exterior due to imperfect sealing (joints, cracks, defective joints constructive elements, broken windows, broken plastic), a certain amount of heat (Q_{inf.}) is lost due heating the cold air that enters in the greenhouse from the surrounding atmosphere. In this case,

$$Q_{inf} = 0,31 * V * (t_i - t_0) \quad (10)$$

The heat consumed for heating the infiltrated air is conditioned by the wind speed, the length of leaks, the glass or plastic quality and the pressure difference between inside and outside air. Nafrady (1953) proposed the following mathematical expression:

$$V = L * a * (p_k - p_e)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (11)$$

where:

Q_{inf} - heat consumption for heating the infiltrated air emissions in kcal/h;

0.31 - specific heat of air Kcal/m³deg;

V - the volume of infiltrated air m³/h;

L - length of cracks in them;

a - quality windows factor (3 ... 10);

(P_k - P_e) - pressure difference between indoor and outdoor air in the inches of mercury.

In addition to these factors an important role plays the side wall sheight and wind direction and intensity at the existing leaks level.

As a result of these influences was found underneath the transparent coating that the temperature differences between the peripheral area of the green house (low temperatures) and the central (higher temperatures). As the wind strength increases is established (according to the experiences of Manescu and Giuvelea at Popesti Leordeni IAS) that horizontal movement of cold air infiltration in the direction of the central area is difficult due to up drafts of warm air, which forms at he "buffer" in the cold air. To this is added the resistance of vegetal carpet.

4. Heat loss in soil

Represents more or less weight to heat loss, depending on the convective heat transfer regime, of water evaporation from the soil and the physico - thermal cultivated land . Heat loss through the soil is conditioned by the fact that land is artificially heated or through solar energy. The loss of heat in the soil may be its depth, vertically or perimeter horizontally. From observations can be noted that the nature of the soil, the groundwater, irrigation regime and ground moisture directly affects heat loss, even temperature distribution in the soil. Convective heat transfer increases with the speed of movement of the air at the surface of the soil, which leads to increased heat loss by 5-20 % , depending on the coating system of the greenhouse . Also, the low values of air temperature above ground and elevated temperature at the soil surface, loses a large amount of heat due to convection $Q_{conv.s}$. In this case,

$$Q_{conv.s} = \alpha'(t_{ss} - t_{vs}) \quad (12)$$

Where $(t_{ss} - t_{vs})$ represents the difference between temperatures at the soil surface and ground proximity, and the coefficient α' characterizes the conditions for the heat exchange between the soil surface and the layer of air adjacent to a wind speed up to 5m/s.

Heat loss by evaporation of the soil is determined using the equation proposed by Korolkov (1955);

$$Q_{ev} = 0,6 * G \quad (13)$$

Where 0.6 is a number characteristic and G results from Dalton's equation:

$$G = \eta(21,9 + 17,8v) * (p_{ss} - p_{vs}) \quad (14)$$

where:

QEV - the amount of heat lost through the ground water evaporation in Kcal/h;

G - the amount of water evaporated in g/m²h;

v- wind speed in m/s;

η - coefficient equal to 0.3 that shows the reducing of evaporation from the soil surface compared to the slick surface;

P_{ss} - pressure of water vapor on the surface, in mm of mercury;

P_{vs} - pressure of water vapor in the vicinity of the ground in mm of mercury;

22.9; 17.8 – Characteristic numbers.

However, the heat lost from the soil by evaporation does not greatly affect the heat balance of the greenhouse because it is found in moist air inside the greenhouse. Some of this heat is transferred by condensatont hrough the roof

when indoor air reaches saturation and is deposited on glass or plastic roof as acont inuous film or droplets of water.

5. Heat lossthroughthermal conductivity

In greenhouses, these losses are quite small compared to the losses by convection, but are not negligible. However, in building the greenhouses are meet two components contributing to the loss of heat through thermal conductivity: the element sof construction and greenhouse cover (infrastructure and superstructure) and soil in the greenhouse. Following the convective heat transfer from greenhouse construction elements will heat and contact with the outside will lose heat accumulated on their inner surface. This mechanism of heat transfer is characterized by the coefficient of thermal conductivity λ of the material of infrastructure or superstructure are made. For the calculations below are given somevalues of λ for the different materials used (Table1).

Table 1: Values of λ forvarious materials

<i>Materials</i>	<i>λ calculated in Kcal/m²h.grd.</i>
Steel	50
Aluminum	107
Simple concrete base	1,20
Fir wood	
- transversal fiber	0,15
- longitudinal fiber	0,30
Oak wood	
- transversal fiber	0,20
- longitudinal fiber	0,35
Glass	0,65
Plastic	0,045

The amount of heat taken by the ground may be calculated according to Kurtener (1969):

$$Q_s = \lambda S \int_0^{\tau_m} \frac{dT(0,\tau)}{dx} * d\tau \quad (15)$$

where:

λ - coefficient of thermal conductivity;

$T(0, \tau)$ - the temperature of the soil surface at the τ time;

$[0, \tau_m]$ - the time interval in which the heating installation operates and there is solar radiant energy intake. The soil moisture content caused

by the irrigation mode or under ground water depth it affects the thermal properties of the soil, which refers to:

- thermal capacity per volume unit $C = \rho C_p$ in $\text{Kcal/m}^3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ depends on the thermal capacity of different soil components, respectively;

Wet soil have higher heat capacity than dry soils that require more calories to be brought to a certain temperature (optimal);

- soil thermal conductivity λ increases with raising soil moisture, air is bad conductor;

- thermal diffusivity is given by the ratio between A and C (in the case of the ground homogeneous and isotropic values of these two magnitudes are constant in depth).

At greenhouse heating through heating pipes, Vander Post (1960) concluded that 90% of the total heat disposed of by the heat spreads in the air and only 10% warms the greenhouse soil.

Conclusions

Reducing heat loss in greenhouses is focused on two main areas such as reducing losses due to convective exchange and reducing the soil losses by conduction.

Heat losses occur through the transparent cover of the greenhouse due to irradiation through the super structure and greenhouse soil by conduction as well as through construction joints leak, by convection.

At building greenhouses are found two components contributing to the loss of heat

through thermal conductivity: the elements of construction and greenhouse cover (infrastructure and over structure) and soil in the greenhouse.

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WAY TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF ALTERNATIVE FEEDSTUFFS

O. OZHERELEVA, E. KRYVENKO, I.CHEREMUSHKINA

Abstract: *The paper discusses the prospects for the use of alternative plant materials in the diet of livestock, poultry and fisheries. Received a comprehensive assessment of quality feed products. Based on the analysis it was concluded feasibility of an alternative plant material in the feed, which contributes to: increase the weight gain of animals, birds, fish, leads to the replacement cost components included in the feed to cheaper raw materials of plant origin, provided that the nutritional value is not reduced, and the terms and conditions of storage meet the requirements.*

Key words: *feed efficiency, traditional technology, alternative energy, livestock, poultry and fish farms, the price, and grain.*

1. Introduction

The problem of providing feed livestock, poultry and fish farms is a major in the production of meat and a fundamental factor in determining the structure of animal agriculture, and most importantly pricing policies on meat and fish products. In the traditional technology produced mixed feeds, the share of grain components is 60-80 % , which is comparable with the components necessary for human nutrition, with the world's grain reserves are reduced from year to year.

The constant drive to increase grain production hopelessly behind the growth of consumption associated with an intense increase in the ability of consumers in developing countries.

The result of this development may be an increase in the price of grain on the world market. At the same time, it should be noted that in all countries there are constantly accumulating a significant amount of underutilized or even unused agricultural residues, livestock, crops, grain processing and other industries that are a result of additional treatment may acquire properties in the 1,5-3,0 feed times superior cornmeal good quality, as well as have a number of important and desirable properties that do not have cornmeal. Approximately 1 kg of feed grain mixture has 5 kg of vegetable waste, 4 kg of animal waste and 1 kg of food waste, not including plant waste engineering industries.

The number of secondary resource in the food industry is 60 ... 80% of the feedstock, and in some cases up to 95 %. Potentially possible

revenues from the sale of products derived from different types of waste can many times exceed the income from the sale of the main product, and allow no additional cost to the cultivation of grain, to raise the overall profitability of at least 350-400 %.

Unfortunately, in its original condition, most waste is not compatible with the traditional technologies of food production because of its physical and mechanical properties, and also have a low nutritive value due to the presence of a good number of hard hydrolyzing polysaccharides and low content of digestible protein, and some of wastes contain components that constrain their use in animal feed.

Therefore, the search for new raw materials and alternative methods of producing feed products, improve product quality while reducing the cost of their production, as well as the development of related sources of energy - is relevant and is one of the main tasks of the agricultural sector of the economy (fig. 1).

2. The results of research

In most developed countries, there is a steady decline in the number of whole grains produced in compound feed. In Western Europe - in the proportion of feed grains is only 12 - 15 %, which is 4-5 times less than in the domestic feed production.

In addition to feed grains contain a large number of components of non-traditional materials, including made from agricultural waste, animal and plant breeding, processing of secondary raw materials and food industries.

Fig. 1. Prospects of alternative raw materials

The existing well in the domestic feed production dependence on grain components automatically puts all livestock, poultry and fish farms in a rigid connection to the weather conditions, yield, commercial interests in land use, with the state of the food market as well as export-import policy of the state.

And as a result of the current situation - the reduction of agricultural population and the relatively high excess capacity in the grain processing industry.

Escalating rates of economic development in the agriculture, food and forestry industry also has been exacerbated by the use and disposal of related waste.

Irrationally used straw, waste grain and milling industry screenings, bran, corn stalks and any other crop residues and plant waste liquor, beer and confectionery.

Moreover, the amount of vegetable waste is several times the share of the target grown produce.

Another example is the direct application to the land as organic fertilizer plant waste (chopped straw, foliage, etc.) leads to the fact that nitrogen in soil necessary for the plants, is not used to supply the root system, and processes for the decomposition of organic residues.

Another critical issue, putting many agribusinesses to the brink of bankruptcy, is the exorbitant cost of energy. Although these same facilities in disparate amounts burned or thrown into the dustbin of its attendant waste that the rational use can be reduced by 60-80 % of their energy problems.

Thus, the production of raw materials, little-used but potentially suitable for feeding purposes, many times greater than the volume of specially produced forage components.

And the amount of feed that can be obtained from unused waste, significantly exceeds the total demand for the raw feed region. No less than 50 % of cultivated area, focused on the cultivation of forage crops can be safely sent to the cultivation of food crops destination.

As for the food industry wastes, they are rich in nutrients, are harmless, are easier to enzymatic and microbial processing different types of pre-processing.

These resources are considered as the most promising alternative technologies for the development of fodder production.

As for the raw materials used, any plant material and its derivatives are available for microbiological treatment of carbohydrate -protein forage crop associations of micro-organisms: plant components of agricultural crops of grain-processing industry wastes, wastes canning and wine industry, sugar industry waste, waste brewing and malting industry, waste alcohol industry, waste starch industry, tea industry wastes, wastes ether- oil- industry, oil industry wastes, wastes confectionery and dairy industries.

Thus, stocks of raw materials for the production of feed for Alternative Technology - unlimited.

Along with the processing plant and conditioned grain components, some technologies can recover and multiply the previous feed raw material properties, contaminated food pathogens, spoiled by insects or partially decomposed due to improper storage.

At the stage of production in sub-standard components eliminates harmful microorganisms, pathogens of serious diseases (brucellosis, tuberculosis, cholera, typhoid, and others), as well as harmful protozoa parasites (roundworms, tapeworms, and others).

At the same time, feeding value substandard raw materials after appropriate treatment than feeding value conditional analogues in 1,1-1,4 times.

Alternative technologies provide fodder receive zoo technical feed with high quality and performance.

The resulting food is highly nutritious, easier digestibility, biological activity, and the enzyme, vitamin and mineral value.

As in conventional feed, products obtained by alternative technologies or using alternative raw materials, comply with accepted standards for nutrient content and the required set of vitamins and minerals, the animal is safe, certified, and are environmentally friendly.

The average cost of producing 1 kg of feed for innovative technologies using alternative types of vegetable raw materials are commensurate with the cost of 1 kg of feed grain, and on the nutritional value of feed grains higher than those in 1,5-2,1 times.

Conclusions

Nowadays mixed feed industry is experiencing a rise in its development. Many large farms are constructing feed enterprises in their territories, as well as large mixed feed plants that survived hard times, are increasing their production volumes. In practical activity of these industry companies special attention is given both to improvement of the quality of mixed feed and ensuring maximum of genetically determined productivity by the use of highly nutritious animal feed, but the "economic" productivity too. Realities of modern market make it necessary to use animal feed, balanced with taking into account the availability of nutrients by using cheaper components. All this makes us carry out more extensive studies on the effect of different approaches to the processing of non-traditional raw materials of animal and plant origin including enzyme preparation use to improve their digestibility, to increase the productivity of livestock and poultry and to reduce the feed cost. In conclusion, it is worth noting that the main feature of alternative technologies is integrated feed production, which is the ability to simultaneously address the major issues of agricultural enterprises: first, to ensure high-quality forage management, and secondly, environmental issues - waste management, and thirdly, energy and heat supply enterprises.

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DEVELOPMENT OF BIOTECHNOLOGY COMBINED FOOD SYSTEMS BASED ON PLANT SYSTEMS FOR SPECIAL NUTRITION

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Abstract: *One of the priorities of the food industry is expanding the range of healthy foods with Standardized nutrients and energy increased shelf life, taking into account economic and social factors. Creating these products is currently being developed through the use of functional ingredients, ensuring the consumption of fortified foods increase the body's resistance and, consequently, decrease the incidence of all categories of the population.*

Key words: *special nutrition, cake wheat germ, pumpkin seed cake, cake amaranth seeds, millet patties, meatballs wheat.*

1. Introduction

Balanced nutrition - one of the most important components of a healthy way of life of any person. However, nutritional status in our country lately continues to deteriorate, resulting in an increase in the incidence of diseases that have in the recent past is almost never met. This dietary deficiency disease of varying severity - protein and protein-energy malnutrition, hypovitaminosis, deficiency of macro- and micronutrients that are widely spread among the population of our country. In this regard, one of the priorities of the food industry is expanding the range of healthy foods with extended shelf life for different population groups with high consumer and functional properties.

One of the methods is the introduction of natural products of plant origin, containing a significant amount of protein, essential amino acids, vitamins, minerals and dietary fiber.

2. Material and methods

One of the valuable secondary raw materials are wheat germ oil cakes, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds produced during the production of appropriate oils by cold pressing. These cakes

have a high biotechnological potential due to the unique fatty acid (a high content of essential fatty acids), protein (30% complete protein) and vitamins (high natural content of tocopherol, retinol) formulation, which makes them promising application in food products technology, designed for functional, or a special diet [1,2].

3. Results and methods

Chemical, vitamin and mineral composition of plant materials is presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3. In order to develop technology combined food systems with improved consumer and functional properties of the formulation in meat balls and meat balls wheat millet cake injected wheat germ, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds. To eliminate the effect of particle size on the quality indicators zhmyhov finished culinary products was performed them grinding to a particle size of $0,5 \pm 0,01$ mm, was introduced into the formulation of experimental products, replacing them partially millet and wheat groats in a range of 8,0-12,0 %.

Meat balls recipe millet and wheat with wheat germ oil cake (sample number 1), amaranth seeds (sample number 2) and pumpkin seeds (sample number 3) are shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1. The chemical composition of plant materials

Fig. 2. Vitamin composition of plant materials

Fig. 3. The mineral composition of plant materials

Table 1. Formulations meat balls with millet and wheat germ oil cake wheat (sample №1), amaranth seeds (sample № 2) and pumpkin seeds (sample № 3)

Indicator	Millet patties				Wheat meat balls			
	Control	Sample№1	Sample№2	Sample№3	Control	Sample№1	Sample№2	Sample№3
Millet, wheat	31	19	19	23	31	20	20	19
Wheat germ oil cake	-	12	-	-	-	11	-	-
Amaranth seed soil cake	-	-	12	-	-	-	11	-
Pumpkin seed oil cake	-	-	-	8	-	-	-	8
Milk	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Water	62,5	62,5	62,5	62,5	62,5	62,5	62,5	62,5
Sugar	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Eggs	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Crackers wheat	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Weight semifinished	113,5	113,5	113,5	113,5	113,5	113,5	113,5	113,5
CookingOil	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Massafinished meat balls	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

The content of vitamins, macro-and micronutrients in the meatballs millet and wheat cake with the addition of wheat germ, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds are presented in Table 2.

Indicators of biological value and energy value of millet and wheat meat balls with the addition of wheat germ cake, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. The content of vitamins, macro-and micronutrients in the meatballs millet and wheat cake with the addition of wheat germ, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds

Name of the component	Consumption rates, mg /day	Millet patties				Wheat meat balls			
		Control	Sample№1	Sample№2	Sample№3	Control	Sample№1	Sample№2	Sample№3
Proteins, gm	60 - 104	5,4	8,02	5,9	6,2	5,6	7,05	6,1	6,5
Fats, gm	60 – 150	6,17	6,8	6,8	6,5	6,35	6,97	6,94	6,78
Carbohydrates, gm	300 - 590	27,9	25,5	27,6	26,6	28,4	26,5	27,45	27,38
Fe, mg	10 -18	2,4	2,52	2,4	2,6	2,36	2,57	2,43	2,5
Ca, mg	1000	42,38	135,14	78,4	46,78	45,3	127,5	79,4	47,8
Na, mg	1300	47,66	44,38	165,32	49,07	49,5	47,25	153,4	51,2
K, mg	2500	115,23	221,91	256,12	176,65	117,58	226,3	258,6	164,6

P, mg	800	108,54	238,98	140,85	143,23	105,6	228,5	137,67	139,4
Zn, mg	12	0,54	3,01	0,8	1,36	0,46	4,05	0,86	1,46
Mg, mg	400	21,3	24,5	34,36	41,52	22,6	25,13	36,21	40,57
Mn, mg	2	0,29	3,1	1,95	0,6	0,27	2,97	1,85	0,55
Cu, mg	3	0,1	0,1	0,15	0,2	0,1	0,1	0,12	0,24
Vitamin B1, mg	1,5	0,09	0,45	0,1	3,0	0,08	0,36	0,14	2,45
Vitamin B2, mg	1,8	0,07	0,14	2,01	4,54	0,09	0,17	2,36	4,79
Vitamin B3, mg	5,0	3,5	4,88	3,64	3,8	3,28	4,69	3,47	3,68
Vitamin B6, mg	2,0	0,1	0,22	0,13	0,11	0,1	0,23	0,14	0,13
Vitamin B9, mg	0,4	0,01	0,25	0,6	4,3	0,01	0,23	0,46	4,1
Vitamin P P mg	20	1,05	2,12	2,46	6,6	1,03	2,1	2,37	6,4
Vitamin A, mg	0,9	0,06	0,13	0,7	0,9	0,05	0,1	0,58	0,84
Vitamin E, mg	15	0,8	4,85	1,5	3,03	0,9	4,95	1,46	3,08
Vitamin D, mg	0,01	0,01	0,012	0,014	0,011	0,01	0,011	0,013	0,011
Vitamin C, mg	90	0,3	0,32	0,31	0,31	0,35	0,37	0,32	0,31
Vitamin T, mg	300-1500	-	-	-	0,09	-	-	-	0,08
Vitamin K, mg	300	-	-	-	0,73	-	-	-	0,67

Table 3. Indicators of biological value of millet and wheat meat balls with the addition of wheat germ cake, amaranth seeds and pumpkin seeds

Indicator	Milletpatties				Wheatmeatballs			
	Control	Sample №1	Sample №2	Sample №3	Control	Sample №1	Sample №2	Sample №3
Indicators of biological value								
Difference coefficient amino-acid score, %	30,1	23,6	22,5	23,3	29,8	20,4	21,5	22,2
Biological value, %	69,9	76,4	77,5	76,7	70,2	79,6	78,5	77,8
Energy value 100 gm, kCal	151,9	154,5	156,7	155,3	149,4	154,6	153,8	154,3

Conclusions

On the basis of the experiments it can be concluded that the introduction of the test combinations optimized materials plant in meat balls recipe millet and wheat in them increases protein, carbohydrates, fat, and energy value.

With the introduction of wheat germ oil cake in the meat balls of millet and wheat daily nutrient requirement for vitamin B3 is satisfied by more than 97 % and 94 %.

At the same time the need for vitamin B9 satisfied by 60-62 %, and phosphorus - by 20-30 % in both formulations. Addressing the need for macro- and microelement composition is 5-18 %. Introduction cake wheat germ provides a product that meets the daily requirement of vitamins A and E.

Thus, it is proved that the proposed combination of ingredients designed to millet and wheat patties with pomace allows you to create food systems with high consumer and functional prop-

erties. These combinations of food ingredients made taking into account social and economic factors that ensure the continuity of the main micronutrients fortified foods for the general population.

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DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGIES OF FUNCTIONAL FOODS BASED ON THE SHRIMP WITH VEGETABLE-PART FOOD SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *One of the valuable secondary raw materials are wheat germ oil cakes, amaranth and pumpkin produced during the production of appropriate oils by cold pressing. These oil cakes have a high biotechnological potential due to the unique fatty acid, protein and vitamin content, which makes them promising application in food technology products for functional, or a special diet.*

Key words: *Chemical composition and characterization of optimized combination of plant systems, introduction to food, improving the chemical composition.*

1.Introduction

As a result of the sharp increase in the intensity of the rhythm of life, environmental problems and other factors, the actual development of "superior" food products, on the basis of their composition by essentially elements. The most promising development for the combination of vegetable raw materials with a high level of food and biological value of the raw materials of animal origin. Based on the analysis of literary sources, interesting is the development of formulations and technologies combined animal-vegetable products based on amaranth, wheat germ oil cake and pumpkin.

As a result of processing of listed plant material, cold press method with oils, vegetable main part remains oilcake nutrients (proteins, carbohydrates, fats), vitamins and minerals, biologically active substances contained in raw materials.

The meal amaranth seeds (ZSA) contains up to 16% protein (made up of more than 30% of the essential amino acids), up to 7% fat, and about 2-2, 5% dietary fiber (cellulose), a very high content of vitamins (e, a, B1, B2, B4, c, D) are very important for human body of macro-and microelements (iron, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, copper, etc.), as well as other biologically active substances (phytosterols, phospholipids, and others). In addition to the amaranth oil is squalene, which is 10 mg per 100 g of plant systems.

Wheat germ oil (ZCP) contains vitamins E, D, B1, B2, B6, pp, pantotenovu acid, carotenoids and folic; as well as macro-and microelement 21,

among them such as phosphorus, calcium, potassium, magnesium, selenium and zinc.

Pumpkin cake (ZST) is a valuable protein (up to 45% crude protein) additive and contains a large proportion of fiber (20%) and oils. The pumpkin cake includes: sugar, phytosterol, resin, organic acids, carotenoids, b vitamins, salts of phosphoric and silicic acids, potassium, calcium, iron, magnesium and zinc.

2. Matherial and methods

To date, virtually none of the plant-animal food, mass produced food cannot be optimized by zirnokislotnomu. In considering the proper composition of plant material for the best chemical composition and organoleptic characteristics are optimized and identified the best combination. Plant systems are three-and two-component ratios:

- wheat germ oil, amaranth and pumpkin - 4.5; 4; 1.5 (ZCP + ZSA + ZST);
- wheat germ oil and amaranth - 5; 5 (ZCP + ZSA);
- cake amaranth seeds and pumpkin - 6; 4 (ZSA + ZST);
- wheat germ cake and pumpkin - 9; 1 (ZCP + ZST).

3.Results and methods

Due consideration has been given to the characteristic and chemical composition of optimized combinations of plant systems (table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of plant system optimized balanced fatty acid polinenasysennym

mg/100g	ZCP + ZSA + ZST 4,5;4;1,5	ZCP + ZSA 5;5	ZSA + ZST 6;4	ZCP + ZST 9;1
Moisture	612,5	645	572,12	359
Protein	2502,6	2504,5	1065,4	3262
Fats	772,6	784,5	741,4	790
Carbohydrates	5483	5600	5948	4742
Vitamins				
Thiamine (B1)	6,9032	1,504	14,8048	6,4
Riboflavin (B2)	17,82	10,8	37	6,64
Vitamin PP	19,55	10,75	35,5	15,1
Vitamin A	4,045	03,05	7,5	1,59
Vitamin E	21,745	20,15	14,1	33,39
Vitamin C	0,0345	-	0,092	0,023
Vitamin T	0,168	-	0,448	0,112
Vitamin K	1,3785	-	3,676	0,919
Micro-and macroelements				
Sodium	403,096	500,5	607,056	2,664
Potassium	1090,5	1150	1028	1067
Calcium	496,25	560	214	725,5
Magnesium	104,4	79	176,8	60,4
Phosphorus	776	805	350	1232
Iron	4,095	4	1,32	7,53
Amino Acids				
Lysine	206,1	151,5	243,2	251,6
Threonine	141	99	178	166
Valine	181,35	114,5	246,2	214,1
Methionine	83,75	50	124,6	90,7
Isoleucine	139,6	74	221,8	149,8
Leucine	311,15	148,5	536,4	311,1
Phenylalanine	198,05	86	360,6	189,3
Tryptophan	30,3	13	54	30,6

Multicomponent vegetable systems optimized for indispensable fatty acids were introduced into experimental food system in a dispersed form, with partial replacement of traditional ingredients. Variants of recipes of dishes with the high-

est organoleptic characteristics on the basis of the perfect combination of wheat germ oil, amaranth and pumpkin seed (Experience 1, 2, 3, 4) are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Test recipes fish and plant systems

Components	Culinary products			
	Recipe 1		Recipe 2	
	Control	Experience №1, №2, №3, №4	Control	Experience №1, №2, №3, №4
1	2	3	4	5
Filletoftolstolobike	40	30	50	40
Onion	6	6	10	10
<i>Continuation of table 2</i>				
1	2	3	4	5
Carrot	-	-	15	15
Eggs	15	15	-	-
Milk	10	10	-	-

SourCream	5	5	-	-
Butter	10	10	10	10
Whitebread	7	7	-	-
Breadcrumbs	3	3	-	-
Parsley	2	2	2	2
Salt	1	1	2	2
Blackpepperpowder	1	1	1	1
ZCP + ZSA + ZST(1), ZCP + ZSA (2), ZSA + ZST (3), ZCP + ZST (4)	-	10	-	10

Analysis on contents of main components and energy value of pilot fish and vegetable dishes are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Composition and energy value of pilot fish and plant products

Massfraction of, %	Culinary products									
	Recipe 1					Recipe2				
	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4
Moisture	74,3	64.1	64.4	63.7	61.6	74,6	63.0	63.4	62.6	60.5
Protein	10,0	25,8	25,9	11,5	33,5	8,5	25,7	25,7	11,3	33,3
Fats	5,3	8,1	8,2	7,8	8,3	3,5	8,0	8,1	7,7	8,2
Carbohydrates	3,9	55,2	56,4	59,9	47,8	2,2	55,1	56,2	59,7	47,6

Comparative analysis of vitamin composition with control, produced by the traditional recipe is presented in table 4.

Table 4. Vitamin composition combination products

Components, mg/100g	Culinary products									
	Recipe 1					Recipe2				
	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Thiamine (B1)	0,11	0,79	0,25	1,58	0,74	0,09	0,76	0,22	1,55	0,71
Riboflavin (B2)	0,16	1,92	1,22	3,84	0,81	0,09	1,86	1,16	3,78	0,74
Vitamin PP	1,12	2,83	1,95	4,42	2,38	1,45	3,16	2,28	4,75	2,71
Vitamin A	96,1	94,5	94,4	94,9	94,3	50	48,41	48,31	48,75	48,16
Vitamin E	0,64	2,8	2,64	2,04	3,97	0,52	2,65	2,49	1,88	3,81
<i>Continuation of table 4</i>										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11

Vitamin C	4,36	7,96	7,96	7,96	7,96	4,83	8,5	8,5	8,51	8,5
Vitamin T	-	0,02	-	0,05	0,01	-	0,02	-	0,05	0,01
Vitamin K	-	0,14	-	0,37	0,09	-	0,14	-	0,37	0,09

Comparative analysis of macro-and microelement composition experienced combined plant system in comparison with control is presented in table 5.

Table 5. Macro-and microelement composition of fish and plant systems

Components, mg/100g	Culinary products									
	Recipe 1					Recipe 2				
	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4
Sodium	87,7	122,5	132,2	142,9	82,5	33,7	96,8	78,3	88,9	28,5
Potassium	189,2	271,7	277,7	265,5	269,4	199,0	281,6	287,5	275,3	279,2
Calcium	49,5	95,7	102,0	67,4	118,6	31,6	77,7	84,1	49,5	100,6
Magnesium	19,0	26,9	24,4	34,2	22,5	21,3	29,2	26,7	36,5	24,8
Phosphorus	141,7	198,3	201,2	155,7	243,9	124,0	180,6	183,5	138,0	226,2
Iron	1,0	1,3	1,3	1,0	1,7	0,6	1,0	0,9	0,7	1,3

Table 5 data analysis showed that the content of macro-and micronutrients has risen by 7-70%. Analysis of protein content of essential amino acids in the prototypes listed in table 6.

Table 6. Content of essential amino acids in the combined fish and plant products

Components, mg/100g	Culinary products									
	Recipe 1					Recipe 2				
	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4	Control	Experience №1	Experience №2	Experience №3	Experience №4
Lysine	857,3	713,9	708,5	717,6	718,5	842,8	699,4	694,0	703,1	704,0
Threonine	438,0	374,1	369,9	377,8	376,6	405,5	341,6	337,4	345,3	344,1
Valine	557,0	483,2	476,5	489,7	486,5	478,8	405,0	398,2	411,4	408,2
Methionine	290,3	245,7	242,3	249,8	246,4	270,3	225,7	222,3	229,8	226,4
Isoleucine	481,0	412,9	406,4	421,2	414,0	426,9	358,9	352,3	367,1	359,9
Leucine	831,9	718,1	701,8	740,6	718,1	749,2	635,4	619,1	657,9	635,4

Phenylalanine	433,1	382,9	371,7	399,2	382,1	366,0	315,8	304,6	332,1	314,9
Tryptophan	181,3	164,4	162,6	166,7	164,4	105,2	88,3	86,5	90,6	88,3

Analysis of amino acid composition of fish and plant farsevyh products with the introduction of optimized combinations of plant materials showed that major irreplaceable amino acids

products have quite high values of amino acid quick, biological value of new fish and plant products remained practically not treason (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1- The biological value of fish and plant system recipe 1, 2

Conclusions

Based on the experiments it can be concluded that the introduction of optimized combinations of plant materials in formulations combined fish and vegetable dishes increases the protein, carbohydrates, fat and energy content. With the introduction of any of the four plant system optimized balanced polinenasysennym fatty acids of the pilot of the daily requirement of the human body into vitamin A is met by more than 100%. The need for vitamin C is met by 10-15% and phosphorus to 20-30% in both formulations. Addressing the need for macro- and Elemental hair composition is 5-18%. Pilot fish of both formulations with the introduction of Amaranth oil cake and pumpkin combination provide 100% of the daily intake of thiamine needs and riboflavine. When the element composition of oil cake needs riboflavine 100% is the introduction of wheat germ cake allows you to get a product that

satisfies the daily need for vitamins A and E. the cost of pilot fish and plant products are reduced by 3-4%.

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EFFECT OF EXTRACTION CONDITIONS ON THE YIELD AND QUALITY OF OIL FROM SUNFLOWER SEEDS

A. O. ARISANU, F. RUS

Abstract: Separation of oil from oilseeds is an important processing operation. The process employed has a direct effect on the quality and quantity of protein and oil obtained from the oilseeds. Basically, two methods are used for this purpose. One is the solvent extraction method in which a solvent, when brought in contact with the preconditioned oilseed, dissolves the oil present in the seed and the separated mixture is later heated to evaporate the solvent and obtain the oil. The other method used involves mechanical oil expression. In this process, the preconditioned oilseed is passed through a screw press where a combination of high temperature and shear is used to crush the oilseed to release the oil. The objective of this study was to investigate the effects of some process conditions (nature of seeds, heating temperature and pressing time) on the yield and quality of oil mechanically expressed from sunflower seeds.

Keywords: sunflower oilseeds, mechanical expression, process conditions, oil yield, oil quality.

1. Introduction

On a worldwide scale, there appears to be an ever-growing need for vegetable oils, which is only understandable considering the advantages they present, from a dietary perspective, as compared to animal fats, namely [2]:

- more easily assimilated (unsaturated fatty acids predominate over saturated fatty acids);
- superior, from a nutritional perspective, given the polyunsaturated fatty acid content;
- less impact on cholesterol levels;
- more fit for the preparation of certain foodstuffs (mayonnaise, sauces, dressings etc.).

In nature, all plant tissues contain vegetable fats in certain amounts (0.01...75%), which would theoretically mean that there is a variety of vegetal sources from which oils for human consumption can be extracted. Practically speaking, things are very different because in industry oils are extracted only from the parts of the plant that contain vegetal fats in economically acceptable quantities (at least 15...18% of the vegetable fats, commonly found in seeds, fruits, kernels or germs).

As regards the extraction methods used, although many experiments are done to develop the procedures for the extraction of vegetable oils using supercritical fluids, and also by the GAME (Gas Assisted Mechanical Expression) method, currently, worldwide, we can talk about the existence of two dedicated extraction processes:

mechanical pressing (mechanical expression) and solvent based extraction, processes which may be applied independently or in succession, depending on the type of the raw oil, the oil content thereof and the degree of extraction required to be attained. For example, in Romania, to extract vegetable oils from oleiferous seeds, in most cases the combined process is used: pressing the seed material, ensuring oil separation of up 85...90%, is followed by the solvent based extraction, a method by which the oil is separated from the remainder (up to 99...99.9%).

2. Materials and methods

The oleaginous raw materials are numerous and most varied. Of more than 115 species of oleaginous plants, on the world market there are presently about 55, grouped in 15 important botanical families [11], namely: compositae (sunflower), cruciferae (rape), leguminous plants (soya), malvaceae (cotton), papaveraceae (poppy), rozaceae (almond tree, hazel tree), peduliaceae (sesame), vitaceae (grape seed), jugladaceae (nut tree), palmae (oil palm, coconut palm, palm kernel), foleaceae (olive tree), linaceae (flax), cucurbitaceae (pumpkin seeds), leufobiaceae (castor oil plant) and solanaceae (tomato seeds, tobacco seeds).

Due to their particular importance, oleaginous plants are being grown worldwide, the extent of each culture depending on the geographical area. Thus, if on a worldwide scale the palm tree holds the top position among the oleaginous raw materials, with 33.6% of the world vegetable oil production, in Europe, sunflower is ranked first, with 34.7% of the oil production, being closely followed by rape, with a share of 33.6%. In Romania, the mainly grown oleaginous plant is sunflower (fig. 1), with 81% of the domestic vegetable oil production. As far as the areas under cultivation are concerned, in 2013

Romania was ranked first among the EU member states; however, the average yield per hectare remained by approximately 15% lower than the means on record in the other states of the European Union.

Considering the exceptional dietary qualities and the numerous industrial uses of sunflower oil, and on top of that the prospect of using it on a large scale, together with the rapeseed oil, as a biofuel – biodiesel to be more precise, the materials which constitute the subject matter of this paper are the oleaginous sunflower seeds (hulled and unhulled sunflower oilseeds).

Fig. 1. Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) [11].

Sunflower seeds (fig. 2) are achenes of variable dimensions (5...26 mm in length, 3...10 mm in width and 2...8 mm in thickness), generally in an elongated shape, pointed at the end attaching to the head. The chemical composition of the achenes is set forth in table 1, and they consist of a pericarp (hull), with a weight of 14...28% of the total weight of the seed (tab. 2), of a ligneous consistency, ashy, white,

black-coloured or striped, and the oleaginous kernel, which can store up to 62...68% oil content [1, 6, 7].

As may be seen from the data contained in table 1, besides the high oil content, oleaginous seeds also contain significant quantities of protein substances, which is why sunflower is classified as a high-protein oil content plant (oleoproteic plant) [6].

Table 1. Chemical composition of sunflower oilseeds [1, 6, 7]

DESIGNATION	VALUE
Humidity, %	9...11
Raw oil, %	44...48
Gross proteins, %	18...20
Non-nitrogenous extractive substances, %	10...15
Cellulose, %	14...18
Ash, %	2...3

Table 2. Main characteristics of sunflower oilseeds [1, 6, 7]

DESIGNATION	VALUE
Hectolitre weight, kg/hl	38...42
Hull content, %	14...28
Equivalent diameter, mm	5.64
Density, kg/m ³	730
Bulk density, kg/m ³	438
Porosity index, %	40

Fig. 2. Sunflower oilseeds [8].

3. Results and discussions

To separate the vegetable oil from the sunflower seeds, the combined process is almost always used in industry practice, namely the pressing of the oleaginous material, which enables an oil separation of up to 85...90%, followed by solvent extraction, whereby the remaining oil is being separated (99...99.9%) [6].

The combined procedure (expression-solvent extraction) is applied in the processing of oleaginous raw materials with a minimum oil content of 30%. Raw materials with lower oil content are directly processed by solvent extraction, as the low yield of their expression does not justify the costs generated by this method [1, 6, 7].

Depending on the characteristics of oleaginous sunflower seeds, the degree of equipment of the processing facilities and the desired extraction degree, there are 5 main categories of oleaginous material which can be subjected to extraction by pressing: oleaginous seeds as such (having reached technological maturity, dried but unshelled, ground or

hydrothermally processed), ground unshelled oleaginous seeds, ground unshelled but hydrothermally processed oleaginous seeds, ground shelled oleaginous seeds, ground shelled and hydrothermally processed oleaginous seeds.

Considering the above, we may note that the grinding of oleaginous sunflower seeds is an omnipresent operation in the vegetable oil processing technologies (except for the first situation, very rarely met in current industrial practice on account of the low quality of the obtained oil). As regards the hulling of the oleaginous seeds and the hydrothermal processing of the ground seeds, although these perceived as optional operations, both the quality of oil and that of the resulting seed meal, as well as the enhancement of extraction yields, greatly depend on their application.

Due to their chemical composition characterized by a low botanical oil content (0.5...6%) and a high cellulose content (up to 60% in the case of sunflower seeds), the hulls of oleaginous seeds are an inert material in

processing and unwanted in the composition of the seed meal. Therefore, as far as this is possible, hulls are partially eliminated by oleaginous seed shelling or hulling (a certain percentage of hulls – approximately 8...10% in the case of sunflower seeds – is not removed from the hulled material because it ensures optimal conditions for grinding and pressing). Considering that the hulling of oleaginous seeds involves two steps: cracking and separating the hull from the kernel, and separating the hulls from the resulting mixture, respectively, in order to obtain satisfactory results both from a technological and an economical point of view, only those oleaginous seeds with a high content of hull, which is loosely attached to the kernel shall be put through a hulling process [1].

In the case of sunflower seeds, the main advantages derived from the hulling thereof lie in the:

- improvement in the quality of seed meal, by reducing the cellulose content and increasing the protein content: the seed meal obtained from unhulled sunflower seeds contains approximately 25% protein substances and 25...28% cellulose, that obtained from partially hulled seeds (10...12% hull remaining in the hulled material) contains 35...37% protein substances and 18% cellulose, while the seed meal obtained from mostly hulled seeds (6...8.5% hull remaining in the hulled material) contains 40...42% protein substances and 12...14% cellulose [1];
- increase in the processing capacity of the grinding rolls, of the hydrothermal processing facilities, of the pressing equipment, as well as of the extractors;
- reduction of equipment wear, especially on the grinding rolls and presses, given that the sunflower seed hull contains silicon dioxide, which is an abrasive material;
- reduction of oil losses occurring during the expression and solvent extraction processes;
- reduction of the wax content in the raw press oil (waxes, due to their high melting point, give to the oil a specific cloudiness – white sediments on the bottom of containers – for which reason these are being removed during the refining process through winterization);
- salvage of hulls and their use as fuel, in the manufacture of various products (furfural) or as an ingredient in forage for ruminants (ground hulls easily absorb molasses) etc.

The hydrothermal conditioning of the ground oleaginous seeds is an integral part of the

material preparation operations preceding oil extraction by pressing and sometimes even solvent oil extraction [1, 6].

After the grinding of the hulled or unhulled oleaginous sunflower seeds and the hydrothermal processing of the resulting ground seeds, the technological process of vegetable oil extraction from sunflower seeds continues with the pressing of the hydrothermally processed oleaginous material. For that purpose, the oleaginous material heated at temperatures comprised between 60 and 90 Celsius degrees (in the case of sunflower seeds) can be transferred from the hydrothermal processing system directly inside the feeding vat of the pressing equipment. The results of the experimental researches have pointed out that in this temperature range (60...90 Celsius degrees), a maximum extraction degree can be attained (fig. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) and at the same time the obtained oil is of the highest quality, for which reason the ground oleaginous seeds are transferred from the hydrothermal processing system directly to the pressing equipment without any intermediate processing [1, 2, 3, 6, 12]. Temperature is parameter acting in several ways on the pressing performance. The rise in temperature causes a decrease in oil viscosity favorable to its flowing, but it can also alter the cellular structure and plasticity of the raw material [3, 4, 10]. Following the introduction of the oleaginous material into the pressing chamber, the first thing that occurs is the separation of oil (over a short period of time) without any exterior action, only through the effect of the gravitational field and of the pressure of material layers. This first phase unfolds as a sheer filtering process under the influence of a hydrostatic pressure. The actual pressing process is achieved through the action of an active organ (piston or screw), which initially achieves a compression of the oleaginous materials aimed at eliminating air pockets by evacuating the air existing between the particles of ground seeds. This is followed by the separation of the oil kept on the surface of the particles due to the surface forces of the molecular field, through the channels formed between the particles [1, 6]. The increase in the pressing forces engenders a decrease in particle volume, which causes the oil to be eliminated from the particle capillaries, at the same time as the separation of the oil existing on the surface thereof. The increase in the pressure exerted on the ground oleaginous seeds needs to be gradual, so that the finely ground particles do not obstruct

the capillaries thereby blocking oil evacuation [1, 6]. When the space between the surfaces of two particles becomes so narrow that the oil film is subjected to the retention forces exerted by both particle surfaces, the oil cannot be eliminated

anymore, the film breaks in several places, the surfaces hit one against the other and the so-called oilseed cakes are formed (the cake is a valuable source of protein for animal feeds).

Fig. 3. Average oil recovery over time from hulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 30 MPa.

Fig. 4. Average oil recovery over time from unhulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 30 MPa.

Fig. 5. Average oil recovery over time from hulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 50 MPa.

Fig. 6. Average oil recovery over time from unhulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 50 MPa.

Fig. 7. Average oil recovery over time from hulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 80 MPa.

Fig. 8. Average oil recovery over time from unhulled sunflower seeds for various applied pressures and pressing temperatures – pressure: 80 MPa.

Conclusions

Sunflower oil is an excellent edible oil which has come to be more and more appreciated in modern dietetics due to its high unsaturated fatty acids content (85...91%) mostly represented by the oleic and linoleic acid (up to 65%), one of the essential nutritive fatty acids. Unlike the other vegetable oils, sunflower oil ideally combines the high nutritive value with stability and a long shelf-life, owing to the absence of the linolenic acid. From this perspective, no other vegetable oil can stand comparison.

Temperature is parameter acting in several ways on the pressing performance. The rise in temperature causes a decrease in oil viscosity favorable to its flowing, but it can also alter the cellular structure and plasticity of the raw material.

The results of the experimental researches have pointed out that in this temperature range (60...90 Celsius degrees), a maximum extraction degree can be attained and at the same time the obtained oil is of the highest quality.

Vegetable oil extraction by pressing hulled and thermally processed sunflower seeds is the most adequate modality of increasing the extraction degree and the quality of obtained oil and oilseed cakes.

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HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENTS IN OIL EXTRACTION METHODS AND PRESENT PRACTICES OF OIL EXTRACTION

ADRIAN-OVIDIU ARISANU*

Abstract: *On a worldwide scale, obtaining quality vegetable oils greatly depends on the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the raw materials, as well as on the extraction procedure (mechanical expression, solvent extraction, supercritical extraction and gas assisted mechanical expression – the GAME method). The issue of vegetable oils extraction from oleaginous raw materials is quite topical nowadays, being a major concern both for specialists, who are permanently working on finding solutions intended to improve this process (increasing extraction efficiency, reducing energy consumption, introducing various environmentally friendly technologies), but in the present situation, when the humanity is faced with a serious economic crisis, potential consumers seem to grow more and more concerned about this issue.*

Keywords: *mechanical expression, solvent extraction, supercritical extraction, gas assisted mechanical expression, oil quality, oil yield.*

1. Introduction

Vegetable oils are one of the oldest classes of chemical compounds known to mankind and even the famous Homer concerned himself with the use of vegetable oils [8]. Numerous references and clues are found that indicate the use of these oils during Stone Age and Bronze Age. During the Egyptian times, the sesame plant had a mythical status. In certain ceremonies, black sesame seeds were used to represent problems and regrets and were ritually burned [8]. Nowadays, the view on oilseeds and oils is slightly more down to earth: the oils are used in food, paint and the market for renewable fuels is growing rapidly. World market for oils and fats is approaching 400 million metric tons of seed produced every year, resulting in a total amount of oil of around 100 million ton [8].

In increasing markets, such as the one for vegetable oils, improvement of the production process is always pursued. In this case improvement can be obtained in three areas: oil yield, oil quality and production costs. Apart from research into optimisation of existing technologies, new technologies are developed as well [8].

Given the maturity of the existing technologies, optimisation will not result in huge improvements. When large improvements are required, new technologies have to be developed.

Oilseeds are a very important component of modern agriculture, for they provide easily available and highly nutritious human and animal

food. Oil crops and their products are the second most valuable commodity moving in world trade [3]. Nutritionally, oils obtained from oilseeds provide the calories, vitamins and essential fatty acids in the human diet in an easily digested form and at a relatively low cost. The deoiled or partially deoiled cake, remaining after the oil has been extracted, is a valuable source of protein for animal feeds [3].

2. Historical developments in oil extraction methods

Over the centuries, three basic methods of separation of oil from oilseeds, nuts and fruits have been evolved.

The first, which is now almost obsolete, was the wet rendering method. In this primitive method, oil-bearing material was boiled in water leading to partial separation of oil, which was skimmed off the top of the vessel.

The second method was mechanical pressing of oil-bearing material which has been practiced for thousands of years. The mechanical presses can be classified as hydraulic presses and screw presses.

The hydraulic press (fig. 1), so named because it works on the principle of the hydraulic ram, operates like an ordinary machine shop press. It originated in England and was first patented in 1795 by Joseph Bramah in England. In this original unit, pressure was put on a stationary

mass by levers, screw jacks or hydraulic cylinders, and the oil flowed from the compressed mass to collecting rings below.

Many improvements were made in this press to make it a commercially viable unit in the early part of this century [3].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the pressing process – hydraulic presses [5].

No major revolution in the development of oil expressing devices however came until the year 1900, when the first oil expeller (screw press) was developed by Anderson in the United States of America [3]. This press permitted continuous operation of hydraulic presses which resulted in greater capacities with smaller machines and less labor. Expellers quickly replaced the hydraulic presses as the major oil extraction units. Considerable improvements have been made since then, mostly by the press manufacturers, in the energy efficiency and capacities of these screw presses. The oil mill operators must determine the optimum operating conditions for

each type of seed being crushed by trial and error [3]. Although the process conditions and pretreatments used are widely known, there is a lack of systematic data on the quantitative effects of individual parameters on press performance. Despite considerable research in this area, the maximum oil recovery from any oilseed with the best of possible pretreatments rarely reaches 85...90% in commercial presses, indicating limitations of the available screw presses and the need for improvement through some fundamental research. Screw presses/expellers (fig. 2) are in present manufactured by many companies worldwide.

Fig. 2. Mechanical screw press for oil extraction: I – feeding container; II – feeding hopper; III – housing; IV – screw; V – press cylinder with oil outlet holes; VI – heating; VII – nozzle; VIII – press cake; IX – press head; X – compression zone; XI – oil collector; XII – coupling; XIII – motor; XIV – speed alternator; T1...T5 – temperature sensors; p – pressure sensor; E – torque transducer sensor.

The third method is the solvent extraction method. In a (continuous) solvent extraction process, the seeds are contacted with a solvent, generally hexane. The oil contained in the seeds is dissolved in the solvent after which solvent and solids are separated. The solvent/oil mixture is sent to the solvent recovery operation, where solvent is removed by evaporation. The residual cake is sent to a desolventiser/toaster, which also removes the solvent by evaporation. Both oil and solids therefore undergo a heat treatment, which is detrimental for the oil and cake quality. The co-extraction of undesired components further reduces the quality of the oil. However, with this method it is possible to recover almost all of the oil from the seeds. Generally, this method is used in the high(est) capacity plants [8]. To further improve the efficiency of the process, the extraction can be preceded by a pre-pressing step. Here part of the oil is recovered by a screw press, which reduces the size of the extractor and improves the permeability of the solids for the solvent [4, 7].

3. Present practices of oil extraction

When the pressure and temperature of a compound are increased beyond the so-called critical values, the interface between the liquid and vapour phase disappears. This is the supercritical state, in which properties like density and viscosity can be varied continuously between those of the liquid and the vapour state by adjusting temperature and pressure. This also allows for a large change in solubility of solutes with a relatively small change in pressure and/or temperature. This makes supercritical fluids interesting candidates as extraction solvents. CO₂ has been the most used solvent up to now, because of its relatively low critical pressure and temperature, availability, low toxicity and low cost [8].

The principle of extraction itself is similar to normal solvent extraction; however the use of high pressure has a number of complications. Up to now, no continuous feeding system for solids at high pressure is available necessitating the extraction vessels to be depressurised for feeding and pressurised for the extraction. This makes it a semi-batch process by nature. Furthermore, the solubility of vegetable oils in supercritical CO₂ (SCCO₂) is limited to a few weight percent and a large amount of solvent is required for the extraction [8]. To overcome this discontinuous operation, research is ongoing into the use of

extruders as a unit operation for SCE (supercritical extraction). The amount of solvent required is still very large.

Apart from one exception, SCE-plants for oils are focussed on essential oils, which have a different composition, higher solubility in SCCO₂, lower concentration in the raw material and higher added value than (glyceridic) vegetable oils [8].

Recently a new technique has been described for obtaining cocoa butter from cocoa nibs. This technique, called Gas Assisted Mechanical Expression (GAME), is a combination of mechanical expression and the use of supercritical CO₂ (hence gas assisted). It was shown that GAME can increase the oil yield from cocoa nibs beyond values obtained in industry at milder conditions than generally used without the need for large quantities of carbon dioxide.

In the GAME process, CO₂ is dissolved in the oil contained in the seeds before pressing. After equilibration, the oil/CO₂ mixture is expressed from the seeds. It was shown for cocoa that the dissolved CO₂ displaces part of the oil during pressing [3, 7, 8]. It was concluded that at the same effective mechanical pressure (absolute mechanical pressure minus the actual CO₂ pressure) the liquid content is the same in both conventional and GAME press cakes. The liquid in the GAME press cake is saturated with CO₂, reducing the oil content compared to the conventional cake by the same amount. The amount of this effect increases with increasing solubility of the CO₂ in the oil. Furthermore, the dissolved CO₂ reduces the viscosity of oil by an order of magnitude, which increases the rate of pressing [3, 6, 8]. After pressing, the CO₂ is easily removed from the cake and oil by depressurisation. During depressurisation of the cake, some additional oil is removed by entrainment in the gas flow [8].

Conclusions

Oilseeds are a very important component of modern agriculture, for they provide easily available and highly nutritious human and animal food. Oil crops and their products are the second most valuable commodity moving in world trade. Nutritionally, oils obtained from oilseeds provide the calories, vitamins and essential fatty acids in the human diet in an easily digested form and at a relatively low cost. The deoiled or partially deoiled cake, remaining after the oil has been

extracted, is a valuable source of protein for animal feeds.

Mechanical expression is the oldest method used for oil extraction from seeds. The seeds are placed between permeable barriers and mechanical pressure is increased by reducing the volume available for the seeds. This way oil is squeezed from the seeds. In practice, this operation can take two shapes: a hydraulic, uniaxial press or a screw press (also called extruder or expeller).

Mechanical expression and supercritical extraction produce high quality oil, solvent extraction and supercritical extraction give high yields.

Mechanical expression has a low yield, solvent extraction a reduced oil and meal quality and supercritical extraction requires a huge amount of CO₂.

Recently, in United States of America, a new technique has been described for obtaining cocoa butter from cocoa nibs. This technique, called Gas Assisted Mechanical Expression (GAME), is a combination of mechanical expression (mechanical pressing) and the use of supercritical CO₂ (hence gas assisted).

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ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF POTATO SORTING AND SIZING PROCESS BY VIDEO TECHNIQUE

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Abstract: The sorting and sizing of potatoes is a process that implies two main phases, that are the eliminating of the foreign bodies and the selecting of healthy potatoes and the separation on sizes. The paper presents the analyzing of the potato sorting on the band with axes and the sorting table and the separation on sizes on the sorting sieves. These two phases are analyzed in detail and they are video recorded, as to analyze the kinematics and the dynamics of potatoes on the sorting and sizing machine. The images obtained by video recording are afterwards analyzed. The last step in this work is the correlation of the data achieved by video technique with the determinations of the sizes and masses of the potatoes.

Keywords: sorting, sizing, potatoes, data, video technique.

1. Introduction

The sorting and sizing machine from the National Institute of Potato and Sugar Beet from Brasov, that represents the object of study for research theme, is composed by two parts that do the basically operations of separating healthy potatoes from the rest of the foreign bodies (left) and their distribution on different sizes (right) Fig. 1 [1].

Fig. 1. The sorting and sizing machine [1]

The description of the sorting and sizing machine

The sorting machine Bijlsma Hercules – 6000/3 is composed by the main elements:

- Reception hopper;
- The band with axes;
- The elevating band for sorting;
- The sorting table;
- The sizing sieves [1].

Fig. 2. Reception hopper

Fig. 3. The axes

Fig. 4. Elevating band

Fig. 5. Sorting table

Fig. 6. The sorting sieves on 3 sizes

Fig. 7. The main construction of sorting and sizing machine from NIPSB Brasov [1]

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The band with axes (Fig. 3) is the first active organ of the sorting and sizing machine. It takes the potatoes from the reception hopper and does the first separation of potatoes and foreign bodies, especially the soil and other adherent materials, mainly potato stems.

The mass of potatoes is undertaken by the elevating band (Fig. 4) that moves it on to the sorting table (Fig. 5). The sorting table is equipped with a series of rolls that move along a square surface.

The two above mentioned phases, that are the reception, the first foreign bodies separation and the undertaken of the mass for manual sorting and sizing, as they dispartate the mass and the unhealthy potatoes are taken away. As well, the foreign bodies that originate from the potato harvesting (soil and potato stems) are separated by the rest of the mass, constituted only by healthy potatoes.

Although the above mentioned steps are important, the greatest importance is the one of the sizing that means the separating of the sorted mass of potatoes on groups of utilization. The size separation (Fig. 6) has the greatest advantage that the potatoes may be distributed in the commercial chain [1].

2. Methods for the research theme

Preliminary tests were done by video recording of the dynamics of potatoes:

- from the prelevation hopper on the band with axes;
- from the sorting table on the sorting sieves.

The tests also aimed the recording of the frequency and amplitude of the sorting sieves.

This data gathering was taken with the aim of evaluating the kinematics of the potatoes on the sorting and sizing machine, of the types of forces that interfere (the dynamics) and as well as the effects of these on the potatoes, especially the study of the mechanical damages.

Testing equipment description

The video camera FASTCAM SA3 used in the research may record up to 120.000 fps (frames per second). It has a special connection to the PC and dedicated software. The camera may also do a dynamic analysis of the bodies [2].

Fig. 8. *The video camera FASTCAM SA3 [2]*

The video camera FASTCAM SA3 has a special memory, which is able to save images that are in a very fast movement in a format of uncompressed data. The video camera has a connection for rendering of the images and interfaces for different types of inputs and outputs, respectively for the synchronization or capturing of the signals [2].

• Correlation analysis

In the research theme, there are projected some aspect that will correlate the process of sorting and sizing with the main effects upon the potatoes, by the previous strict analysis of all of the aspects of interest regarding the sorting and sizing machine and process.

As to make this type of evaluation, it is also necessary to know the information regarding the objects that are going to be sorted, that are the potatoes. Potatoes should be analyzed under the aspect of the characteristics that could influence the sorting and sizing process. These characteristics are the sizes and the masses of the potatoes.

There were analyzed the sizes and the masses of potatoes using an electronic weigher (Fig. 9) and a electronic caliper (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9. *The electronic weigher [3]*

Fig. 10. *The electronic caliper [4]*

3. Data acquisition, interpreting and correlation

Data acquisition consisted in the filming with the camera FASTCAM SA3 of specific parts from the machine of sorting and sizing potatoes. The area of interest for the data acquisition was the band with axes and the sorting sieves.

The reason for this selection of the areas for filming was the fact that the mentioned steps are the most important in the manner of potato selection and moving on to specific parts for as the final role of separation to take act.

Fig. 11. *The band with axes highlighting*

Fig. 12. *The band with axes filming*

Fig. 13. *Preparing for filming the sieves*

Fig. 14. *The filming of the sieves movement*

At the sorting sieves, it was of interest to evaluate the frequency and amplitude of the movements, taking into account that the sieves start moving, than they move fast and the last step is when they stop moving and move only a while by the force of inarch.

As to evaluate the movement of the sieves, it was mounted a accelerometer sensor for the evaluation of the sieve's specific movements.

Fig. 15. *Sensor mounting* Fig. 16. *The sensor*

The graphics that results after the placement of the sensor on the sorting sieves was a of the type presented below.

Fig. 17. *Graphical interpreting of sieves moving*

As it can be observed, the picks on the graphic are relatively constant, but at specific moments, it can be observed an abrupt oscillation of the frequency, that means the sieves move faster, as to separate the mass of potatoes on sizes.

- **Data transfer for the interpretation**

The video camera FASTCAM SA3 was connected to a computer that has installed the specific software for data acquisition and interpreting.

Fig. 18. *The video camera's transfer point*

As a fact of computer transfer, it resulted in to specific images. The specific images were decomposed by filming with a rate of 150 frames per second (fps) [2].

There were analyzed the two specific areas of interest, that are the band with axes and the sorting sieves.

Video images decomposed

The final results consisted in the acquisition of images (Fig. 19, Fig. 20) that were decomposed with the help of the video camera's software. The rate of decomposing was at 150 frames per second (fps). The obtained images showed clearly all the aspects regarding the movement of potatoes on the sorting and sizing machine. The results of the dynamics will be correlated with the ones regarding the sizes and masses of the sorted potatoes. After this determinations, there will be emitted some conclusions in the manner of improving the process of sorting and sizing potatoes.

Fig. 19. *Axes images decomposed*

Fig. 20. *Sieves images decomposed*

Conclusions

The potatoes sorting and sizing technological flow is of great interest for the research theme. After its close analyzing, there were found two parts of interest that are the band with axes and the sorting sieves. These two phases were recorded and analyzed for the kinematics and dynamics of the potatoes on the sorting and sizing machine.

The acquired data from the video recording of the technological flow of sorting and sizing potatoes will be correlated with the measurements of the dimensions and masses of the potatoes aimed for this process.

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RESEARCH REGARDING RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF CEREAL GRAINS

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Abstract: Cereals, over time, represented a great importance to humankind, and it covered the world's largest planted area of all crops. The need for the crushing operations in the food industry results from the fact that the cereals grains are rarely used in their original shape and size. Rheological properties of the cereal grains serve as parameters for engineers designing the grain processing technologies and grinding techniques. The paper presents a research regarding the rheological properties of cereal grains by compression.

Keywords: compression, cereals grain, rheology, deformation.

1. Introduction

Cereal production and technologies processing have been subjected over the development of human civilization, to continuous improvements and adaptations to food needs of the population, serving to improve living standards. [2]

Knowing the main properties, and especially the rheological properties of food products, is the appropriate choice for cereal grain processing technologies and grinding techniques, which are leading to electing the active and working regime in cereal processing.

Rheology has been defined as “a science devoted to the study of deformation and flow”. In the material, when the action of forces results like deformation and flow, the mechanical properties will be referred as rheological properties. [5]

Moreover, rheology considers the time effect during the loading of a body. Rheology then, like a mechanical behavior of a material, is expressed in term of the three parameters of force, deformation and time. The structure of rheology is shown in figure 1. [3,5]

Fig. 1. Rheology structure [3, 5]

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Because of the complex structure, cereal grains can be considered as "colloidal-capillary-porous" bodies, and from rheological point of view showing concomitant, in certain proportions, the three basic rheological properties: elasticity, viscosity and plasticity. The granule shape deformations can be classified into one of these categories: elastic deformation, plastic deformation and viscous flow or combinations thereof.[2,3]

Deformation is the relative displacement of points within a body. Deformation like stress is a vector quantity. In general, deformation is accompanied either by change of volume or by change of shape.

The change of volume is caused by isotropic stress such as hydrostatic pressure. The change of shape is brought about by shear stresses.

Material can be deformed by uniaxial compression, uniaxial tension, shear, and bulk compression. The grains deformation can be characterized by grain elasticity and plasticity. The grains elasticity is the capacity of the material for taking elastic or recoverable deformation. In those positions of the curve (fig. 2) before the point LL is reached elongation area, in large part at least, recoverable, and is a measure of elastic deformation.

Fig. 2. Degree of elasticity from a loading-unloading curve

De – elastic or recoverable deformation; Dp – plastic or residual deformation; $De/(Dp+De)$ - degree of elasticity[6]

From the analysis of the work carried out by the grinding machinery, showed that the main applications apply cereal grains refer to the crushing and cutting.

2. Rheological Measurements

In the grinding process, materials are reduced in size by fracturing them. The mechanism of fracture is not fully understood, but in the process, the material is stressed by the action of mechanical moving parts in the grinding machine and initially the stress is absorbed internally by the material as strain energy. When the local strain energy exceeds a critical level, which is a function of the material, fracture occurs along lines of weakness and the stored energy is released. Some of the energy is taken up in the creation of new surface, but the greater part of it is dissipated as heat. Time also plays a part in the fracturing process and it appears that material will fracture at lower stress concentrations if

these can be maintained for longer periods. Grinding is, therefore, achieved by mechanical stress followed by rupture and the energy required depends upon the hardness of the material and also upon the tendency of the material to crack - its friability. The force applied may be compression, impact, or shear, and both the magnitude of the force and the time of application affect the extent of grinding achieved. For efficient grinding, the energy applied to the material should exceed, by as small a margin as possible, the minimum energy needed to rupture the material.[1,3]

A number of researchers have dealt with the behavior of solid particles, belonging to different materials to the action of concentrated forces compression, aiming to highlight the dependence of "force-deformation".

Grinding cereal grains by compression is a wide spread procedure in the grinding industry. Concerning this graining procedure, cereal grains are compressed by applying the external forces of

the compression. This grinding method is applied to plastic, plastic-elastic materials and various hard materials.[3]

The type and geometry of a compression test can vary rather widely, but the basic measuring principles are the same regardless of the testing geometry. Those basic principles are illustrated in a parallel plate testing mode, in which one plate is fixed to a force transducer and the other plate is oscillated in a sinusoidal motion. This is illustrated in Figure 3. As the top plate is moved, stress is applied to the grain kernel sample between the plates. When sufficient force is applied to the kernel, the kernel deforms, and the deformation produces a strain in the kernel.

Fig. 3. The geometric device used for grains compression [3]

Experimental investigations made for the case of regular granules, if requested by a compressive force (Fig. 4), point out that the granule mass is developed state of the work space, and as a result, a first phase grain will deform elastically and as the deformation increases the external application in the field of plastic passes and finally the particles will disintegrate with different shapes and sizes. [3,6]

The force is applied in one direction, so in the mass of the particle will appear two different areas which will be requested different: the central area (shaded) at compression and the

peripheral tension, as demonstrated by experimental research and photo elasticity.

Fig. 4. A spherical model subjected to compression [3,6]

The central area which has the form of two cones (truncated cones), having the basis at the points of application of force, and the tip (lower base) in the center of the particle, is subjected to compression, and is being called cone force. Cone force crossing particle is centered on the direction of force.

The peripheral areas of particle, outside the cone of force, is required to stretch, which is constant over a large region in the center of the particle, the tensile being more pronounced in the external surface of particle.

If the state of efforts, generated in the mass of the particle by the external force is below the elastic limit of the material, the energy consumed is converted into heat energy which is lost irretrievably.

Dependency analysis "force deformation" is a very important step to explain how the cracks propagate inside a granular medium constituted by a continuous and homogeneous particle.

Shape of the curve, which expresses the dependence "deformation - force" characteristic of the diametral compression test application with a specific speed of granules having certain moisture content, is shown in Figure 5. The grain kernel deformation, until the complete grinding, is carried out in four distinct steps.

Step I begins when the plate comes into contact with the granule application, characterized by the elastic deformation of micro asperities from the surface of the granule, the slope of the curve is reduced, which suggests a reduced rigidity thereof.

Fig. 5. Dependence on deformation - force diagram for the application of compression [3]

Stage II (AF portion of the curve) is characteristic of elastic deformation of grain, in grain mass is developing a state of space efforts. If the external load is canceled, the grain returns to its original state and form. The diagram shows a parabolic variation. The characteristic values can be calculated based on the Young's modulus, shear modulus and stiffness of grain. Slope of the curve characterizes the material rigidity of grain.

The stage III (FB portion of the curve) is characteristic of elastic-plastic deformation of granules; FB slope is a measure of elastic-plastic rigidities, which is proportional to the radius of grain (Thomas 2000). A low value of the slope of the curve indicates a higher share of the plasticity property and a higher slope reveals a high rigidity. In section B, characterized by the maximum of the resistance value of the grain, occurs the grain cracking.

Stage IV (BE portion of the curve) is characteristic grinding grain into smaller particles. In the first phase of the stage, the resistance of the particle decreases rapidly as the crack widens. The curve shows some local maximum which are due to the particle cracking new obtained.[3]

Conclusions

Knowing the rheological properties of cereal grains is important to improve the processing technologies and grinding techniques.

Grinding cereal grains by compression is a wide spread procedure in the grinding industry.

At compression, as the top plate is moved, stress is applied to the grain kernel sample between the plates. When sufficient force is applied to the kernel, the kernel deforms, and the deformation produces a strain in the kernel.

If the state of efforts, generated in the mass of the particle by the external force is below the elastic limit of the material, the energy consumed is converted into heat energy which is lost irretrievably.

The grain kernel deformation, until the complete grinding, is carried out in four distinct steps: elastic deformation of micro asperities from the surface of the granule, of elastic deformation of grain, elastic-plastic deformation of grain, grinding grain into smaller particles.

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THE ASPECTS OF VACUUM PACKAGING IN FOOD TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: *Vacuum package is packaging material used for packaging of food products that require long-term storage. Mechanical strength package ensures the safety of the packaged product at all stages of packing, transportation, warehousing and storage. Transparency and gloss packages provide good visibility of the product and improve its appearance. Good weld ability package excludes depressurization product during storage and transport.*

Key words: *barrier sealing characteristics, polymeric materials, «Sous-Vide» technology*

Introduction

Choosing a package for foodstuffs, a producer is facing with the problem of the shelf life. Polymeric materials are generally used to improve the preservation of products since the materials have the best barrier sealing characteristics, i.e. the materials are able to prevent the permeation of atmospheric gases, water vapor and off-odors. The stable atmosphere inside the package is required to prevent the development of spoilage microorganisms and keep the product safe for consumption. Vacuum-sealing is a primary way to create this atmosphere. During the process most bacteria and microorganisms are removed from the package, and a remaining portion is prevented from growth and development. In this way, the prime factor influencing the shelf life of a product inside the vacuum package is the permeability of polymeric materials.

2. Methods

A modified atmosphere packaging technique has emerged not by coincidence. The impact of carbon dioxide on food pigmentation was marked as far back as in the 18th century. It emerged that carbon dioxide sustains meat and fish natural red color for longer period than the atmospheric air develop under conditions of oxygen absence. Unlike nitrogen, carbon dioxide has high solubility in water and fats. A presence of carbon dioxide in products with high water content acidifies them and thus extends their shelf life. Carbon dioxide solubility lowers its molecular pressure in the mixture and in case of choosing CO₂ wrong concentration a package occasionally shrinks a

does. A modified atmosphere packaging is the process of inert gas sealing of products when a mixture of inert gases taken in exact proportions (nitrogen, oxygen and carbon dioxide) at 0-4 °C is required. Each gas is «responsible» for its particular function in the process whether it is the suppression of bacterial growth or the preservation of product pigmentation. Nitrogen, oxygen and carbon dioxide are basic components of gas mixtures.

Nitrogen is an inert gas used as a «diluent» (as a means of oxygen removal from a package). Nitrogen has low solubility in water and in fats, has no direct bacteriostatic effect and does not influence directly the packaged product storage life. Application of the gas allows complete oxygen remainder removal to be achieved, which means anaerobic bacteria development limitation. Maintaining of constant gas mixture concentration is easier when higher nitrogen content is provided, due to the fact that molecular pressures inside a package and in the atmospheric air are closer to an equilibrium state.

Carbon dioxide usually composing 20% of the mixture performs as a bacteriostatic component which limits and suppresses aerobic bacteria and mold growth because they are able to product the same way as it happens after vacuuming. This effect is corrected by nitrogen injection into a package. Carbon dioxide is also used to cool mincemeat and meat mixes, which extends the storage life. A cooling by liquid nitrogen and liquid carbon dioxide of meat and dough specialties eliminates a process of nutritive properties and gustatory qualities being lost and

prevents moisture and mold inside a package from being formed. On the one hand, it is oxygen which is the culprit of oxidation and fats rancidifying processes and food spoilage.

On the other hand, it is impossible to sustain red color of beef which is associated by consumers with its freshness. O₂ content can reach up to 80 % in a gas mixture inside a fresh meat package. Application of the gas mixture in the process of products vacuum packaging suppresses the growth of microorganisms on a product surface by means of maintaining its microflora adequate level, preserves its gustatory qualities, aroma and other properties for a certain period, regulates product oxygen evolution and permeation of oxygen into a package and significantly increases the product shelf life with no quality change. The lower a product pH, the less an atmosphere impact on the shelf life. It occurs because decrease of acidity leads to slower bacteria growth. In this case, the factor limiting the shelf life is not bacteria growth but chemical reactions such as oxidation, product decoloring (a packaging film is in contact with a moist product surface). If a product consists of multiple components, natural gas is added to extend the shelf life for one of the components[3].

3. Materials

It should be noted that nowadays vacuum packaging is the most progressive and efficient type of food packaging. Polymeric materials with best barrier sealing characteristics are used for vacuum packs:

- PET / PE (lavsan (polyethyleneterephthalate)/polyethylene) have good optical characteristics, allow application of interlayer printing, are suitable for packages with a «pattern». Laminate polyethylene terephthalate (polyester, polyester) and high-density polyethylene - one of the cheapest materials for the manufacture of vacuum bags. Standard thickness of Dacron (PET) - 12µm, 2-3 microns adhesive (glue), the thickness of the polyethylene (PE) depends on customer requirements: the more the percentage of PE, the denser and thus more resistant to puncture and will break package. Typically, using 60, 80, 100 and 120 microns packets in material thickness will have 12 PET // 45 PE PET 12 // 65 PE PET

12 // 85 PE PET 12 // PE 105 microns. This material polyester (PET) is a barrier layer: a good barrier to water vapor, most gases, but a low barrier to oxygen, which is critical for the storage of meat delicacies with implementation period longer than 7 days. This material is perfect for packaging frozen foods (fish, shrimp, meat, etc.), with sub-zero temperatures (-15 °C to -20 °C) shelf life can reach more than 6 months.

- PA / PE (polyamide/polyethylene) have good barrier sealing characteristics, high elasticity and high puncture resistance. The total thickness of the polyamide (PA) is usually 17-20 microns, and the thickness of the polyethylene (PE) - depending on customer requirements, - more than polyethylene, the denser will be the package. Typically used 65, 80, 90, 100 and 120 microns packages that are respectively the thickness of the materials will be: PA 20 // 43 PE, PA 20 // 57 PE, PA 20 // 67 PE, PA 20 // 77 PE 20 PA / PE 93 microns. The barrier layer here is a polyamide, it has: a good oxygen, most of gases but low barrier to water (it is hygroscopic - " get wet ", that is, it can absorb water during processing, e.g., pasteurization, hot water at a), which may lead to delamination and reducing the barrier properties. Therefore, the polyamide generally sealed on both sides with polyethylene, which has a good barrier to water. With this configuration, this lack disappears. Using these materials affects a large range of packed products from frozen foods (fish, meat semis, vegetables, fruits, etc.), delicatessen products (expensive slicing and whole pieces) banknotes to banks, medical devices and drugs. Subject to temperature shelf life: more than 3 months; in the case of frozen food - more than 12 months.

- EVOH has maximum barrier properties for transparent materials; it is intended for modified atmosphere packaging

- OPA / PE (oriented polyamide/polyethylene) have high transparency, have good barrier characteristics and allow application of interlayer printing

- Shrink vacuum bags- Also in vacuum packaging is a whole separate line - shrink vacuum bags. These vacuum bags are made of complex composite materials, using polyolefin, polyethylene, polyamide layers possible. The number of layers in them can reach 9-11 with a thickness of 45-80 microns. Shrink bags also

evacuated, and then they dipped in a hot bath (90-95 °C), then the edges and unused space package "cringe" and pressed to the package itself. The cost of such a package in comparison with the conventional vacuum to be 2-3 times more. In the market shrink bags made in Germany, Holland, Great Britain and Poland.

The primary vacuum packages producers today are Smartplast, LansPak, Kondorpak, Esko Market, Multipack, Lietpak, VakumPak, Delta pack etc[2].

Vacuum pack usage has the following advantages:

- 1) a vacuum pack prevents a product from oxidizing by atmospheric oxygen in normal conditions, which leads to loss of nutritive properties and gustatory qualities;
- 2) the lack of oxygen in a vacuum pack prevents dangerous microorganisms, which may be contained in a product, from reproduction;
- 3) during handling and storage, products may absorb circumambient odors, which leads to off-odor and off-taste, but vacuum pack usage makes it impossible;
- 4) a vacuum pack made of multilayer film prevents the product evaporation, i.e. during the entire shelf life period product has its initial water content, which is usually required;
- 5) the low cost is one of major vacuum pack advantages in contrast to traditional packages such as glass and tin;
- 6) vacuum-packed products handling requires much less space than glass, plastic or tin containers;
- 7) it is possible to overprint multilayer films with better quality and bigger number of color inks using flexographic or gravure printing unlike in case of paper label, glass or tin containers;
- 8) decrease of process losses is achieved by means of vacuum heat treatment[3].

In this connection, an application of low-temperature cooking with preliminary products vacuum packaging («Sous-Vide» technology) is one of most promising directions for the development of food technology.

The method was first described by Sir Benjamin Thompson (Count Rumford) in 1799 (although he used air as the heat transfer medium). It was re-discovered by American and French engineers in the mid-1960s and developed into an industrial food preservation method. The method was adopted by Georges Pralus in 1974 for the

Restaurant Troisgros (of Pierre and Michel Troisgros) in Roanne, France. He discovered that when foie gras was cooked in this manner it kept its original appearance, did not lose excess amounts of fat and had better texture. Another pioneer in sous-vide is Bruno Goussault, who further researched the effects of temperature on various foods and became well known for training top chefs in the method. As chief scientist of Alexandria, Virginia-based food manufacturer Cuisine Solutions, Goussault developed the parameters of cooking times and temperatures for various foods.

One limitation of sous-vide cooking is the fact that browning (Maillard reactions) happens at much higher temperatures (above the boiling point of water). The flavors and "crust" texture developed by browning are generally seen as very desirable in the cooking of certain types of meat, such as a steak. The flavors and texture produced by browning cannot be obtained with only the sous-vide technique. In many cases, meats and other foods cooked with the sous-vide technique will be browned before and/or after being placed in the water bath, using techniques such as grilling or searing on an extremely hot pan. This secondary browning is done briefly, and sometimes at higher heat than normally used, so as to affect only the surface of the food and to avoid overcooking the interior. Similarly, the skin of fish can be cooked at high temperatures after the sous-vide to make the skin crisp.

Amid many types of thermal equipment used in «Sous-Vide» technology one of the central positions belongs to the convection steamer which is a universal thermal equipment to set out and control temperature, humidity, air velocity inside a process chamber and duration of the heat treatment. A combi steamer (or combi-steamer) is a professional cooking appliance that combines the functionality of a convection oven and a steam cooker. That is, it can produce dry heat, moist heat or a combination of the two at various temperatures. The appliance is therefore fit for many culinary applications, including baking, roasting, grilling, steaming, braising, blanching and poaching.

The advantages of a combi steamer over other thermal equipment include:

- control of both temperature and humidity in the chamber, which reduces cooking time
- uniform preparation
- no need to reverse products

- if different dishes are prepared at the same time, each preserves its flavour, vitamins and nutritional value
- simultaneous processing of different products (up to 10-12 dishes) without smell mixture
- food preparation without oil, grease crust and carcinogen formation
- suitable for cooking sous-vide
- regeneration of previously prepared food without loss of moisture and/or crispness [2].
- space saving due to fewer kitchen appliances
- reduction of final product shrinkage losses
- electricity savings
- reduction of labour costs
- self-cleaning

The advantages of this technology are short cooking times and a gentle preparation method, both of which lead to enhanced vitamin and nutritional preservation when compared to traditional cooking methods.

A range of these characteristics enables one to reduce heat treatment duration as well as simultaneously the heat transfer process intensified which in turn, reduces a number of process losses of semi-finished and finished food and also contributes to higher finished product quality [1].

Conclusions

This treatment technology enables the preservation of vitamins, proteins, carbohydrates, fats, macro- and micronutrients in an unchanged state and prevents food from undesirable organoleptic changes which occur under conventional treatment. The technology retains consumer appeal of product and its hygienic safety guaranteed throughout the entire storage life.

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DEVELOPMENT OF FORMULATIONS ENRICHED MEAT PRODUCTS IN APPLYING THE SECONDARY FRACTIONS OF GRAIN PROCESSING

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M. ZYABLOV

Abstract: Developed meat and vegetable for culinary enriched grain raw ingredients with essential substances, macro-and micronutrients, with partial replacement of rice oilcake wheat germ. Products enriched broad spectrum of vital minerals and vitamins. These products have a high biological and nutritional value, balanced amino acid composition and good digestibility

Key words: wheat germ cake, meat and vegetable products, functional foods

1. Introduction

Food fortification with vitamins, missing macro- and micronutrients - is a serious interference in the traditionally existing structure of human nutrition. The need for such intervention is dictated by objective environmental factors associated with the change in the composition and nutritional value of food products we use, as well as the transformation of our way of life associated with a decrease in physical energy. For these reasons, the interference can only be based on scientifically sound principles and proven practices [1]. Foods fortified with vitamins and minerals are included in the broad group of functional foods, ie foods rich in physiologically useful food ingredients that improve human health. To these ingredients, along with vitamins and minerals, also include dietary fiber, lipids containing polyunsaturated fatty acids, beneficial species of live lactic acid bacteria. In this regard it is of interest in attracting formulation culinary products, as components, products of complex processing grain wheat germ. The aim of this study was to develop formulations and technologies for meat and vegetable products with partial replacement of rice oilcake wheat germ.

2. Materials and Methods

Wheat germ oilcake - priceless gift of nature, rich with all necessary materials. It contains 12 vitamins, 18 amino acids, 21 macro- and micronutrients. In embryos of the content of B

vitamins 3-4 times higher than in the whole grain, but by the content of calcium, this superiority is estimated figure of 1.5-2.5 times, potassium - 2.5-5 times. Main components of the wheat germ: protein ballast substances, polysaccharides, starch, oil, vitamins, trace elements and mineral substances. Wheat germ oil cake is an important source of raw materials, increase the nutritional and biological value of food. Component composition of wheat germ cake is presented in Table 1. The aim of this study was to develop formulations and technologies for meat and vegetable products with partial replacement of rice oilcake wheat germ.

Table 1.

The main components in the meal of wheat germ

Indicator (mass fraction)	Content%
Crude fat	8,0
Ash	4,3
Carbohydrates	47,0
Crude protein	33,8
Crude fiber	1,9

For the preparation of test samples of vegetable and meat products used wheat germ oil cake obtained after extraction by cold pressing oil from wheat germ, while it retains almost completely biologically active substances initial embryos [2, 3].

Comparative analysis of the amino acid composition and biological value of the investigated materials shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Amino acid composition and fast components of vegetable and meat products

Name of amino acids	Components meat-vegetable products.			
	Rice		Wheat germ oil cake	
	Mg/1g	Fast, %	Mg/1g	Fast, %
Valine	60	95	178	356
Isoleucine	47,1	92,7	111	278
Leucine	88,5	101	211	301
Lysine	37,1	42,4	225	409
Methionine + cystine	42,8	97,3	58	97
Threonine	34,3	60,7	144	360
Tryptophan	14,3	118	20	200
Phenylalanine + triozin	94,2	132	154	257

As seen from the table, and combining the protein rice flour wheat germ will significantly increase the amount of essential amino acids in the new products.

3. Results and Discussion

Wheat germ oilcake formulation was injected into the experimental product at 30 % by weight of rice. Formulations with the highest organoleptic indicators presented in Tables 3.1 and 3.2.

Table 3.1. Recipe meat-vegetable products "stuffed cabbage", "dolma" cake using wheat germ

Components	Products			
	Stuffed cabbage		Dolma	
	Contr ol	Exper ience	Contr ol	Exper ience
Wheat germ oil cake hydrated (1:1.7)	-	25	-	47
Minced pork	310	310	300	300
Cabbage	390	390	-	-
Carrots	60	60	113	113
Rice	70	45	135	88
Grape leaves	-	-	150	150
Onions	116	116	226	226
Tomato paste	20	20	23	23
Vegetable oil	20	20	-	-
Pepper	7	7	-	-
Greens	-	-	38	38
Salt	7	7	15	15
In total	1000			

Table 3.2. Recipe meat-vegetable products "stuffed peppers", "meatballs with rice" cake using wheat germ

Components	Products			
	Stuffed peppers		Meatballs with rice	
	Contr ol	Exper ience	Contr ol	Exper ience
Wheat germ oil cake hydrated (1:1.7)	-	23	-	49
Minced pork	182	182	462	462
Carrots	55	55	116	116
Egg	-	-	38	38
Rice	66	43	139	90
Red sweet pepper	440	440	-	-
Onions	110	110	230	230
Tomatoes	110	110	-	-
Salt	9	9	15	15
Pepper	11	11	-	-
Garlic	6	6	-	-
Tomato paste	11	11	-	-
In total	1000			

Technology of preparation of meat and vegetable products consisted of traditional stages: primary processing of raw materials, grinding materials, saute raw, raw cooking, forming and heat treatment products. Wheatgerm Oil cake was ground to a particle size of $0,5\pm 0,01$ mm, to eliminate particle size effect on product quality parameters of the finished product. Further wheat germ cake was hydrated with water in a ratio of 1:1,7 drinking, the mixture was stirred and maintained for 5-7 minutes to achieve a state close to the consistency of ground meat. Then all materials coalesced and kneaded until a homogeneous mass, portioned formed into semi-circular flattened and wrapped vine leaves, cabbage, chilli, and subjected to heat treatment in a combi oven for 25 minutes at temperature 240°C . Wheat germ oil cake has the following organoleptic characteristics: has a neutral smell and taste, has a creamy color, allowing you to keep organoleptic characteristics of finished products, products characteristic of meat.

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 presents the macro, trace element and vitamin composition of new products, enabling them to include product functionality.

Table 4.1. Macro, trace element and vitamin composition of products, "stuffed cabbage", "dolma" (mg per 100 g of product)

Name of the refractive mg	Stuffed cabbage		Dolma	
	Control	Experience	Control	Experience
Fe	1,16	1,25	1,22	1,31
Ca	41,8	55,4	68,41	82
Na	517,9	517,3	514,14	513
K	250,74	265	266,04	280
P	112,47	128	120,48	136
Mg	26,51	25	36,6	35
Vitamin B ₁	0,3	0,35	0,32	0,37
Vitamin B ₂	0,14	0,14	0,16	0,16
Vitamin C	10,4	10,47	9,43	9,5
Vitamin A	-	0,01	-	0,01
B-carotene	1273,8	1273,8	3065,9	3065,9
Vitamin PP	2,24	2,66	2,5	2,92

Table 4.2. Macro, trace element and vitamin composition of products, "stuffed cabbage", "meatballs with rice" (mg per 100 g of product)

Name of the refractive mg	Stuffed peppers		Meatballs with rice	
	Control	Experience	Control	Experience
Fe	1	1,1	1,12	1,2
Ca	29,25	43	41	54,6
Na	510,23	509,6	531	530
K	25857	272	216,31	230
P	106,55	122	141	156
Mg	23,82	22	25	23,2
Vitamin B ₁	0,32	0,37	0,39	0,44
Vitamin B ₂	0,14	0,14	0,18	0,18
Vitamin C	45,31	45,4	7	7,07
Vitamin A	-	0,01	-	0,01
B-carotene	444	444	253,5	253,5
Vitamin PP	2,29	2,7	2,51	3

Wheat germ oil cake has the following organoleptic characteristics: has a neutral smell and taste, has a creamy color, allowing you to keep organoleptic characteristics of finished products, products characteristic of meat.

Organoleptic parameters characterize the shape, surface, color, taste and smell, kind of fracture in new food products.

Organoleptic parameters of new meat products plant shown in Figure 1, which shows that when injected into the semi innovative plant materials organoleptic new compositions generally not deteriorated, and some positions have become even better.

Fig. 1 - Organoleptic meat and vegetable products: a - "stuffed", "dolma"; b - "stuffed pepper", "cutlet with rice"

The resulting product had a high organoleptic within 4,5-5 points.

According to the results of organoleptic studies all samples received the highest score. Taste, smell, color and shape of the surface, all the samples of meat and vegetable dishes meet the requirements of the standard. Amino acid composition (mg/1g) new meat-vegetable food products is shown in Fig. 2. Analysis of the data indicates that the level of amino acids combined experimental product meets and exceeds by some amino acids in the reference protein content. It is important that a mass fraction of vita-mins E and cover riboflavin daily requirement for 15% and more.

Fig. 2 - Amino acid composition of new combination products

The wide range of mineral substances is presented; products are especially rich with calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and manganese. Existence in products of selenium and policosanol which deficiency is referred to the most important violations of the food status of the person is especially valuable. Calculation, generalization and the analysis of data testify to the high biological value of the developed products (80-92 %). High balance on aminokislotny composition of proteins (coefficient of utility 0,83-0,88).

Conclusions

Thus, as a result of studies:

1. Developed recipes and techniques with innovative products with improved organoleptic properties;

2. Designed meat and vegetable products using wheat germ oil cakes have a high biological and nutritional value, balanced amino acid composition and digestibility of the good;

3. Meat and vegetable culinary products with the introduction to the recipe of deep processing of grain were enriched broad spectrum of vital minerals and vitamins;

4. Due to the innovative characteristics of data items, can be used as functional food.

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DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOUNDING ENRICHED FLOUR CONFECTIONERY WITH APPLICATION OF PRODUCTS OF DEEP PROCESSING OF GRAIN

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Abstract: Cookies compounding with application of products of deep processing of grain are developed. Flour confectionery in which wheat flour is partially replaced with cake of germs of wheat New products are received were are enriched with a wide range of the vital, mineral substances and vitamins. The developed products possess high rates of the biological value, the balanced aminokislотно structure and good comprehensibility.

Key words: wheat germs oilcake, flour confectionery, functional products

1. Introduction

Functional food and drinks are for today the most fast-growing segment of world food branch. Growth rates of the industry of healthy food surpass rates of development of the key food industry.

Development of production of functional products in our country became result of realization the Concept of a state policy in the field of healthy food for the period till 2020, Russia accepted by the Government. The concept as a priority task puts forward creation of conditions for development of a domestic production of products for healthy food, including functional.

The Russian market of healthy products dynamically develops now as at the expense of products of a domestic production, and the import. In the domestic market such segments of functional products as sour-milk, bakery products, grain porridges and flakes most actively grow. In other segments the enriched products are presented while is insignificant.

In spite of the fact that the global market of functional products increases, growth rates within the last several years were slowed down. Nevertheless, health remains the main driving force of marketing strategy of advance of food and drinks in many regions of the world.

Now is particularly acute a question of additional sources of the feedstuffs necessary for a human body, containing the essentialnykh components, macro - and micronutrients. The fact is that the considerable part of useful substances of

grain gets to production by-products – processing by-products. The analysis of a chemical composition of these products shows that they can serve as raw materials for production of functional food, thus there is more rational use of products of deep processing of grain [1, 2].

In this aspect cakes of cereal cultures, in particular the wheat germs oilcake (WGO) are of interest. The purpose of researches was development of compoundings and technologies of cookies with partial replacement of a flour wheat on WGO.

2. Materials and Methods

WGO received after extraction by a method of cold pressing of oil from germs of grain of wheat was applied to preparation of prototypes of cookies, thus it keeps almost completely biologically active agents of initial germs. As a result of shift deformation under the influence of high pressures, in WGO these valuable biological substances become in form more available for an organism that leads to increase in comprehensibility of these substances in comparison with initial raw materials.

More than 33% of the protein containing all range of irreplaceable amino acids are a part of WGO; the maintenance of lipids is at the level of 8%, thus their main part is made by valuable poline-saturated fatty acids – linoleic and linolenovy. Existence the polygoat - nola, more than 20 macro - and microcells, including phosphorus, potassium, calcium, iron and selenium is valu-

able. Availability of vitamins of group B, vitamins E, do to D and A perspective introduction of this vegetable product in cookies compoundings as an effective food enriching additive [3, 4].

WGO is characterized by the following organoleptic properties: possesses a neutral smell and taste, has cream color that allows to keep the organoleptic indicators of finished products peculiar to traditional flour confectionery.

3. Results and Discussion

Flour confectionery differ big variety, in spite of the fact that the same main raw materials - wheat flour (in rare instances rye, oat, corn) and granulated sugar are used. It is connected with use of many types of auxiliary raw materials with a big variety of a chemical composition and properties.

Compounding of new types of cookies are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Cookies compoundings with use of wheat germs oil cake

Product	Components					
	Chocolate and nut cookies		Slastenka		Chocolate pleasure	
	Control	Experience	Control	Experience	Control	Experience
WGO	-	60	-	113	-	78
Flour wheat	233	173	453	340	311	233
Sugar sand	114	114	180	180	208	208
Butter	182	182	-	-	208	208
Cottage cheese 9%	-	-	180	180	260	260
Margarine	-	-	180	180	-	-
Sugar brown	114	114	-	-	-	-
Egg chicken	1,5 шт	60	-	-	-	-
Walnuts	76	76	-	-	-	-
Milk chocolate	205	205	-	-	-	-
Salt cooking	4	4	-	-	-	-
Vanillin	4	4	-	-	-	-
Baking powder	4	4	-	-	13	13

Soda food	-	-	7	7	-	-
Going out	1000					

continuation table 1

Chocolate glaze	
Milk 3,2%	45
Butter	50
Sugar brown	50
Cocoa	20

The technology of preparation of cookies consisted of traditional stages: preprocessing of raw materials, crushing of raw materials, formation and thermal treatment of products. WGO crushed to the size of particles $0,5 \pm 0,01$ mm to exclude influences of the size of particles of a product on quality indicators of finished products. Further WGO hydrated water drinking in the ratio 1:1,7, mix mixed up and maintained 5-7 min. before achievement of the state close to a consistence of dough. Then all raw materials connected and kneaded up to the uniform weight and were located in the refrigerator at 1-1,5 o'clock at a temperature of 2-6 °C then it was portioned, formed according to a type of cookies and were exposed to thermal treatment in a germ case at a temperature of 170-180 °C, 10-15 min.

The Aminokislотно structure (mg/1r) new flour culinary products is presented to mg in figure 1. The analysis of the obtained data testifies that level of amino acids of the experimental combined products corresponds, and on some amino acids exceeds the content in reference protein. Innovative products were characterized by decrease in coefficients of redundancy, coefficients of distinctions of aminokislотно is fast also increase of coefficients of utility that speaks about increase in value of protein and balance of aminokislотно structure.

Fig. 1. Aminokislотноy structure of the new combined products

In table 2 it is presented macro - microelement and vitamin structure of the new products, allowing to carry them to products of a functional purpose. The content of such vitamin as B₁ was at the level of daily requirement and confirmed a high nutrition value of the received products.

Table 2. Macro – microelement and vitamin structure of innovative products (mg in 100 rp a product).

Compo nents	Chocolate and nut cookies		Slastenka		Chocolate pleasure	
	Contr ol	Exp er i e n c e	Contr ol	Exp er i e n c e	Contr ol	Exp er i e n c e
Iron	0,88	2,32	0,51	2,05	0,9	2,59
Calcium	92,64	236,84	31,22	185,83	39,35	209,97
Sodium	119,85	120,02	217,71	218,13	12,83	13,33
Potassium	194,59	392,87	118,6	385,15	126	227,24
Phosphorus	123,67	387,36	94,45	347,84	98,78	362,57
Zinc	0,42	4,03	0,14	4,03	0,17	4,3
Magnesium	43,52	50	18,96	25,21	29,65	34,9
Manganese	0,6	5,46	0,52	5,76	0,31	5,91
Sulfur	13,73	7,5	7,87	5,55	4,76	3,83
Vitamin B ₁	2,02	2,56	0,15	0,73	0,3	0,78
Vitamin B ₂	0,32	0,47	0,09	0,20	0,13	0,33
Vitamin B ₅	0,56	2,27	0,30	2,87	0,32	2,20
Vitamin B ₆	0,11	0,29	0,10	0,20	0,08	0,37

Vitam in B ₉	25,10	25,46	0,10	0,49	21,52	24,97
Vitam in A	5,10	5,20	5,17	5,39	3,08	3,33
Vitam in C	0,111	0,112	0,034	0,035	0,066	0,067
Vitam in E	0,91	6,32	5,92	11,52	0,66	6,70
Vitam in PP	2,42	4,78	1,88	4,03	1,47	3,81

It is important that a mass fraction of vitamins E and cover riboflavin daily requirement for 15% and more. The wide range of mineral substances is presented; products are especially rich with calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and manganese. Existence in products of selenium and policosanol which deficiency is referred to the most important violations of the food status of the person is especially valuable.

Calculation, generalization and the analysis of data testify to the high biological value of the developed products (80-85 %). Coefficient of distinction of aminokislотноy it is fast (15-20 %), showing the size of surplus of aminokislотноy it is fast irreplaceable amino acids in comparison with the smallest level it is fast limiting amino acid – indole amino-propionic acid, I had small value and I meant that excess amount of amino acids in protein of new products insignificantly. High balance on aminokislотноy composition of proteins (coefficient of utility 0,82-0,87 is thus noted; indicators of comparable redundancy - 3,54 %).

The organoleptic assessment of skilled products is given in fig. 2, 3 and 4. By results of researches the highest average assessment was received by a sample "Chocolate and nut cookies» - 9 points. Other products gained less point as in these samples insufficiently expressed taste and smells were established.

Color of all samples of cookies conformed to standard requirements. They had characteristic for this type of a product uniform color therefore the mark assessment on this indicator for everyone was maximum.

The look in a break at prototypes met the requirements of State Standard. Production was uniform without inclusions of crude dough and uniform and porous.

Fig. 2. Organoleptic assessment of "Chocolate and nut cookies"

Fig. 3. Organoleptic assessment of Chocolate pleasure cookies

Fig. 4. Organoleptic assessment of Slastenka cookies

Conclusions

Thus, as a result of conducted researches:

1. technologies of innovative products with high organoleptic rates are developed;
2. cookies with application of WGO possess high biological rates and the food value, the balanced aminokislotny structure and good comprehensibility;
3. flour confectionery because of introduction in drawing up products of deep processing of

grain it was enriched with a wide range vital, mineral substances and vitamins;

4. according to calculation of satisfaction of daily requirement had it is possible to tell productions that the developed innovative products can be used in functional food [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

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STUDY REGARDING THE POSSIBILITIES TO OBTAIN FUNCTIONAL TRADITIONAL FOODS FROM WHEY

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Abstract: *Whey may be defined broadly, as the serum or watery part of milk remaining after separation of the curd resulting from the coagulation of milk by acid or proteolytic enzymes. Capitalization of whey by cheese obtainment is a traditional method and the resulting products are nutritionally valuable food. Cheese whey is a product with a short lifetime, susceptible to microbial contamination due to its high water content. Researchers are looking for new ways to increase validity and to obtain a final product with high nutritional value. This paper proposes a solution to exploit traditional whey by using it to obtain cheese whey, to increase nutritional value and digestive by adding different plant products.*

Keywords: *by-product, cheese whey, cow milk, goat milk, nutritional value*

1. Introduction

Whey is a valuable by-product resulting from the manufacture of cheese, which in our country is not fully exploited. Whey is the by-product of cheese or casein production, it is of relative importance in the dairy industry due to the large volumes produced and the nutritional composition. Worldwide whey production is estimated at around 180 to 190×10⁶ tons/year. It is estimated that only half the amount of whey produced is used for human food or animal feed, the remainder being discharged through sewage leading to increased environmental pollution. A traditional whey recovery solution is to obtain cheese from whey. A total of 40×10⁶ tons/year of whey is produced in the European Union [1,2,3].

Whey contains more than half of the solids present in the original whole milk, including whey proteins (20% of the total protein) and most of the lactose, water-soluble vitamins and minerals. Consequently, whey can be considered a valuable by-product with several applications in the food and pharmaceutical industries [4].

Whey may be defined broadly, as the serum or watery part of milk remaining after separation of the curd those results from the coagulation of milk by acid or proteolytic enzymes. The type and composition of whey at dairy industry mainly depends upon the processing technique resulting in casein removal from fluid milk. The most often encountered type of whey originates from the manufacture of cheese or certain casein cheese products, where processing is based on coagulating the casein by rennet, an industrial casein-clotting preparation containing chymosin

or other casein-coagulating enzymes. Since the rennet-induced coagulation of casein occurs at approximately pH 6.5, this type of whey is sweet whey. The second type of whey, acid whey (pH max.5), results from processes using fermentation or addition of organic or mineral acids to coagulate the casein as in the manufacture of fresh cheeses [6, 7]. The main components of both sweet and acid whey, after water are lactose (70–72% of the total solids), whey proteins (8–10%) and minerals (12–15%). The main differences between the two whey types are in mineral content, the acidity and the composition of the whey protein fraction [8].

Biological treatment of whey by conventional aerobic process is very expensive and most milk plants do not have proper treatment systems for its disposal. As a consequence, around 50% of the amount produced is disposed of in rivers or lakes, or loaded onto the land, causing serious pollution problems since whey is a heavy organic pollutant with high biochemical oxygen demand [9, 10, 11].

Physiological action of whey protein has been highlighted by recent studies following the development of technologies for isolation and purification of whey protein components. Whey proteins are proteins that are discharged faster from the stomach and go through transit intact, which helps preserve bioactivity in the intestines. The whey proteins have a high content in essential amino acids, particularly sulphur amino acids (cysteine, methionine), which increases their biological value [12, 13, 14].

Romanian cheeses are little known and appreciated worldwide, although Romania is

producing over 100 varieties of cheese, some traditional. Lately, the focus is on the promotion of Romanian traditional products, the exploitation of national resources and realization of safe products for consumption with a high nutritional value.

Cheese whey is a traditional product whose historical origin is very old (the first document of the word in Romanian dates from 1220). It has been obtained for thousands of years and emerged at the same time as normal cheese manufacturing [10]. Cheese whey is prepared in the form of fresh, salted and smoked (in some mountain areas). In order to preserve it, well drained fresh cheese whey is crumbed and kneaded with 3-4% salt. Cheese whey has great nutritional value as it includes valuable milk serum proteins (lactalbumins and lactoglobulins) containing amino acids considered important factors for growth of the organism [15, 16, 17].

Worldwide, cheese whey specific to each country is obtained. For example, Italy originated a cheese-whey salted with approx. 4% salt called Ricotta, obtained from Pecorino-Romano cheese from sheep's milk, heated to 72 ° C with the addition of acetic acid or citric acid [11]. There is also a Corsican assortment which is called "bruccio" or "brucciu" very similar to the Romanian cheese-whey. In Norway, concentrated whey from cow's milk is produced as Mysost cheese, while the whey derived from sheep's milk is known as Gjetost cheese, the whey with added milk fat is Primost cheese and the whey from sheep's milk (88%) and cow's milk (12%) is known as Gudbrandsdalsost cheese [18, 19, 20].

Cheese whey has a short shelf-life and is susceptible to microbial contamination due to the high water content. For marketing is very important for the stability of whey cheese obtained to be as long lasting. One can apply some physical and biochemical processes to increase validity (salting, pasteurization, aging, etc.) known but currently applied to other cheeses. In addition, starter culture may be used (bacterial and fungal) in order to increase the definition of the term of validity and the sensory characteristics of the cheese whey.

This paper proposes a solution to exploit traditional whey by using it to obtain cheese whey with enhanced nutrition and digestion through the addition of various plant products.

2. Materials and methods

The experiments used whey resulted from the process of production of cheese from cow's milk and goat's milk. In many companies the whey resulting from obtaining several cheeses collected centrally.

The whey obtained by the above processes is characterized by the specific sensorial properties:

- aspect - whey is a yellowish green, opalescent liquid;
- consistency - fluid, viscous not accepted;
- odour and taste - sour, specific to lactic fermentation.

The composition of the whey will vary depending on milk characteristics and on the manufacturing process of the main product. The whey contains the most soluble components of milk and casein and fat residue. Often, during the manufacturing process, number of substances are added in the milk (calcium chloride, sodium chloride, acid dyes, and so on), which is found in the whey.

There are two types of whey:

- sweet whey, derived from enzymatic coagulation of milk;
- acidic whey, from the production of fresh or soft cheeses or the production of lactic casein.

Table 1. The typical whey composition [13]

Components	Whey type	
	Sweet whey [g/L]	Acid whey [g/L]
Dry substance, from which:	63-70	63-70
- lactose	46-52	44-46
- protein	6-10	6-8
- lipids	3	2
- calcium	0,4-0,6	1,2-1,6
- phosphate	1-3	2-4,5
- lactate	2	6,4

This raw material was obtained from a traditional cheese manufacturing, followed by processing in order to obtain a product with added cream onion and dill.

Cheese whey is obtained both from the production of cheese from cow's milk and from the manufacture of cheese from sheep's milk, as well as the whey from goat's milk cheese. To achieve the curd, whey is heated to a temperature of less than or equal to 80°C and maintained at this temperature, in this case favours the precipitation of most of the serum proteins,

which causes the fat from whey, which is accumulated in whey heated surface in the form of agglomerates which are collected in a cedilla, in which after draining the whey, the cheese whey is formed by automatic press. Generally, the cheese whey is accumulated in the cedilla as round balls with a mass of 2-3 kg, the product having a pleasant sweet taste, smooth creamy white texture.

The cheese whey obtained in the desired quantity is dosed according to the recipe and bring in a mixing machine for operation with onion, dill and salt. The mixing takes place until a homogeneous mass is obtained and the secondary raw materials are distributed uniformly throughout the mass of the product.

Onion is a biannual plant of the genus *Allium*, rich in active principles which explain its many therapeutic uses. The onions are found organosulphur compounds, flavonoids, essential oils, organic acids, vitamins (C, B1, B3, B6, B9, PP, E, etc.), carotenes, fitoncide, minerals (calcium, iron, sulphur, iodine, silicon, chromium, magnesium, potassium and so on). The chemical composition of onions is presented in Table 2.

Dill is an annual plant with a short life of the *Anatheum* genus, species *graveolens*. It is rich in vitamin A, B, C, chlorophyll, essential oils, and tannins (eg a teaspoon of fennel seeds contain more calcium than a cup of milk). It can stimulate digestion, antiseptic effect, combat hiccups, diuretic, depurative. The chemical composition of dill is presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Onion's chemical composition

Medium composition for 100 g	
Energy	3 kcal
Water	89 %
Glucids	7.1 %
Lipids	0.2 %
Proteins	1.3 %
Fiber	2.1 %
Calcium	80 mg
Magnezium	18 mg
Potasium	250 mg
Iron	1 mg
Vitamins	38 mg

3. Results and discussions

The finished product, cheese whey, was in the form of smooth paste, soft consistency, finely granular. The colour was white, light grey, and

palatability, sweet characteristic, the presence of lactose.

Table 3. Dill's chemical composition

Components	Quantity/100g
Carbohydrates, with fiber	7 g 2.1 g
Lipids	1.1 g
Proteins	3.5 g
Tiamine (B ₁)	0.1 mg
Riboflavine(B ₂)	0.3 mg
Niacine (B ₃)	1.6 mg
Pantotenic acid (B ₅)	0.4 mg
Vitamine B ₆	0.2 mg
Folic acid (B ₉)	150 µg
Vitamine C	85 mg
Minerals	1.5 g
Energy value	43 kcal

In cheese whey resulting from the capitalization of cow's milk whey cheese dill added in different proportions, as follows:

P₁ – cheese whey cream with 1% dill

P₂ – cheese whey cream with 3% dill

P₃ – cheese whey cream with 5% dill

P₄ – cheese whey cream with 7% dill.

After the sensorial analysis of products, scale scoring method, the optimal proportion of dill added was found to be 3%. As dill content grows added appreciation for the new product decreases the sensory characteristics affected the appearance, followed by taste and smell, and consistency is not influenced by the amount of dill added.

Fig.1. Assessment of sensory qualities of the product whey cheese cream with dill scoring scale method

In cheese made from whey resulting from the capitalization of goat milk cheeses were added onions and dill, finally after several attempts, the optimal proportion of these ingredients was 4%

onion and 3% dill (Fig. 2). Physical-chemical properties and sensory properties are shown in table 4 and table 5.

Fig.2. Cheese whey cream from goat's milk with onion and dill

Table 4. Sensorial properties of the product "Cheese whey cream from goat milk with onion and dill"

Characteristics	Admission requirements
Aspect	Homogeneous
Colour	Whitish - green
Consistency	Creamy
Taste and odour	Pleasant, salty enough, characteristic for the added ingredients

Table 5. Physical-chemical properties of the product "Cheese whey cream from goat milk with onion and dill"

Characteristics	Value	Analysis method
Fat/S.U.	30	SR ISO 3433:2009
Humidity	65	SR EN ISO 5534:2004
Proteic substances	10	SR EN ISO 8968:2004
NaCl	3	SR ISO 57651:2008
Acidity, °T	120	SR ISO 6092:2008

Conclusions

Lately, the world speaks more of crisis: natural resources and energy crisis, food crisis. In this case, the main concern of mankind is to exploit at a rate as high as its resources.

If we analyze the milk processing industry, we see a very important thing: it is an industry that can exploit the existing potential in raw materials, reducing pollutants.

Consumption of dairy products in Romania is steadily increasing; manufacturers are oriented towards diversification of product assortments, especially traditional cheeses. Due to its composition, whey is a valuable by-product that can be exploited by obtaining complex functional foods for human nutrition.

The paper proposes dairy manufacturers a product to please all consumers. Cheese whey cream was made from a traditional assortment of cheeses whey, with added onions and dill finally obtaining a finished product with superior quality and nutritional sensorial properties.

Dairy - cheese - whey - cheese whey - whey beverages is evidence that raw materials may bring many benefits. The only thing left to do is to use what already exists, but more wisely.

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INNOVATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GLUTEN-FREE CONFECTIONERY BAKERY PRODUCTS

S.TEFIKOVA, * A.STARIKOVA **

Abstract: *The article considers the actual topic of development of gluten-free mixes and improvement of the range of gluten-free flour confectionery products for people with celiac disease and seeks healthy nutrition. Over the received products experiments: definition of indicators of acidity and humidity of the products, studies of organoleptic indicators of quality. Retrieved innovative gluten-free mixture for clinical nutrition.*

Key words: *gluten-free mixes, healthy food, confectionery, experiences*

1. Introduction

In the state programs and the forecast of development of the industry of Russia for the period till 2015 formulated the main directions of innovative development of the baking, confectionery and other industries. Innovative way provides improved range of products at lower unit costs of all types of resources and introduction into production of results of R & d. One of the ways of improvement of quality and expansion of assortment of bakery is the use in the production of dry mixtures possessing a number of advantages in comparison with other kinds of raw materials. They contain the minimum amount of moisture, have a small size and weight, and the absence of active enzyme systems contribute to a more long-term storage. Dry powder mixture comfortable in the processing of their application simplifies the technology of the product and improves the culture of production while maintaining or even exceeding the quality of products, ensuring economic effect.

Given that the production of dry mixtures as an independent direction has already begun, and receipts in more developed abroad and are not always available, the creation of technological bases of domestic assortment of dry mixtures with a set of advantages acquires practical importance. On the basis of dry building mixtures is possible to create a range of products for preventive or even dietary orientation through the use

of, for example, protein vegetable and animal origin or other components, is able to provide the necessary chemical composition, food and biological value. Polyfunctional properties of dry mixtures can afford to exclude undesirable for human body parts or to enrich food healthy ingredients.

For the development of new and improvement of existing technological bases of manufacture of dry mixes for flour confectionery products in the country has significant experience and established scientific and practical bases of works by the famous scientists such as Tolstoguzov V.B. have been, Braudo E.E., Shaternikov VA, A.P. Nechaev, Krasilnikov V.N., Puchkova LI, Aksenova. Technology of preparation of dry mixes is the preparation of raw materials to the manufacture, formulation and dosing of raw materials, mixing, packaging, storage. With this method of production of all raw materials in the recipe is payable immediately, allowing to reduce time of preparation and dosing of raw materials, to improve sanitary conditions at the enterprises and to create optimal conditions for efficient organization of the production process. The application is ready for use dry mixtures does not require highly qualified personnel for development and formulation allows to promptly react to inquiries of consumers in respect of assortment, to reduce monitoring

costs of raw materials and auxiliary technological equipment for storage of raw material stocks. The advantage of using ready-made mixtures are such consumer properties as: convenience and ease of use and consumption in the home, different functional purpose mixes a wide range, meeting the diverse needs, relatively long shelf life. Upon receipt of mixtures it is necessary to consider a number of factors forming their quality and safety. Special attention is paid to food production meeting modern requirements of quality and safety, development of domestic production of food ingredients, and technologies for the production of products of functional purpose and specialized. For confectionery production are ready dry semi-multicomponent mixture intended for production of wide assortment of confectionery products, as functional purpose and specialized. These blends are possible to apply not only at home but also in production (enterprises of small capacity and catering). Flour semiproducts relate to food concentrates and represent a dry mix of pre-prepared products: flour, sugar, milk, egg powder and other components intended for cooking different types of pastry - cakes, cakes, biscuits and other.

One of the ways of improvement of quality and expansion of assortment of bakery is the use in the production of dry mixtures possessing a number of advantages in comparison with other kinds of raw materials. They contain the minimum amount of moisture, have a small size and weight, and the absence of active enzyme systems contribute to a more long-term storage.[2]

During enrichment of food with vitamins and mineral substances, extracts, herbal preparations, dairy products, pectins and other additives possible chemical interaction enriching additives among themselves and with the components of the product itself. Therefore, it is necessary to choose such combinations thereof, forms, methods and stages of introduction that provide maximum safety during production and storage. Currently, for each type of food product developed the most effective enrichment technology: selected stable forms of vitamins

and identify ways and stages of their entry in the food mass.

On the basis of dry building mixtures is possible to create a range of products for preventive or even dietary orientation through the use of, for example, protein vegetable and animal origin or other components, is able to provide the necessary chemical composition, food and biological value. Polyfunctional properties of dry mixtures can afford to exclude undesirable for human body parts or to enrich food healthy ingredients. So, for example, bezlyudova a mixture of corn and amaranth flour.

Gluten-free mixture mixture, not containing or containing in minimal quantities of the protein gluten. Despite its apparent simplicity, organize food that is completely devoid of gluten can be rather difficult. He is present in the "hidden" in many daily consumption products: meat, sausage, sour-dairy, confectionery, vegetables, fish, fruit canned food, spices, medicines, cosmetic products, etc.

As a full-fledged replacement glutamatergic product you can use non-toxic celiac disease cereals: rice, buckwheat, corn, millet. Safe are also flour and starch made from potato, tapioca, cassava, yams, beans, peas, soybeans, various nuts [4].

In the world market there is a rather wide selection of food for celiacs (bread, pasta, cookies, pizza, baking mixes and so on). They are easy to recognize by the presence on the packaging crossed out of the ear and labeling "gluten-free". Today there are two basic directions of development of formulations and manufacturing containing no gluten products. The first is based on natural gluten-free raw materials, primarily plant, the second - biocatalytic - oriented to remove gluten from raw material or its modification.

In accordance with the international standards are gluten-free and have the right to bear the products that its level does not exceed 20 mg/kg produced without the use of glutentergamemode of raw materials or the use thereof, but after special treatment for the removal of this peptide; products with reduced levels of gluten are called specially processed to remove the products in which the content of gluten is 20-100 mg/kg. In some people, the use of this protein in the diet causes the disease - gluten enteropathy (celiac disease). The disease is hereditary nature. In patients not produce enzymes that break down

one of the components of gluten up of amino acids, which the body accumulates the products of incomplete hydrolysis. These substances damage the mucous membrane of the intestines, and lint on his walls are gone. Because of this impaired absorption of nutrients, including those that the body is able to metabolize and prepare for suction. Currently the only proven method of treatment and prevention of complications in persons with a diagnosis of celiac disease is a strict lifelong gluten-free diet. It implies a complete exclusion from the power of all bakeries. Confectionery, pasta and other products containing explicit and hidden gluten. It is strongly prohibited to receive even 100 mg gluten (50 grams of white bread contains 2-3 g gluten). That is why the important issue is development of recipes of bakery products intended for people suffering from this disease and those in need of life-long special meals.

Gluten is a separate type elastic proteins, it is contained in some products: wheat, rye, barley, food and pastries.

In connection with the relevance of this topic we have developed two gluten-free mixtures consisting of the following components: flour corn /buckwheat, amaranth flour, sugar, eggs, buttermilk, vanilla, sesame seeds, nuts, soda.

The main advantage of buckwheat flour is its low glycemic index and a complete lack of protein gluten. In buckwheat flour in 1,5-2 times more fibre than wheat, amaranth and rice flour. In buckwheat flour contains rutin, a part of which is the quercetin, preventing cancer [1].

Amaranth flour has high nutritive value and unique biochemical composition. In amaranth flour contains up to 16 % of protein (more than 30% composed of essential amino acids), up to 15 % of fat (50 % of which fall to the share of polyunsaturated fatty acids V-6). In amaranth seeds are also very high in vitamins [E, a, B1, B2, B4 (choline chloride), C and D], macro - and microelements (iron, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, copper and others), as well as other biologically active substances (phytosterols, phospholipids, and others) that define a variety of therapeutic and prophylactic properties of amaranth flour [2].

Corn flour is superior to the other sorts of flour their performance of fat content, acidity and calorie and very appreciated because of the presence of channelling excess cholesterol, components. Flour of corn useful at

cardiovascular diseases, blood circulation disorders, anemia, diseases of the biliary tract, it slows down the aging process, strengthens teeth, etc. Corn flour are rich in fiber, it makes possible to use for manufacture of products of children's and dietary food.

2. Materials and working methods

Analyzed the chemical composition of the basic components of gluten-free mixes and presented in table 1.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the components of a gluten-free.

Flour	Prot e- ins	Fat	Carbo hydrat es	Ca	Fe	Na
Amara nt	14, 5	6,5	66,1	214, 0	9,8	21,0
Buckw he-at	13, 2	3,4	71,5	18,0	2,2	1,0
Corn	9,4	4,7	74,2	7,0	2,7	35,0

In connection with rich chemical composition and high nutritional value-stew, unique therapeutic and prophylactic properties in was based on three types of flour: amaranth, buckwheat, corn. To conduct a trial of the cakes were made variants of different mixes in different ratios, which are shown in table 2.

Table 2- Dosage of flour in composite mixtures 1 and 2.

Experience №	Mix 1 (corn flour: amaranth flour)	Mix 2 (buckwheat flour: amaranth flour)
1	40%:60%	
2		40%:60%
3	50%:50%	
4	60%:40%	
5		10%:90%

The studies used the conventional modern physico-chemical, structural, mechanical, organoleptic methods of research of properties of finished products. Selection and preparation of samples for laboratory tests conducted according to the methodology of studying food GOST, finished products according to GOST 59204 and method of sampling for HOST.[1] performed

measurements of humidity of prototypes, presented in (figure 1) and pH of mix components (figure 2) compared to the control.

Fig. 1. Change of humidity of test samples by comparison with the control.

Fig. 2. Effect of mixture composition on acidity biscuit dough.

3. Results and discussion

Analyzing figure 1 and 2, we can conclude that the most optimal systems ratio in a mixture of 1: 50% of amaranth flour: 50% of corn flour; mix 2

optimal ratio: 10% of buckwheat flour: 90% of amaranth flour.

Organoleptic characteristics of the product quality. Visual look- the product has the surface-big cracks. Surface odd-popular Golden-yellow with brown tone, without impurities. Color-golden-yellow color. Odor- pleasant, without foreign taste, the nature of this type of semi-product and raw materials used, with easy kind of nut flavor. Taste- pleasant, without foreign taste, the nature of this type of semi-product and raw materials used, with easy unusual taste of nut.

Conclusions

Thus, the use of mixtures of different components, gluten-free, allows you to expand the range of flour confectionery products with improved organoleptic indicators for people suffering from celiac disease.

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DIAGNOSIS OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES

N. BOIAN*

Abstract: *The paper presents a method of diagnosis appropriate to enterprises operating in the field of tourism. Method proposed a global evaluation containing technical, economical, financial and social criteria. Starting from a general model and tacking account of the main factors dissemination for tourism, we drew a specific model to be used to these enterprises. The method of evaluation is as type of scoring allowing assessing the business with a single rate on a five steps scale computed trough a mathematical model. The overall recommended strategy to improve the business is achieved in a stencil.*

Keywords: *diagnosis, tourism, model, score, criteria, business strategy*

1. Introduction

Diagnosis is the main method of research and study of enterprises that evaluate the technical and economic potential of the system and how it is recovery in the economic activity of production of goods for consumption. Diagnostic analysis of production systems highlights strengths and opportunities as levers of economic development, as well as weaknesses and vulnerabilities that require compensation measures. The global diagnosis enables integrated evaluation of enterprises in all its aspects (technical, economic, financial, strategic, and social) in the external environment in which it operates. In this way, enterprise's structures and functions have value only in a global context and therefore a component optimization makes sense only if carried out in harmony with the other components. Global diagnosis cannot be limited to technical issues as these generate economic results which sooner or later will generate financial flows and social problems.

Diagnosis main objectives are:

- setting the competitive positioning of enterprises in its close environment;
- evaluation of internal potential, especially resources and processes;
- establish the most appropriate strategy to increase efficiency of the activity;
- achieving a plan of action to accomplish the desired change and able to be appropriated by the company management;

2. Models of diagnosis

The general model of diagnosis (Fig.1) includes six different domain of evaluation:

- market position;
- relationships system;
- business potential;
- management;
- financial results;

Each domain is analyzed by means of specific criteria as so in the general model are summarized thirty criteria.

The specific model four tourism enterprises (Fig.2) results from the general model by removing insignificant or low significance criteria for tourism businesses. The main factors of dissemination criteria are grouped in: independents (who affect all enterprises in the same extent) and factors of management (who affect in different extent the management of enterprises).

The main independent factors in tourism are immobility of natural and technical resources, which lead to seasonality of sales and high importance of human resources, and high elasticity of demand and low of the offer which leads to predominance of internal towards external potential.

The main factors of management in tourism are the high unpredictability of the market and the long term of recovery investments which leads to low relevance of strategic management and high of financial one.

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Fig. 1. General model of diagnosis

Fig. 2. Specific model of diagnosis four tourism enterprises

3. Method of evaluation

Method of evaluation is a type of scoring that involves the calculation of enterprise's diagnosis total score (S_{DG}) by summing the scores of domains, corrected with the coefficients of relevance of each one (1). These coefficients (K_{DMK} , K_{DSREL} , K_{DSR} , K_{DSP} , K_{DSM} and K_{DF}) take into account the contribution of each domain to fulfill business and their value is determined based on the current statement of the tourism industry, the outlook for development and the national strategy in the field. The score of domains is also calculated as average weight of criteria scores, seated on a five point scale (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), and (7). The scores of domains mark, on a scale from 1 to 5 points, the level of competitiveness. Thus, it is considered as

strengths (forces of the enterprise) those domains that get more than 4 conventional points and weaknesses of the enterprise that gets less 2 conventional points. Domains dotted with 2 to 4 points are considered normal, not a danger (risk) but neither lever for development. The criteria's weighting coefficients of importance are established considering the consequences of failure on the business (Table 1). For tourism enterprises, taking into account the specific factors presented in chapter 2, we proposed a set of values of coefficients to be used in diagnosis (Table 2). The set of coefficients values is indicative only and analysts need to adjust it for each enterprise.

$$S_{DG} = K_{DMK} \cdot \overline{DMK} + K_{DSREL} \cdot \overline{DSREL} + K_{DSR} \cdot \overline{DSR} + K_{DSP} \cdot \overline{DSP} + K_{DSM} \cdot \overline{DSM} + K_{DF} \cdot \overline{DF} \quad (1)$$

$$\overline{DMK} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 Pdmk_i \cdot a_i}{\sum_{i=1}^2 a_i} \quad (2)$$

$$\overline{DSREL} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 Pdsrel_i \cdot b_i}{\sum_{i=1}^2 b_i} \quad (3)$$

$$\overline{DSR} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 Pdsr_i \cdot c_i}{\sum_{i=1}^4 c_i} \quad (4)$$

$$\overline{DSP} = P_{dsp} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{DSM} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 Pdsm_i \cdot e_i}{\sum_{i=1}^3 e_i} \quad (6)$$

$$\overline{DF} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{10} Pdf_i \cdot f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{10} f_i} \quad (7)$$

Table 1

Level of importance of criteria	Consequences of failure to fulfill criterion	Weighting coefficient of importance (a, b, c, d, e, f)
Very important (I)	Extremely serious empowers the entire enterprise	5
Major (M)	Serious sectoral effects	2
Secondary (S)	Isolated effects	1

4. Interpretation of score

Synthesis of the diagnosis involves framing enterprise in a stencil with five predefined classes by the value of diagnosis total score (S_{DG}). For each classes of the stencil is suggested the overall strategy to restructure the company, the more realistic and with the highest chance of success (Table 3).

Like any economic and mathematical model, the proposed one can be subjected to objective criticism because of absolutisms of diagnostic team point of view regarding the establishment of weighting coefficients of importance. However the model is useful because it provides stable landmarks and justifications to economic phenomenon that may underlie the final decision based on the professional judgment of experts and interest of the beneficiaries.

Table 2

Domain of diagnosis	Coefficients of domain	Criteria	Coefficients of importance criteria
Market	0,15	Demand	5
		Competition	2
Relationship system	0,15	Environmentally relationships	5
		Environmentally impact	1
Resources	0,2	Resources portfolio	2
		Technical resources	2
		Human resources	5
		Financial resources	1
Internal potential	0,1	Trade potential	2
Management	0,2	Objectives	2
		Structure	1
		Control	5
Financial	0,2	Value added	2
		Liquidity	2
		Result	2
		Return on commercial activity	1
		Return on financial activity	2
		Financial balance	2
		Net patrimony	1
		Working capital	2
		Working capital requirement	2
		Risk of returns	5

Table 3

Diagnosis score S_{DG}	Significance	Overall strategy recommended
1	Business failure	Concentration of activities in profit centers and beginning procedures for splitting the company. Insolvency proceedings for the rest of the enterprise.
2	Critical position	Measures to overcome the critical thresholds: restricting activities, stopping of investments, administrative reorganization, capitalization, capital injection, measures of technical efficiency.
3	Position to limit	Important restructuring, new targets on short/medium time: stimulation of sales, management improvement, saving resources, capital injection.
4	Position good	New strategic lines: funding preferential the activities, development of collateral activities, integration of external activities.
5	Business very well adapted to environment	Offensive strategy of development: entering new markets, assimilation of new products, intensifying promotional activities, technical and technological investments; Fusion, absorption, sale of the business.

Conclusions

The proposed method of diagnosis provides quality and opportunity of evaluation by objectivity, relevance, completeness and speed of determinations. The five diagnosis domains considered in the general model, cover a complete portfolio of internal and external potential enterprise has and their weighting contribution to business, largely solve the relevancy of diagnosis by approaching the model to reality.

Specific model achieves an approach of the analysis to the field of tourism by focusing on specific issues such as seasonality, high importance of human resources, and high elasticity of demand and low of the offer.

The adaptation of models to enterprises is provided by the criteria's weighting coefficients of importance.

Finally, through predefined overall strategic recommendations, according to the calculated score, method of diagnosis shortens the time necessary to develop the strategy to improve businesses.

Diagnosis model for tourism also can be used in monitoring enterprise's activity after the strategic plan is implemented, in order to evaluate its reaction. If these are not according to the expectations, adjustments may be made in short time to improve the

results before the situation become irreversible.

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THE MULTIDIMENSIONALITY OF TOURISM PHENOMENON

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Abstract: *The paper treats the subject of multidimensionality of tourism phenomenon, through the prism of four main dimensions, and namely, the economic dimension, geographic and ecological dimension, socio-cultural dimension and political-administrative dimension. The expert researches on the multidimensional phenomenon of tourism generally approach three dimensions: economic, ecological and geographical, and socio-cultural. We consider necessary and we justify in this paper the approach this phenomenon in terms of four dimensions, including political-administrative dimension, in addition we open a future topic for research - human right to tourism.*

Keywords: *multidimensionality, tourism phenomenon, economic dimension, geographic and ecological dimension, socio-cultural dimension, political-administrative dimension.*

1. Introduction

Starting from the definition of the concept of "phenomenon", evolution of nature and of society, and by joining the definition "touristic"-referring to tourism, we can define the *tourism phenomenon* as a process, an evolution of the society relating to tourism.

The tourism phenomenon, by its nature, is particularly complex, with deep implications for economic, social, administrative, political, cultural, etc., through its interpenetration of its heterogeneous components results a unique specific unique and original phenomenon.

Tourism is a phenomenon with a multidisciplinary approach (multipurpose), it requires an approach from the perspective of several sciences as well as from the perspective of several professions [1]. Tourism as we know it today is distinctly a twentieth-century phenomena [10].

Tourism multidisciplinary is reflected by the fact that is difficult to identify the disciplines that have something in common with tourism, the scientific side of tourism that integrates different and varied informative sources, analyzing problems and methods of research.

The interdisciplinary research methodology of tourism has a relatively short history, in the context of which in the year 1950 tourism was almost exclusively purely economic [5].

Nowadays, still the economy is the main discipline that deals with tourism at a macro and micro economic level, as well as applied economics. After the year 1960 the contributions

of geography, sociology and anthropology became also important, knowing the impact of tourism on the environment, and also the social and cultural impact of its destinations and, obviously, of the hosts companies. Psychology contributes to the scientific researches in the market in tourism, but history helps us to establish trends in development of tourism.

The contribution of law and administrative sciences in tourism is noticed also by the investigating of both freedom of movement to all spatial levels (freedom which, at an international level, has been promoted by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948), but also through the organization and supervision of tourism industry by protecting the rights and safety of tourists.

The research methodology involved activities of collection, processing and interpretation of information on the issue of the multidimensionality of the tourism phenomenon, using a large documentary material (books, studies, magazines, legislative regulations, database information available through Internet etc.), making analytical and objective observations, theoretical analysis and content analysis

2. The dimensions of the tourism phenomenon

We consider that the main dimensions of the tourism phenomenon are the following:

- Economic;
- Geographical and ecological;

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- Socio-cultural;
- Political-administrative.

The economic dimension analyzed in conjunction with the national economy as a whole, places tourism as a stimulating factor of the global economic system.

Tourism is a stimulating factor of the production [8], on the development of other branches of the national economy (transport, agriculture, industry, trade, etc) and also as a generator of jobs, and having the capacity to overcome and attract the labor force to other sectors.

Through the development of tourism it can be obtained a significant increase of production. Tourism is not only creator of the P.I.B, but also has an important contribution to the achievement of added value. For example, tourism is the major source of income for countries such as Bermuda, Greece, Italy, Spain, Switzerland and most Caribbean countries...It is a growth industry of increasing power, influence and importance, highly competitive in both a national and international sense [7].

Tourism also manifests itself as a mean of diversification and development of the structure of a country's economy. Thus, the necessity, to adapt tourism domain to the needs and the requirements of tourists which are more increasingly and more sophisticated, favours on the one hand, the emergence of fields, of the specific activity sectors (entertainment, transportation industry, travel and tour agencies, handicraft production) and, on the other hand, brings new dimensions of some of the existing branches: agriculture, food industry, construction, transport, services in the field of sport, and cultural.

The positive effects of tourism of the economic development of national or territorial level, manifests, as well as multiplier effects of: tourism, tourism investments, and also of the foreign trade.

Thus, it outlines the positive effects of international tourism upon equilibrium of payments balance, upon the level of exchange rate, upon the ratio of real trade, upon the monetary expansion and the movement of a money balance. International tourism is considered to be the biggest exporter in the world.

Tourism can be regarded as an opportunity of decrement of interregional imbalances, a lever for development of regional and rural environment, encouraging the use of local availabilities of

labor, and acting positively on demographic movement. Tourism regarded as a user of different resources, of whose effects reflects upon the prices stability, with implications to the inflation level, and of the way of income distribution, and increase the value of real estates. Tourism encourages investments in infrastructure, thereby helping to improve the living conditions of the local population.

In addition upon the incidences to regional economy and of the areas of tourists receiving, the results from their involvement in the values circuit, it has consequences for tourism development upon urbanization and the houses construction, infrastructure development (facilities, provision of public services, etc.). Tourism, thus, becomes an important vector in the use of local available resources, and of a plus workforce.

Tourism plays an important role in the economy and due to its capacity to generate new jobs, having, from this point of view, a major contribution to attract the human resources overplus from other sectors, i.e. persons that are not employed, and also to a decrease of unemployment. The relationship between tourism and the use of labor force manifests itself both at a qualitative and quantitative level, and also directly and indirectly.

Tourism generates positive effects on public budgets, being an important generator of incomes, the tourism sector annually brings each year to the states hundreds of millions of dollars in tax revenue, but it is also a receiver of public costs.

The geographical and ecological dimension of tourism phenomenon it is outlined from the analysis of this activity, tourism being able to cause mutations and in the territorial development; from this point of view, tourism is regarded as a lever of decrement of interregional imbalances, looked at national or global scale. In addition to the incidents of regional economy and tourist areas, resulted from their involvement in the circuit, the tourism development has as consequences upon their geography, urbanization and housing construction, upon infrastructure, and the development of public services, etc. It also favors the use of local resources, the availability of manpower. We also mentioned and the eco-tourism vocation within tourism development strategy, which is appropriate measures to protect the environment, and the fundamental values of human existence: landscape, water, air, flora, fauna, etc.

Tourism can have an important role in environmental protection, conservation of biodiversity and can be sustainable for the use of natural resources. For example, the tourism industry can protect and regenerate natural places as parks, protected areas, cultural and natural sites, by its financial contributions, through the implementation of an infrastructure with care towards the environment, and also through a better management of the environment. Also, tourism can contribute to the better understanding of the local population regarding financial interests and intrinsic value of natural and cultural sites, by motivating the same communities to regain its natural and cultural heritage, protection and preservation of the environment.

The socio-cultural dimension of the tourism phenomenon [2] is driven by the importance and the social point of view of this activity, manifesting itself as an active mean of educating and raising the level of education, culture and civilization of humans, recreation, relaxation, but also of restoring strength and potential, rest, motion, spa treatments, contributing to maintaining physical health of the population.

The tourism phenomenon is inextricably linked to civilization, culture. Between tourism, culture and civilization there is a relationship of close interdependence. Firstly, tourism is an act of culture, due to the fact that the tourist accumulates on journey an appreciable set of knowledge in various fields, and secondly, the degree of culture and civilisation decisively influence the quality and attractiveness of the tourism product offered.

Tourism generates effects on socio-cultural values [11]. Identifying the effects of tourism on socio-cultural values implies an approach from two points of view [6], namely, according to tourist inbound areas and collectivities, and of tourism outbound areas and countries.

The effects of tourism to tourist inbound areas and collectivities:

- strengthens the coherence of national and political community to which one belongs,
- allows the evolution of mindsets to inbound countries,
- the emergence of a touristic culture, especially for the middle class of inbound countries.

The effects of tourism upon of tourism outbound areas and collectivities, which have a great impact of creating new jobs, which may cause changes in:

- the social structure of the communities visited by tourists,
- demographic and professional structure of outbound collectivities,
- education and incomes of local population,
- prestige structure and the power in the local community.

Tourism has an important role and also in the use of leisure time of the population, thus ensuring: recreation, recoil, but also a potential work power restoration through rest, motion, medical spa treatments, influencing in an active way the maintenance of the physical and psychological health of the contemporary human

Like any other domain, tourism, in order to have a coherent, unitary and efficient evolution, requires an institutional framework of organization and functioning, in which case we identify political-administrative dimension of the tourism phenomenon [4].

The state intervention in the field of tourism is necessary due to the following factors:

- national interest,
- the complexity of features specific to tourism industry,
- the international competition in the field.

Tourism, seen as an increasingly component of the national economy, as a stimulating factor of economic-social growth, as an integral part of the economic unit assembly, requires the intervention of the state in its development, ensuring at the same time and referencing at a macroeconomic level in relation to the evolution of all other branches. State, as the owner of national administrative power of control, ensures a good and proper development of tourism, and it has four distinct functions:

- legislative and regulation function;
- the coordination of tourism domain function;
- the representation function;
- the administrative function.

In the exercise of the coordination function, the international experience concerns the specific modalities of action of governments of various countries, which reveal the guidelines to support the development of tourism are the following:

- to define the general strategy of tourism development;
- assessing needs in terms of tourism accommodation;
- the coordination and the enhancement of the researches in the field of tourism;
- the regulatory framework and the control of the functioning of the components of tourism industry, in order to ensure the legal framework of this activity, to protect and promote the interests of tourism industry and of tourists;
- creation and implementation of the training programmes and upgrade human resources skills in tourism;
- to provide services of a general interest, necessary for the tourism expanding;
- to expand and to support the tourism promotion campaigns.

The administrative tasks in the field of tourism, by a ministry or by another body of ministerial administration, represent a political option of the party or coalition of parties that are in the government decision, to express interests and policy priorities.

Therefore, recognizing and supporting the tourism sector by the government as a priority for the industry, considering the existence of this domain, it is identified in the policies and the positions adopted by decision makers and the level of government investment in this sector [3]. Policy implementation is facilitated by public involvement in decision making [9].

Tourism represents, therefore, a transversal activity of political power and public administration, including the areas of economic, social, environmental, security issues, education, information technology, planning, communication etc., as a result of the development of society.

From an optimistic perspective of the years to come, in line with the development of civilization, in the last decade, trends of development of society require technical transformation, economic, social and political-administrative provisions that affect the tourism phenomenon, such as:

- increase of the average expectancy of life;
- the increase on the income of the population;
- the development and diversification of transportation means, that make the distance-time, be virtually negligible;

- the automation of processes manufacturing and the increase human resources productivity, leading to shortening of the work week and, as a consequence, increase the time for relaxation and recreation;
- the continuous increase of the level of culture of the masses, leading to increase for knowledge;
- a total almost urbanization of the population occupied in manufacturing and in branch services;
- the requirements and the needs of Y generation;
- the enhancement governance concernment for tourism.

Starting from these transformations and taking into account the influence of economic, political, administrative, social, biological, psychological etc, we can appreciate that in the future, in most countries of the world, tourism will turn from an occasional concern in a permanent one, with a tendency to become a need that will be felt more strongly by modern man, which leads to an intensification of the interest of the experts for this area.

Conclusions

Taking into account the influence of economic, political, administrative, social, biological, psychological, factors etc, we can appreciate that in the future, in most countries of the world, tourism will turn from an occasional concern in a permanent one, with a tendency to become a necessity, a need that will be felt more strongly by the modern man.

We consider the approach of the multidimensionality of tourism phenomenon in terms of four dimensions, three of them established in the literature: the economic dimension, geographic and ecological dimension, socio-cultural dimension, as well as through a new dimension: the political-administrative one.

It is prefigured the need of the recognition of "human right to tourism" of the contemporary man, the way of spending the holidays being an important indicator of life quality, and a step towards the future is to ensure human right to tourism, thus opening a future topic research of the complexity and of multidimensionality of tourism phenomenon.

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RURAL TOURISM IN BRASOV COUNTY

MIRON FLOREA*

Abstract: *The Brasov County is well known for mountain and cultural tourism. In the last years, a new type of tourism has been developed – rural tourism. There are present: agritourism, cultural rural tourism connected with citadels, fortified churches, and monasteries. Also ecological and adventure tourism were developed. Rural tourism will ensure a sustainable economic development of these areas.*

Keywords: *rural tourism, fortified churches, agritourism, protected areas.*

1. Introduction

Starting Located in the South East of Transylvania, Braşov County includes three major relief units: the Bârsa Depression (known also as The Land of Bârsa – Bârsa being the major water collector of this area), the Făgăraş Depression (known as Olt river County), and the Homoroadelor Plateau, a part of the Tarnave Plateau.

The county is very well known for the Poiana Braşov Resort (the largest mountain resort of Romania) as well as for the cultural tourism related to the medieval city of Braşov, one of the most visited places in Romania.

Besides urban and mountain tourism, Braşov County is characterized by an important rural touristic potential, both in volume and in diversity. Its main attraction is related to **ancient citadels and fortified Saxon churches**.

The most visited location is **Bran Castle**, for marketing reasons associated with Count Dracula (who has, in fact, never been there). It has been erected in the 14th century in order to supervise the movement through Bran Pass, between Wallachia and Transylvania.

Located on a limestone cliff, it offers a great view of Bârsa County. Now a museum, it has on display a large amount of medieval artifacts and organizes many events, of which Halloween is one of the most popular.

Located close to the castle there are the Rural Civilization Museum of Bran, as well as the old Customs Museum.

Another citadel is nearby – the Râşnov peasant citadel, similar to Bran with respect to location (on top of a limestone mountain), but boasting a better view.

Fig.1. *The Râşnov Citadel and SW Bârsa Depression*

Feldioara Citadel, located on a lower terrace of the River Olt, was almost a ruin but local authorities have now started a reconstruction program which should bring it (in 2016) to its former, Middle Ages glory.

Castle Beldy Ladislau and Castle Beldy Pal are two locations in Budila Village, with gardens and adendrological park, where restorations are also ongoing.

Râşnov peasant Citadel was recently renovated; many cultural events are now being held. Also, at the foot of the mountain there is a sports area and, relatively close, a nice cave arranged for touristic visits.

On various county locations there are very well preserved, unique throughout Europe, Saxon fortified churches. They were originally built by the Teutonic Knights.

Following their departure, German colonists brought in by the Hungarian kings (who administrated at that time Transylvania) continued the work. Two of these wonderful rural

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architecture works were put on UNESCO's list of world cultural patrimony heritage:

Prejmer is the most sophisticated in architecture, surrounded by a huge circular wall. Inside it there are the well-known "guard route" and many defense devices, such as "the death organ", which is similar to an old machinegun. Inside the old gothic church within citadel walls, one can find a beautiful organ, a collection of oriental carpets and old tombstones.

The inner walls have over three hundred small chambers which served to store food during Tatar and Ottoman invasions.

Fig. 2. Aerial view of the Prejmer Fortified Church

Viscri, located in the region of the Tarnave Plateau, near the town of Rupea (fortified, and with a nice and recently renovated citadel) is unique due to its isolation and very good preservation.

Named in Romanian after its original German name – Weisse Kirche – the citadel was erected on hilltop with a nice view. The church is surrounded by a huge circular wall. Inside the church there is an organ, and a collection of oriental carpets.

From the clock tower one can see the whole region. Just across the road one can visit the newly created museum of Saxon civilization.

Owing to its cultural value the village of **Viscri** is visited each year by H.R.H. Prince Charles, who even bought a house there, which has been transformed into a rural pension. He also founded **The Mihai Eminescu Trust**; a foundation specialized in the renovation of rural houses and churches.

Other rural gothic fortified churches of interest are: Hărman, Homorod, Cața, Drăușeni, Feldioara, Rotbav, Sânpetru, Bod, Vulcan, Cristian, Cincu and Cincșor (the last two are

located in the northern part of the Făgăraș Depression).

Fig. 3. Homorod fortified church

Fig.4. Drăușeni fortified church

The Agritourism area of Bran is the most visited rural touristic area in Romania, due to its wonderful mountain landscape, folklore traditions (there is a real calendar of events specific to each month), craftsmanship products (related to wool, wood art, and carpets).

One of the most representative touristic locations is called "Cheile Grădiștei" or "Grădiștea Gorges", where many rustic hotels were erected, as well as restaurants with traditional food. Also, a sky route had been constructed.

Another well-known touristic location is "Crăiasa Munților" ("The Queen of the Mountains") in the same Moieciu area.

Fig.5 Piatra Craiului Mountains, as seen from Bran Pass

Fig.6 Constantin Brâncoveanu Monastery from Sâmbăta de Sus

On the high plateau of Bran, close to Giuvala Pass, there are tiny villages with nice pensions, such as Țirnea (with “Hanul cu struți” or “Ostrich Inn” restaurant and a mini zoo), Fundata and Fundățica with pastoral traditions and ecological food. **Agritourism in “Țara Oltului”** (The Olt River Land or The Făgăraș Depression) is related to an unique landscape connected with the highest mountain area of Romania – the Făgăraș Mountains (The Moldoveanu Peak reaches 2544m in altitude). This mountain chain with glaciated relief and beautiful glacial lakes (Urlea and Podragu, corresponding to Brașov County), was called by the great French geographer Emm. De Martonne, “The Transylvanian Alps”. Some villages are rich in popular traditions (Drăguș), others are known due to their monasteries (Sâmbăta de Sus - Constantin Brâncoveanu Monastery), while others host ancient churches built in stone (Ținca Veche- “Templul Ursitelor”). In the village Sâmbăta de Sus a nice castle of Baron Samuel von Brukenthal is the location for a horse race area.

Agritourism in Vama Buzăului. Relatively new as an agrotouristic area, located in the

northeastern part of the county, Vama Buzăului has a wild buffalo reservation, a nice waterfall called “Urlătoarea” and many popular traditions.

Fig. 7. Urlătoarea waterfall

Fig. 8 Wild buffalo in the reservation of Vama Buzăului

Agritourism in Poiana Mărului. The village of Poiana Mărului is one of the most dispersed settlements in Romania, with temporary, summer houses being located on the hilltops. Besides the untouched natural landscapes, the dwellers prepare a lot of rural gastronomic products (based on milk, meat and forest fruits).

Another type of rural tourism is ecotourism (known also as “green tourism”). Due to the variety of landforms, vegetation and fauna, in Brașov County there are many protected areas such as national parks, natural parks, and scientific reservations. The only national park is **Piatra Craiului Massif**, a huge limestone ridge with carstic relief, alpine flora and fauna. A wild red carnation variety, called “Garofița Pietrei Craiului” can only be found here. Two fauna reservations have been established: one for wolves, and another for bears.

Bucegi Natural Park has its northern slopes in the Brașov County. The landscape is dynamic, with steep slopes (even rock walls), many residual landforms such as natural towers,

needles, or sharp ridges. The most interesting mountain area located in Braşov County is related to the glaciated valleys of Mălăieşti, Ţigăneşti and Gaura.

Fig. 9. *The Cross from the Caraiman Peak in the natural park of Bucegi Mountains*

Perşani Mountains could be considered a small petrographic diversity: limestone, basalt, conglomerates and sandstones. In Racoş area are preserved an old volcano structure and a very nice basalt columns front. There are also present many fossils.

Făgăraş Mountains, the highest mountain area in our country has recently been included in Natura 2000 Sit (ROSCIO122) protected areas with 17 natural protected sites. The area holds two fauna world records: the largest sample of mountain wild goat and the biggest wolf trophy.

Poiana cu Narcise from Vad Village (Narcissus Meadow) is located in the new protected area called Făgăraş Piedmont.

Fig. 10. *The Muddy Volcanoes from former Homorod Spa*

The Lakes from Dumbrăviţa Village is also called “The Delta from the Carpathians”, due to their specific flora and fauna. This is an ideal place for bird-watchers. Other protected areas are: The muddy volcanoes from Homorod, Tâmpa Mountain (the southern slope is occupied by an altitude steppe), VamaStrunga fossil area in the Bucegi Mountains, and the swamps from Lempeş Hill, Prejmer and Hărman (with a unique variety of tulip – “laleaua pestriţă”).

Conclusions

One can practice **adventure tourism** in plenty of ways: climbing the limestone walls of Piatra Craiului and Bucegi, zip-lining in the Râşnov Gorges, cycling on the forest roads in Ciucaş, Bucegi or Făgăraş Mountains. Recently, near the small town of Zărneşti, a large amusement park, with six rides and covering five hectares, has been opened.

Spa tourism used to be an important type of rural tourism in Braşov County. Due to a long period of neglect many resorts, well-known during the interwar period, disappeared: Zizin (today only the mineral springs are used), where the infrastructure has been destroyed, Homorod Spa with efficient curative mineral waters which was demolished by the local community of gypsies, and Rodbav Spa which was left in a fight of divergent interests. The only currently active spa is “Băile Perşani” (located between Braşov and Făgăraş), which was called the “seaside from the mountains” due to the existence of curative mud’s, thermal waters and new and modern facilities. The rural tourism in Braşov County adds a new component to the mountain, business and cultural types which already exist. This new type will ensure sustainable economic development for the rural areas.

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RESEARCH OF INFLUENCE OF EXTENT OF HYDRATION OF BIOPOLYMERS OF CAKE OF GERMS OF WHEAT ON RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF SYSTEM

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Abstract: Influence of extent of hydration of biopolymers of cake of germs of wheat on rheological properties of paste is experimentally investigated. The prospect of use of paste in food systems on the basis of meat, fish, dairy and vegetable raw materials is established

Key words: cake of germs of wheat, paste, extent of hydration, rheological properties

1. Introduction

In today's market increase in assortment of foods and improvement of their consumer properties are of primary importance. Cereals oilcake flour is a promising raw material with a relatively low cost and containing a significant amount of essential substances. Every day more and more actual there is a problem of a state of health of people. The major factor in prevention and treatment of diseases is food. Excess weight has more than 35% of the population of the country and about 12 million people have the diabetes, about 50 million need treatment-and-prophylactic products at a disease of digestive organs.

The conducted researches in Russia showed that in recent years separate groups of the population have violations in the food, connected, including, with the contents and a ratio of the main nutrients and biologically active components: vitamins, microcells, etc. Therefore, development of qualitatively new food, is a priority of the present stage of development of the food industry, in addition enriched with physiologically functional ingredients, the most corresponding to requirements of a human body.

The problem of improvement of quality and improvement of the production technology of production of mass food comprises enrichment of products on the main components and economic feasibility of their production. [1, 2, 3].

At the same time vegetable additives thanks to existence in their composition of vitamins, nitrogenous, sugars, pectinaceous and other substances allow to intensify technological processes of production of mass food, to increase quality of finished goods.

According to key provisions of the Concept of the State policy in the field of healthy food of the population of the Russian Federation, research are directed on creation of food of the raised nutrition value and a functional purpose.

Perspective object for formation of the range of products with functional properties is the group of flour products as they are an one of daily a diet component due to the developed traditions in structure of food of the population of Russia.

Products from a flour possess a number of valuable nutritious properties. At the expense of grain products more than ½ needs of an organism for carbohydrates and about 40% in proteins are compensated. Their major role in food of the person consists in providing an organism with group B vitamins: tiaminy (B1), Riboflavinum (B2) and nicotinic acid (RR).

For the purpose of increase of a nutrition value of finished products of this group and reasonable modification of proteinaceous raw materials, i.e. creation of vegetable additives in the form of powders for production of flour products is perspective. Production creation on the basis of the developed vegetable powders in a certain measure will promote correction of food and decrease in mikronutriyentny deficiency, improvement of health of consumers and prevention of alimentary and dependent diseases.

Therefore development of complex systems for increase of biological value of products, studying of influence of vegetable powders as additives on organoleptic, physical and chemical, microbiological indicators of a ready-made product

and their introduction in production is a necessary and actual task.

Now in Russia the considerable attention is paid to a question of maintenance of health, working capacity and active longevity of the person. Irrational and unbalanced food of the population, inactive way of life, environmental pollution by the harmful substances, the raised noise and radiation background bring to so-called to "civilization diseases". To them refer violations in work of nervous, immune, haematogenic, digestive systems, diseases of a thyroid gland and still a number of the illnesses causing a metabolic disorder therefore food is one of the major factors in prevention and treatment of the extensive list of diseases.

In this aspect an actual task is development of compoundings and technologies of the combined food vegetable systems, the being characterized high rates nutrition and biological value. One of the most perspective sources of biologically active agents of a phytogenesis can consider a flour of germs of wheat.

2. Materials and Methods

The object of our study was wheat germ flour (WGF).

The main properties of a flour of germs of wheat – increase and immunity stimulation, treatment and prevention of oncological diseases, improvement of reproductive function, a conclusion from an organism of slags and harmful substances, improvement of a gastrointestinal path, and owing to – digestion improvement, acceleration of updating and skin healing, an obstacle to education and accumulation of excess weight. It is possible to buy a flour of germs of wheat and it is simple for implementation of complex positive influence on an organism as a useful additive in food.

The flour of germs of wheat is applied also to treatment and weakening of symptoms of diabetes, chronic gastritis, dysbacteriosis, diseases of kidneys, and also during the rehabilitation periods after courses of treatment, operations or carrying out therapy.

The flour of germs of wheat becomes the main dietary product for the people who are playing sports or simply keeping the figure. The flour of germs of wheat is used for addition in food on some tablespoons in day that allows to improve a metabolism and intestinal flora considerably.

The list of products which part the flour of germs of wheat can be, is huge and diverse. It can be added in dough at production of bakery products, with its help it is possible to receive unique porridges, soups, macaroni, sauces, it can be added in *п о д л и а н н ы* and spices. It will help to make any dish more healthy and useful.

Also the flour of germs of wheat is applied in the cosmetic purposes to care of face skin and a body. For this purpose from it masks on a kefiric or oil basis which are put on skin for ten-fifteen minutes are created. After that skin rejuvenates and smoothed, process of cell regeneration is accelerated, skin becomes softer and elastic. The flour of germs of wheat is suitable for food and improvement of any types of skin.

Thanks to existence of these substances the flour of germs of wheat becomes useful alternative to a usual flour. Many people decide to buy a flour of germs of wheat for prevention and treatment of various diseases or it is simple for the general improvement of an organism and maintenance of the correct and useful diet. Anyway, influence of a flour of germs of wheat obviously and invaluablely. Thus, the flour of germs of wheat remains the unique product allowing at the same time to bring benefit practically all systems of a human body.

Higher nutritional value, hypo-allergenic properties, rich vitamin and mineral content, good organoleptic characteristics and easy digestibility makes it possible to include the WGF into a wide range of products of different purposes. The study of chemical composition of WGF (Fig. 1) shows a high protein content - 33.8%, the digestibility of the proteins in the flour being significantly higher than in the composition of the germ itself, since all biologically valuable components are more available to the body due to the mechanical processing. WGF proteins contain a full range of amino acids, including essential ones (tab. 1).

WGF contains B vitamins, vitamins A, D and E, which exceed their concentration in the raw grain. Flour contains over 20 minerals, including iron, calcium, magnesium, manganese, selenium, phosphorus, zinc [4, 5, 6].

Food systems of various kinds of animal and vegetable raw materials have certain functionally technological properties, the introduction of new components into them implies to give them similar properties.

Fig. 1. Chemical composition of wheat germ flour

The purpose of the work was to study the rheological properties of hydrated food systems based on wheat germ flour.

Table 1 – Amino acid structure of of wheat germ flour

Amino acids	Content of amino acid, g/ 100 g of protein
The irreplaceable	
Lysine	2,17
Methionine	0,85
Treonin	1,87
Leytsin	12,82
Izoleytsin	1,53
Fenilalanin	1,20
Valin	1,55
Triptofan	0,52
Total	22,51
The replaceable	
Arginin	3,62
Tsistin	0,63
Tirozin	1,20
Gistidin	1,30
Asparaginovaya acid	3,26
Serin	1,11
Glutaminovaya acid	6,71
Proline	5,20
Glycine	2,01
Alanin	1,99
Total	27,03
In total	49,54

A mixer was used for cooking paste from WGF. In this test, the resulting dough moisture content was changed from 59% to 68% in 2% steps. Rheological properties of the resulting viscous- and plastic dough paste was controlled by information- and measuring system, comprising a

device "Struktrometr ST-2." Characteristic curves of changing pressing force on the piston during dough mass extrusion are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Changing pressing force F on the piston during viscous and plastic hydrated mass extrusion

3. Results and Discussion

Change of the occurring normal pressure on the piston in the regular mode of the dough extruded within the selected range of moisture was 4.21 kPa, so at high moisture content it was 68% (the ratio of WGF oilcake and water - 1,0:1,9) the pressure was 1.63 kPa, and at low moisture content - 59% (the ratio of WGF and water - 1,0:1,5) - 5.84 kPa. Adding water to the WGF in the ratios of 1,0:1,5-1,6 does not lead to full hydration of WGF macromolecular substances, the dough paste itself was characterized by heterogeneity, the presence of lumps that can be seen by pressure fluctuations that occur in the process of extrusion (Fig. 2). With an increase in the mass of water in hydrated WGF its plasticity and uniformity increased and the pressure reduced. Table 2 shows the results of calculating the normal mechanical pressures of hydrated pastes based on WGF.

Table 2 – Normal mechanical pressures of hydrated wheat germ flour

Paste moisture content, %	Ratio of WGF and water	Normal mechanical pressure (kPa)
59,41	1,0:1,5	5,84
61,55	1,0:1,6	4,49

63,69	1,0:1,7	3,27
65,80	1,0:1,8	2,65
67,91	1,0:1,9	1,63

Conclusions

Values of the normal mechanical pressures (Table 1), the values of pressure strengthening, evaluation of organoleptic characteristics of the dough pastes based on WGF of various degrees of hydration showed that rational hydrated WGF moisture content is 63-64%, which corresponds to the ratio of WGF and water of 1.0:1,7 and consistency assessed by normal pressure of extrusion 3.27 kPa. With this moisture content WGF hydrated condition is close to the consistency of ground beef or thick dough. Flaking of unbound moisture does not occur. This is of primary importance when combining semi-finished WGF components and plant- and animal food systems.

Paste on the basis of MZP is technological, its organoleptic indicators and functionally technological properties allow to enter freely it into food systems on the basis of meat, fish, dairy and vegetable raw materials.

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STUDY OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MOLECULAR CUISINE

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Abstract: *Molecular gastronomy is a sub discipline of food science that seeks to investigate the physical and chemical transformations of ingredients that occur while cooking. Its program includes three axes, as cooking was recognized to have three components, which are social, artistic and technical. Molecular cooking is one application of molecular gastronomy; it means cooking with modern tools. Molecular cuisine is a modern style of cooking, and takes advantage of many technical innovations from the scientific disciplines.*

Key words: *molecular gastronomy, destructive cuisine, foam cuisine, aroma-cuisine, liquid nitrogen*

1. Introduction

Molecular Cuisine is a modern trend in cooking, a branch of trophology associated with the study of physical and chemical processes which occur while cooking [1].

There are many branches of food science, all of which study different aspects of food such as safety, microbiology, preservation, chemistry, engineering, physics and the like. Until the advent of molecular gastronomy, there was no formal scientific discipline dedicated to studying the processes in regular cooking as done in the home or in a restaurant. The aforementioned have mostly been concerned with industrial food production and while the disciplines may overlap with each other to varying degrees, they are considered separate areas of investigation.

Though many disparate examples of the scientific investigation of cooking exist throughout history, the creation of the discipline of molecular gastronomy was intended to bring together what had previously been fragmented and isolated investigation into the chemical and physical processes of cooking into an organized discipline within food science to address what the other disciplines within food science either do not cover, or cover in a manner intended for scientists rather than cooks. These mere investigations into the scientific process of cooking have unintentionally evolved into a revolutionary practice that is now prominent in today's culinary world.

Using a variety of technologies and chemicals, the food may vary drastically. Meat, fish, vegetables and fruit are made in the form of foam, mousse, jelly or ice cream, powder or soufflé. Scrambled eggs with a fruit flavor, transpar-

ent dumplings, caviar with a watermelon flavor, coffee in the form of cookies – this food is designed to surprise with its unexpected taste. The aim is not to feed the guests, but to make a real show and to amaze with taste, smell and flavor.

In the mid 20th century, scientists were more interested in the composition of products and their impact on human rights. Only in the late 20th century there was a separate branch - molecular gastronomy, the study of chemistry and physics applied to the products. The term "molecular gastronomy" was first mentioned in 1992 by a physician Nicholas Kurti from Oxford University and a French chemist Hervé This. Molecular cuisine grew out of scientific gastronomy experiments of Herve This, who connected gastronomy with chemistry and physics. This derived some molecular formulas for classic French sauces, learned to change the taste of food with the help of physical and chemical reactions and special ways of heat treatment. In 1988 This coined the term "molecular and physical gastronomy" [2].

In 1999, Heston Blumenthal, the chef of the famous English restaurant "Fat Duck", prepared the first "molecular dish"- caviar mousse and white chocolate. As it turned out, these types of food contain similar amines which could be easily mixed. In 2005 the Institute of Advanced Studies on Flavour, Gastronomy and Culinary Arts was opened in Reims Institute (France), which combined advanced culinary world. All of our food consists mostly of water, for example, plant cells or animal tissue, and therefore the properties of water and aqueous solutions - one

of the most important issues of molecular gastronomy. From the standpoint of chemistry, there is nothing strange in the fact that alcohol coagulates protein, but if we apply this knowledge in the cooking area, it appears that a raw egg can be cooked, if we leave it in alcohol or any alcohol-containing beverage for some time (for about a month). Chemistry and physics helped to understand the processes occurring in food and dispel some culinary myths. For example, when cooking green vegetables it is not necessary to add salt to preserve flavour and color.

Cooking time depends on a size of a piece of meat, not the weight, and the distance from the edge to the center - the bigger it is, the longer the meat is cooked.

After studying the metamorphosis taking place with the products followed the steps of molecular gastronomy: improvement of traditional dishes, the invention of new dishes based on conventional ingredients, the invention of new products (additives) and experiments with flavors combination.

The first successful molecular gastronomy dishes were named after famous scientists. For example, Gibbs (egg whites with sugar and olive oil in gel form), Vaklu (ruit foam), BAME (egg cooked in alcohol) [3].

2. Methods

New methods of molecular technologies are developed every year at international summits, trendy restaurants are increasingly offering its visitors the food prepared by molecular method, and in 2014 a gastronomic research center opens in Madrid on a laboratory basis, where new ideas and ways of cooking will be generated

Another name for molecular cuisine is destructive cuisine.

In fact, during the cooking process, the molecular bonds of the substance break, and then some new bonds appear. In addition, there are unexpected molecular bonds, which are used in the creation of a dish [2].

In destructive cuisine liquid nitrogen, vacuum, oxygen and inert gases, agar-agar (seaweed extract), various chemical reactions, emulsification, centrifugation, and much more a used. Products are subjected to low temperatures or modified by siphon.

3. Materials

One of the most clear examples of obtaining an item of molecular cuisine is "foam" - the science about turning any product into the air foam. Using a siphon, we put inert gas into semi-liquid consistency product (it can be anything - fish, meat, fruit, vegetables). As a result, each particle of the substance expands, foams and converts into a foam. This light airy foam has a distinct taste of the product from which it is made. Foam dishes (called espuma) became the hallmark of classical molecular restaurants and most successfully characterize their approach. The foam was first introduced to the menu by Ferran Adria (the famous Spanish chef of "El Bulli " on the Costa Brava. He is in the top nine best chefs in the world).

Aromadistillation is a new trend in aromacuisine. Distillation (from Lat. Destillation - staxis) - distillation process for separating a mixture of volatile liquids into its components by evaporation using heating and subsequent condensation of the vapour. The process is based on the ability of various substances to convert into the gas state depending on temperature and pressure. In the distillation process the aromadistillation is carried out [4].

As a result, a person is able to capture the delicate flavours of different dishes and liquids containing volatile essential oils. For example, if you put into a rotary evaporator some water and some fresh rosemary, you will get a rosemary concentrate, which can not be obtained by conventional evaporation (high temperature would change the scent of rosemary).

Centrifuge is an aggregate, dividing the bulk of the body fluids of different specific gravity by using centrifugal force. Centrifuges are actively used in chemical laboratories and is widely used in agriculture: to separate the fat from milk, honey from the honeycombs, etc.

If you put a bottle of tomato juice in a centrifuge, you will get three output units. In the lower part will be some thick red precipitate consisting of cellulose, pectin or heavy pigments, including colorings – actually it is tomato paste obtained in a natural way, without heating. The juice itself which is devoid of these particles is yellowish. It is a solution of sugars, salts, acids, and aromatic compounds. In the upper part there will be a thin fat foam - a concentrated tomato flavour. Each of these substances can be used in

cooking to give a fragrant, thin and light sauces and components of foods. The separation of fats makes sauces and foams more stable, they end up having a clear taste and richer aroma.

PacoJetting is a technology that has received its name in honor of the company homogenizers PacoJet. The peculiarity of this homogenization process is that the products which are prepared from bulk - puree are stored at temperatures up to $-20 - (-22) ^\circ \text{C}$.

The device is unique. Homogeneity of many products is accomplished by adding into them some special natural chemical (not always) agents, which have the adhesive effect. The egg white is a natural agent. In food industry, a variety of chemical agents are used for the production of pates and sausages. PacoJet achieves the same effect by the crushing frozen products without further additives. Thus, minced beef, spices and dried crusts can be frozen, taken from the freezer and crushed in PacoJet. Then the homogeneous mass is put into a polymer sleeve, is boiled for an hour at a temperature of $130-140 ^\circ \text{C}$.

The peculiar feature of the producer is a special strength of the structure of the grinding blades and the highest speed of processing required to ensure that the product does not have time to defrost and melt. At the rest, the device has a structure of the kitchen blender.

Liquid nitrogen was firstly used by Heston Blumenthal. It is used for instant freezing of various substances. As liquid nitrogen evaporates instantly, leaving no trace and no harm to human health, it can be used for cooking - including those that are made right in the plates.

One of the specialties of the "Fat Duck" restaurant (British restaurant of molecular cuisine) - green tea mousse and lime in liquid nitrogen. This bead mousse, which is extruded from a spray bottle on a spoon, seasoned with liquid nitrogen powder, sprinkled with Japanese match tea and sprayed with lime essence. It is hard and looks like a meringue, but melts instantly on the tongue, leaving a light and refreshing feeling. Blumenthal was trying to make a mousse, in other ways, using different natural stabilizers, but nothing worked - mousse lightness and tenderness was unstable and fell off less than in a minute. Liquid nitrogen has solved this problem, as well as many others. It is interesting to know that, despite its obvious futuristic features, this method of cooking appeared almost simultane-

ously with the discovery of liquid nitrogen. In 1877 a Victorian cook Agnes Marshall offered to make ice cream this way.

Transglutaminase is a family of enzymes that allow to "glue" muscle tissues, combined into one mass pieces of meat or fish protein. It is by means of transglutaminase in the food industry that fake shrimps and crab sticks are made from surimi, which is crushed and pressed fish mass. It is used in the preparation of Japanese buckwheat noodle soba, and moreover, the same enzymes are involved in blood clotting. First transglutaminase was studied in Japan in 1959, now it is used not only for the of crab sticks production, but also in molecular restaurants.

The research of the substances that can turn a meal into a gel form started with the beginning of the century in which were involved food companies. The 1950s were opened alginates - salt of alginic acid, viscous rubbery substance derived by natural kelp. This technology has been used for the production of jelly food. On this basis, Ferran Adria developed a system called "spherification", which is a manufacturer of gel spheres of different sizes, filled with edible substances that are literally exploding fireworks of concentrated flavour.

"Hot and cold tea" of Heston Blumenthal is made in such a way that at first a guest drinks iced tea and then it suddenly gets hot. This tea is not prepared from two liquids, as they would have mixed, under the law of diffusion, it is made of two gels of different density, which look and taste like black tea.

Sous-vide - this is a specific method of cooking in a water bath. Products are rolled into vacuum bags and cooked in water at a temperature of 60 degrees. This method was invented by a British physicist Count Rumford (1753-1814). In the mid-1970s, a French chef Georges Pralus, began to use sous-vide method for cooking various dishes. He found that the foie gras, cooked in such way looks perfectly, does not lose the excess fat and has a better texture than the one that is cooked traditionally.

The dry ice is frozen carbon dioxide, which changes from a solid state to gas when heated. If you inhale the smoke of this liquid, a person can get cough. Thus body signals us of danger. But this is what makes sense of carbonated soda and sparkling wine bubbly: champagne bubbles filled with a concentrated carbon dioxide, and tingling

on the tongue that we feel - this is a weak version of the same danger signal.

Conclusions

Smoke from dry ice sharpens all the senses simultaneously. It is this effect which is actively used in molecular restaurants: if a block of dry ice specially prepared aromatic substance are mixed with water, it can be surrounded by the scent of the consumer who is capable of drastically change the taste of the food.

Some admire the molecular cuisine or dreams to try similar dishes and some have been already disappointed by strange and unusual food or afraid of using chemistry in cooking. However, the possibility of molecular cuisine is so great, that it continues to develop, thanks to the interest and active participation of professional chefs worldwide.

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RESEARCH REGARDING PASSIVE ENERGY HOUSES IN ROMANIA

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Abstract: In the paper the authors present three system of insulation for building passive energy houses from Romania. It is important to insulate buildings to consider the heat transfer coefficient (U). A low U -value indicates a high level of insulation.

Keywords: insulation, thermal conductivity of coefficient, heat transfer of coefficient, passive energy houses.

1. Introduction

Insulation has rol of a reduce the energy of consumption for heat. In the following chapters there are presented the three system of insulation: Baukasten system, lumber and steel nodes system, bales of straw system.

2. Insulation used for passive energy houses

The first system is Baukasten. The modular system of Baukasten consists of modules that are made intercoupled wood industry the basic elements of the self are solid wood.

Scope:

The Baukasten system is suitable for building homes that require high demands on energetic efficiency. Interior or exterior walls serve, depending on the model, for termic and fonic insulation.

Advantages:

Due industrial prefabrication modules and additional components, assembly can be done quickly and accurately. The basic modules have $U = 0,42 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$. An average termic extra insulation leads to good values, which allows a slender construction.

Disadvantages:

The wall is locked to a treshhold and the lower part of an item of bending, each having a 80 mm height. Close is realased by lighting boards.

Installation:

Industrially manufactured modules and system components are delivered on pallets.

For opennings in the wall using appropriate system components, closures or sills.

After that were applied installation empty spaces inside the modules put microcrystalline cellulose flakes.

Protection against noise

Depending on the requirements of mitigation acoustic modules can be field with wood chips or sand microcrystalline cellulose.

Acoustic attenuation can be increased by applying a different coating materials or structures with two layers.

Ecological principles

Modular wooden walls are composed of dry wood and insulation materials commonly used which has a passive effect on the ecological balance.

The two system is the beam lumber and steel nodes. The bars are connected to the nodes in a spatial structure.

Advantages:

Untreated lumber and pulp can be reused or recycled without problems.

Disadvantages:

Execution nodes of chrome steel is intensiv energy. This problem was resolved nosed by replacing metal with some wood.

Connection between bars and nodes can be made on site, or if one is needed in a decentralized hall.

Protection against noise

This structure represents a good noise protection.

Ecological principles

The entire wood consumption required beam system with fence is reduced by 50-70% towards conventional construction. Weight of a house completely for one floor of 150 m^2 is 20-50 tonnes for beams with fence. A similar building wooden frames would have about 50 tons and construction of brick and concrete floors should be weighed 180 tons.

Choise of materials, wood and microcrystalline cellulose, leading to a positive ecologic balance. The wood used comes from the forest exploitation, and system components can be easily dismantled, reused or recycled.

The three system is met with bales of straw.

Scope:

Building material, straw has a very affordable price. Building a straw bale house, which leads to cost reductions.

Advantages:

Insulation a bale of straw termic very well have a function of adjusting the humidity.

Demolition materials can easily discard respectively are biologically degradable.

Disadvantages:

Instead, let us turning up the danger may straw bale constructions consists of the persistent humidity level inside the building.

Installation:

Bales of straw as a building material haven't a unconventional trade, and due to the fact that the harvest is for dependence on weather conditions.

It is recommended that the supply of arms building make lets us be a year before.

Protection against noise

Following studies demonstrated that straw bale walls, confers a protection against well noise.

Ecological principles:

Straw is an agricultural product side, therefore the energy consumption required to produce it resume the balers energy consumption of the process of making straw bale.

Wood, straw and clay don't contain harmful substances.

3. Optimization structure for passive energy house

The paper has been taken to study three structures of insulation for passive energy house.

With software from German company (www.u-wert.net) were mapped graphics on temperature variation profiles coefficients from moisture and heat.

The structure of 1 taken for analysis is made of MDF (thickness 16 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity of 0.13 W / mK), hemp (thickness 100 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity of 0.04 W / mK), OSB (Thickness 14 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity of 0.13 W / mK), climacell (thickness 200 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity of 0.04 W / mK).

Figure 1 shows the temperature variation of structure 1.

Fig.1. Temperature variation for the structure 1

Figure 2 shows the variation in moisture for the structure 1.

Fig.2 Changes in moisture for the structure 1

Figure 3 shows the variation coefficients of thermal protection structure 1.

Fig. 3 The variation coefficients of thermal protection structure 1

The structure of 2 taken for analysis is made of: gypsum fibreboard (thickness 16 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.32 W / mK), Knauf Tector (thickness 100 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.045 W / mK), Gutex Multitherm (thickness 14mm coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.042 W / mK), ISOCELL (thickness 200 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.04 W / mK).

Figure 4 shows the chart of temperature variation of the structure 2.

Fig.4. Temperature variation for structure 2

Figure 5 shows the variation in moisture content for structure 2.

Fig.5.Changes in moisture for Structure 2

Figure 6 shows the variation coefficients of thermal protection for structure 2.

Fig.6. The variation coefficients of thermal protection structure 2

The structures of 3 taken for analysis is made of: wool insulation (thickness 18 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.04 W / mK), mineral wool insulation (100mm thickness, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.045 W / mK), cellulose insulation (thickness 14 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.04 W / mK), film (thickness 200 mm, coefficient of thermal conductivity 0.22 W / mK).

Fig.7 Temperature variation for structure 3

Figure 8 shows the variation in moisture content for structure 3.

Fig.8 Changes in moisture for structure 3

Fig. 9 The variation coefficients of thermal protection structure 3

Conclusions

- Costs for external wall finishing, are function applied insulation, coating materials and decoration, between 150-250 euro/m².
- A wall space fence with beams and has a thickness of 717 mm cost 200 -240 euro/m².
- With a price of 10-40 euro/m³, straw is a building material with very affordable price.
- Given that structure 1 has heat transfer coefficient $U = 0.127 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$, structure 2 is the heat transfer coefficient $U = 0.129 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$, structure 3 is the heat transfer coefficient $U = 0.244 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$, the

optimal structure why is the heat transfer coefficient shows the smallest.

- A low U-value indicates a high level of insulation.

Figure 9 shows the variation coefficients of thermal protection structure 3.

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STUDY ON THE LYOPHILIZATION PROCESS OF AROMATIC PLANTS

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Abstract: The lyophilization process of aromatic plants is proving increasingly more useful and advantageous for better capitalization of these. This paper presents some aspects of the lyophilization of aromatic plants in terms of their behavior during the process and after this and some effects on the plants, compared to other drying methods. Are highlighted also some visual and olfactory characteristics of the aromatic plants resulted after lyophilization which can to offer some special possibilities to use these aromatic plants dried by lyophilization.

Keywords: lyophilization, aromatic plants, characteristics, quality

1. Introduction

The aromatic plants are defined as those plants which can do a distinct fragrance or odor. From the chemical point of view, the organic compounds, the molecules which cause the flat aromatic rings, which form easily the bond to the receptors in the nose [7]. The aromatic plants have been used for thousands of years for many purposes different ranging from medicinal to religious; from protection against spirits to culinary delights. For example: Lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*), Vanilla (*Vanilla planifolia*), Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*), oregano (*Origanum vulgare*). [7]

Aromatic plants are the produce and exude aromatic substances (largely ether oils), which is used in making perfumes, in cooking, and in the food, pharmaceutical, and liquor industries. Many aromatic plants have species of the *Lauraceae*, *Umbelliferae*, *Myrtaceae*, and *Labiatae Families*. The roses, geraniums, laurel, lavender, and rosemary is among the plants used in industry. [2], [9].

Aromatic plants list is extremely long. The literature includes several approaches, so this list is different, in report with the authors. However, may be considered in this category around 37 species. [10]. The other approach is to use the term "aromatic herbs", or "herbs". [11]

The applications of the aromatic plants, currently, are oriented to pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries, to food or to ensure the ambience at various locations. For that are used in particularly the aromatic flowers. Because the

plants after the collection lose the freshness and aromatic qualities, it is necessary a drying process for to preserve the plants, for to keep a long time as many features. Therefore, to obtain optimum performances is necessary to achieve of drying of these aromatic plants under optimum conditions, in the depending on the application.

This study is carried out to follow the behavior of some aromatic plants during freeze drying, and after this process.

2. Methods

To dry aromatic plants can be used several methods, each one having both positive and negative effects for to the ability to not taint their main flavoring qualities.

The effects vary in relation to the method used. Thus, besides the influence on organoleptic qualities of herbs can interfere with other changes, such as the changes in total phenolic, hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, and antioxidant properties [8]. In the case on the applying on the spearmint plant five drying treatments:

- convection oven drying,
- freeze-drying,
- microwave drying,
- air drying with the sun exposure
- air drying without the sun exposure.

Were found that lyophilization process produced dried spearmint that had the highest total phenolic (34.6 ± 1.9 mg/g) content and the most potent antioxidant capacity (126.2 ± 0.4 mg/g for FRAP and 88.1 ± 5.9 mg/g for DPPH,

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respectively). When the spearmint that was convection oven and dried by microwave drying presented the amount of phenolic compounds exclusive (12.0 ± 0.5 mg/g) and antioxidant potency (49.3 ± 0.7 mg/g for FRAP and 26.9 ± 1.6 mg/g for DPPH, respectively). This might be attributed to the heat-sensitive fact that was degraded phenolic or bio-transformed at high temperatures. The loss of phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity reached up to 60% compared to freeze drying. In the table 1 presents the technical conditions used for this investigation, the effect on reducing plant moisture status. (for example: spearmint).

Table 1.

Drying method	Equipment	Time	Final moisture (%)
CD	Convection oven (Venticell 111, MMM Group, Germany)	7.5 h	10.6 ± 0.2
FD	Laboratory-scale freeze dryer (Crist Alpha 1-4 LD plus, SciQuip Ltd, UK)	48 h	10.5 ± 1.2
MD	Microwave oven 800 W (DKL Model W-8811)	80 s	8.0 ± 1.3
SUD	-	312 h	13.4 ± 0.4
SHD	-	312 h	13.9 ± 1.0

CD – convection oven drying; FD – freeze-drying; MD – microwave drying; SUD – air drying with the sun exposure; SHD – air drying without the exposure [8]

Also, in the Figure 1 it can observe their effects on the phenolic content of the drying process of aromatic plants.

Figure 1. – The effect of the drying methods on phenolic content of dried spearmint (the phenolic content was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu method an Obied protocol), [8].

In same time proves the superiority of the freeze-drying method, (in the case of the spearmint drying), using the method of determining the content of phenolic by two spectrophotometric assays based on different mechanisms.

These are: Folin-Ciocalteu method (method based on the transfer of Electrons in alkaline solution from the phenolic compounds to phosphomolybdic/phosphotungstic acid complexes) and second method, after Obied protocol (based on a maximum wavelength of phenolic compounds at 280 nm. [8]. This superiority is demonstrated also using freeze-drying method in the case of the study maintaining antioxidant capacity.[2]

By the lyophilization process it can better prepare for to the extract of the essential oils from aromatic plants, the lyophilization having positive effects on the quality of oil from the leaves of herbs, the freeze drying at high vacuum pressure medicine is recommended for cosmetic and industrial use. [5]. There are a lot of effects of the freeze drying method on the content of volatiles and dehydration kinetics of the aromatic plants.

In the experimental program were subjected to freeze-drying process some branches and leaves of mint, respectively some fragrant rose petals.

The lyophilization of the samples was carried out in specialized laboratory of the Faculty of Mechanical (POLITEHNICA University of Timisoara), using the Lyophilizer type "Il Shin Europe" (typ. Floor Model Freeze Dryers - FD5512, Figure 2) installed in the *Integrated laboratory for analysis, quality optimization and certification in the food industry*.

Figure 2. – The lyophilization equipment brand IIShin Europe, tip Floor Model Freeze Dryers – FD5512.

The complete cycle of lyophilization lasted 22 hours. It was used the automatic cycle of the lyophilizer. Therefore first, the plants were cooled briefly at -55°C and then sublimation process has started, decreasing the pressure in 10 minutes at 5 mTorr.

Raw material

Mentha belongs to *Lamiaceae* family and includes about 25 species. Leaves, flowers, and the stem of *Mentha* spp., are frequently used as herbal teas or as additives in foods to offer aroma and flavor or to protect against food-pathogens bacteria. *Mentha viridis* is usually consumed in Cyprus as a dried product for herbal tea or as an additive in Cypriot traditional cheese called halloumi. [8]. Fresh spearmint (*Mentha spicata* L.) leaves were purchased from a local grower in Timisoara, (Romania). Harvest was done in the second half of September 2013, when spearmint just before flowering. Mints are regarded as one of the most important spices throughout the world. Mint leaves in botany are the common name for members of the Labiatae, a large family of chiefly annual or perennial herbs. The essential oils of mints are widely used as flavourings in the food, spicing, tea infusions, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries [5]. Only leaves were used for analyses. Fresh leaves were stored in the refrigerator at $5\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ before isolation of volatile compounds; the rest of material was put for drying immediately after sorting. (figure 3).

Figure 3. – Samples of spearmint (*Mentha spicata* L.), a) – during the lyophilization process; b) – dried after lyophilization process.

- Roses petals from the AIDA-specie, red, fragrance level 8 (on a scale 1 to 10) with high strain, vine, resistant to disease, (Level 9 on a

1-10 scale), harvested in Timisoara in the first part of June, 2013.(Figure 4).

Figure 4. – Samples of AIDA – red, fragrant roses petals, a) – fresh; b) dried by lyophilization; c) - during the lyophilization process.

- Roses petals from the BUCCANEER-specie, yellow, fragrance level 8 (on a scale 1 to 10) with high strain, vine, resistant to disease, (Level 9 on a 1-10 scale), harvested in Timisoara in the first part of June, 2013.(Fig 5).

Figure 5. – Samples of BUCCANEER – yellow, fragrant roses petals, a) – fresh; b) and c) - dried by lyophilization.

After 8 month the aromatic plants were dried by lyophilization, after that, these were rehydrated, and were compared with the fresh state. (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. – Samples of dried aromatic plants after rehydration: a) – spearmint; b) – red roses petals; c) – yellow roses petals.

For rehydration, the dried leaves were immersed into one recipient with pure water and closed, and maintained at a constant temperature 20°C , for 24 hours.

3. Results and discussion

During experiments conducted it were noticed several issues related to the behavior of the aromatic plants in the lyophilization process. It was noted that:

- In all the plants once with water removal, its changed their spatial form, becoming more brittle. After the rehydration just partially were regained the flexibility, the form but not the color. In all plants color became darker, losing their shine.

- Red color of the rose petals, after lyophilization, became from bright red to dark claret, and after the rehydration process it has almost completely lost its red color, without that transfer to the water of hydration.

- Yellow color of the rose petals have kept almost the color, but after rehydration have not got the glow.

- Dried aromatic plants, keeping the container closed, its kept odor strong enough (5 to 6 on a scale of 1 ÷ 10), even after 8 months.

- After rehydration and drying, odor intensity were decreased by 1 ÷ 2 points, that was transferred partially to the fluid used for rehydration.

- The infusion of lyophilized plants became very rich in principles assets acquired from these.

During the entire process of freeze-drying the plants behaved approximate similarly. There were differences in the space forms gained due to initial rates of existing water and its distribution. Thus it was found that as the plants containing higher volatile oils its are more stable during freeze-drying process both shape and color.

Conclusions

The lyophilization process is a very useful technique to extend the shelf-life of aromatic plants with a high specific aromatic capacity, and with more another beneficial characteristics of these. This study confirms the superiority of this drying method in comparing with the other. Besides keeping in a higher percentage of phenolic content, a potent antioxidant activity, it remains also an high level of the volatile and odorous substances. Thus, although liophilization technology costs are quite high, the superior quality of the dried aromatic plants, this process causes greater applicability of this method. The lyophilized aromatic plants may be further employed in the industry for obtaining cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, food products, various medical

therapies, and as well other improved of the ambiance and ornamental techniques.

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STUDYING OF THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CORRUGATED PAPERBOARD BY USING FEM-BASED COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

D. GOSPODINOV*

Abstract: FEM-based computer simulations are used to perform study of the critical compressive force which a corrugated paperboard can withstand. Study consists of performing experimental testing of samples from flat paperboard and corrugated paperboard. Mechanical properties of flat paperboard have been determined which are afterwards used to simulate the behavior of a 3D geometric model of the tested samples from corrugated paperboard. The results from the simulations are used to study how basic geometric parameters of this material affect the critical force.

Keywords: FEM-based simulations, stiffness, corrugated paperboard, compressive strength.

1. Introduction

Corrugated paperboard is the most frequently used material for making of vast variety of packages, post-displays used in the advertisement, decorative furniture, miniature shelters for pets, pieces of art and many others. It is a multilayered material which normally consists of 3 layers – two external flat layers and one corrugated layer between them.

According to the pitch of the flute of the corrugated layer P and the height H (figure 1), several types of flute are distinguished [1, 6].

The flat layers are called “liners” while the internal layer is known as “flute”.

Fig. 1. Basic geometric parameters of corrugated paperboard

There are number of parameters related to the quality of the packages made of corrugated paperboard.

Undoubtedly, one of the most important parameter of a box is the BCT [2], which assesses its ability to withstand compressive loads which occur during storage and

transportation, when some packages are oftenly placed on the top of others. Those on the lower level are subjected to forces due to the weight of the boxes in the upper levels. The BCT parameter is determined by the means of standard test also called BCT or Box Crush Test.

The BCT of a package depends on the ECT [4] and FCT [5] parameters of the corrugated paperboard it is made of. ECT is parameter assessing the ability of the corrugated board to with stand compressive loads in direction coincident with its CD direction, while FCT is related to loads applied in the ZD direction of the paperboard.

Engineers can calculate an approximate value for the BCT of a package if they know its geometrical configuration as well as the ECT and the FCT of the corrugated paperboard intended for its producing. This is done by the use of MaKee's equation [7].

Since the strength of the corrugated paperboard is crucial to the strength of the packages, a study is done by using FEM-based computer simulations on the influence of the both geometric parameters, the pitch P and the height H , on the ECT has been carried out.

Other parameters, such as the radius of the curvature of the flute R and the section of contact between the layers has also been examined.

2. Materials and methods

Before proceeding with the computer simulations, it is necessary to conduct some initial experiments. The purpose of these experiments is to collect data on some geometric

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parameters needed for building of a 3D computer model of the corrugated paperboard and mechanical characteristics of the materials which are required in order to perform an analysis on the distribution of stress and deformation in a solid body.

First experiment conducted is the RCT [3] test of flat paperboard.

The aim of this experiment is to determine some mechanical characteristics of this material which are necessary for the FEM-based studies. Samples from two kinds of flat paperboard are subjected to testing. The first paperboard is 100 g/m² and it is used for the making of flat layers of corrugated paperboard. In this article it is referred as L100.

The second type of paperboard, referred as W100, is used to make the internal corrugated layer and its mass per square meter is also 100 g/m². From each type of flat paperboard 6 rectangular samples are cut out. Before testing they are left 48 hours in the conditions of temperature 21,3° C and relative humidity (RH) 48,6%. The length of the samples is 150 mm and the height is 13 mm as the thickness is measured for each kind of paperboard. The samples are rolled to form a circle with diameter of 48,7 mm and then subjected to compressive loading as shown on figure 2.

The magnitude of the force F , which is being measured during the experiment, increases at a constant rate.

The force is measured with accuracy of 0,01 N. The displacement of the upper surface of the specimen D on which the load is applied is also measured in direction coincident with the one of the applied load. The accuracy of measurement for the displacement is 0,01 mm.

The results are presented graphically as a chart – $F(D)$. Loading continues until a drop of the magnitude of the force F is registered at rapidly increasing displacement (D).

The maximal value of F is then recorded. This value is the critical force which the paperboard can withstand – F_{crit} .

The total number of tested samples is 72 as 48 are from L100 paperboard – 24 are loaded in machine direction (MD) and 24 in cross direction (CD). The rest 24 are from W100 – 12 are loaded in MD and 12 in CD.

Fig. 2. Testing of flat paperboard sample

Second experiment consists of testing samples from corrugated paperboard. Rectangular pieces as shown on figure 3 are cut out.

Their dimensions are 100 mm length and 24 mm width as the thickness is measured separately for each type of paperboard. Before testing each sample is left to stay 48 hours in the condition of 21,3° C temperature and relative humidity 48,6%.

Two types of corrugated paperboard are tested. The first one is with “C” flute and the second is with “B” flute. For both of them, flat paperboard L100 is used to make their liners and W100 is used for the making of the flute.

Fig. 3. Sample of corrugated paperboard for testing on compressive strength

The sample is loaded restricted and loaded in a way similar to what is shown on figure 2. Compressive force, which increases at a constant rate, is applied on the upper surface of the corrugated paperboard. Its magnitude F is measured along with the displacement D .

As it is in the case of testing flat paperboard, the loading continues until a drop of its magnitude is registered at rapidly growing displacement.

The maximal force is recorded. This value is the critical force which the paperboard can withstand – F_{crit} .

The $F(D)$ diagrams are transformed into “stress-strain” diagrams which are used at the stage of FEM-based computer simulation studying. In total 12 samples are tested from corrugated paperboard type “C” and 6 from type “B”.

In order to be able to build 3D geometric model of the corrugated paperboard, it is necessary to measure the thickness of the samples.

This is done with the tool shown on figure 4. Its accuracy is 0,001 mm.

Fig. 4. Measuring the thickness of paper, flat paperboard and corrugated paperboard

From theoretical point of view, the contact between the external flat layers and the internal corrugated layer should be a line but in fact, because of deformation which occurs during the process of manufacture (see figure 5) of the corrugated paperboard, it represents a section. In this article this section is characterized with geometric parameter – width of the contact section S .

Fig. 5. Actual contact between the layers of the corrugated paperboard

Fig. 6. Defining the parameter S – width of the contact section

Fig. 7. Calibration of the scale of the image

The S parameter is measured using microscope DigiMicro Profi, which receives the image by using 5,0 MP CMOS sensor and transfers it to computer. Additional tool then allows to calibrate the scale of the image (figure 7). Then by using special software linear dimensions can be measured. The accuracy of this measurement is 0,01 mm.

With known geometric parameters of the flat paperboard and the corrugated paperboard samples, a 3D model of the corrugated paperboard specimen is built and subjected to compressive load under conditions equal to the ones during the experimental testing.

FEM-based simulations are done by using Shell type of quadratic finite elements with 8 nodal points. Six degrees of freedom are considered at each nodal point.

3. Results and discussions

The measured thickness values for the flat and the corrugated paperboard are given in table 1. It should be noted that in this particular case, the thickness of the corrugated paperboard is coincident with the parameter H .

Table 1

Type	Thickness [mm]
<i>Flat paperboard</i>	
L100	0,186
W100	0,175
<i>Corrugated paperboard</i>	
C	3,983
B	3,053

The measured values for the critical force F_{crit} for the both types of corrugated paperboard are given in table 2.

Table 2

Type	F_{crit} [N]
C	324,23±9,02
B	372,15±11,28

The “stress-deformation” curves which are obtained after testing samples of flat paperboard are shown on figure 8.

Those curves are used to define the necessary mechanical properties of the materials for performing FEM-based computer simulations.

Fig. 8. “Stress-deformation” curves for flat paperboard specimens

After processing the experimental data, a 3D geometric model of the corrugated paperboard sample is built.

Its dimensions are chosen to be the same as the ones of the tested specimen for “C” type.

The value for the pitch of the flute is taken from [1, 7] and for the model it is 8 mm.

All dimensions of the model are shown on figure 9.

Fig. 9. Geometric model of the corrugated paperboard – type of flute “C”

Predicted “force-displacement” diagram is obtained and the tangent of the angle of the linear section from both curves (theoretical and experimental) is compared for the purpose of verification of the results from the simulations. This comparison shows that the suggested model can be used to perform further studies of the corrugated paperboard, since a good coincidence is achieved.

The model is then subjected to compressive loading at increasing rate while the model’s height is changed but its pitch remains constant. This is done in order to study how the H parameter influences the critical force F_{crit} . Graphical representation on this dependency is shown on figure 10. It is approximated to a linear function with coefficient of determination R^2 0,98. The equation is written as follows:

$$F_{crit}(H) = 4,60.H + 305,91 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 10. Dependency of F_{crit} on the height

The study continues by subjected to compressive loading at increasing rate while the pitch of the flute of the model is changed but its height remains constant. The aim is to study what is the influence of the pitch on the critical force F_{crit} . The obtained dependency is non linear. Several attempts are made to approximate it to known functions and the approximation with

higher coefficient of determination is achieved with polynomial function of 3rd degree. This function is written as follows:

$$F_{crit}(P) = -0,57.P^3 + 14,98.P^2 - 122,21.P + 643,52 \quad (2)$$

The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0,98. Graphical representation of equation 2 is shown on figure 11.

Fig. 11. Dependency of F_{crit} on the pitch of the flute P

In order to study how S affects F_{crit} , the 3D geometric model of the corrugated paperboard is subjected to compressive loading at increasing rate. The S parameter of the modes is changed while the other geometric parameters remain constant. Graphical representation of the obtained dependency is shown on figure 12.

It was best approximated to a polynomial function of 4th degree with coefficient of determination R^2 0,99. It is written as follows:

$$F_{crit}(S) = -1,76.S^4 + 18,00.S^3 - 4,66.S^2 + 95,19.S + 324,23 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 12. Dependency of F_{crit} on the width of the contact section

The study continues by investigating the influence of the radius of the curvature R of the corrugated layer's flute. This is done by subjecting the model of the corrugated paperboard to compressive loading at increasing rate. Its R parameter is changed while the other parameters remain constant. The theoretical dependency of F_{crit} from R is given on figure 13. It is approximated to linear function with the following equation:

$$F_{crit}(R) = -5,87.R + 333,80 \quad (4)$$

The coefficient of determination R^2 for this approximation is 0,90.

Fig. 13. Dependency of F_{crit} on the radius of curvature

4. Conclusions

The obtained dependencies by the means of experimental testing and computer simulations, show how the basic geometric parameters of corrugated paperboard affect its compressive strength.

The increase of thickness of the corrugated paperboard and the section of contact between the flute and the liners result in higher resistance towards compressive loads while the increase of the pitch of the flute and the radius of curvature R cause lowering of the strength.

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SOME ASPECTS OF OBTAINING AND USE OF GERMINATED WHEAT SEEDS

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Abstract: Investigation results of the influence of sodium chloride solutions and treatment conditions on wheat seeds germination efficiency are presented in the article. It was established that the studied have the maximal amount of water-soluble antioxidants and sugars on the fourth day. There are no antioxidants and water-soluble sugars in non-germinated wheat seeds. An assortment of products with the addition of germinated seeds, their nutritional and caloric values are presented.

Keywords: germinated seeds, antioxidants, nutrition value, culinary products.

The following Diderot's saying has been preserved in history: "Doctors keep on working at our health maintenance, cooks — at its undermining; however, the latter are more confident in their success". But each epoch has its own enlightenments and misconceptions. In the 60's of the XXth century, academician A.M. Uglov formulated the theoretical principles of trophology — the science of adequate nutrition [1, 2]. The terms functional and prophylactic foodstuffs, live food, biogenic products, superfood, producements have become fixed in our mind for the last two decades. Undoubtedly, this applies to various plant seedlings.

The tradition of eating seedlings dates back to ancient centuries. Wheat was first cultivated in ancient Egypt and its seeds were always germinated before eating. Germinated rye and wheat were also known to ancient Slavic tribes.

Germinated seeds can be referred to functional foodstuffs capable of therapeutic effect for both gastrointestinal tract and the whole human organism. Including seedlings in the menu replenishes human organism first with three

groups of important substances: enzymes and polysaccharides which are necessary to normalize substances circulation and for age defiance. Hydrolytic enzymes which decompose spare compounds into simple substances are actively synthesized in germinating seeds. Human is supplied with natural antioxidants mainly through plant food. The average daily antioxidants consumption amount is about 400 mg. Such quantity of water-soluble antioxidants can be found in 100 g of some berry fruits: current-berry, cherry, huckleberry, also in 100 g of the majority of cereal crops seedlings [2, 3].

Various cereal and leguminous crops, also wild plants, are currently used for prophylactic and medicinal nutrition. But wheat remains the most popular crop for obtaining seedlings.

We studied certain wheat seedlings parameters which allowed us to make some conclusions about the processes proceeding at the initial seeds germination period during 1-4 days controlling the result with several simple methods.

Our investigations showed that seed germination and seedlings growth strongly

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depend on incubation time. Wheat seedlings on the fourth day at the time of incubation in water for 6 hours are shown in Fig. 1, and on the third day at the incubation time for 24 hours - in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. *Wheat seedling on the fourth day (incubation — 6 hours)*

Fig. 2. *Barley seedlings on the third day (incubation – 24 hours)*

A change of seedlings mass before the start of biosynthesis may depend on two processes: proteins and polysaccharides hydrolysis which are to lead to a mass growth compared to the initial one and the saccharides consumption process to be accompanied by a mass loss.

Herein, accelerated development of a germinated seed should be provided by easily available water-soluble sugars. True, our investigations showed that seedlings mass is becoming significantly decreased during four days. Seedling sugar concentration growth as a result of hydrolysis during the same time was confirmed with the refractometrical method. The increase of seedlings antioxidant status was proved by direct determination of water extracts

antioxidant activity measured using the amperometrical method assisted by device «Цвет Язык-АА» (i.e. "Yauza Color" device) (Fig. 3). Antioxidant activity of the water extract obtained from seedlings is measured in mgs per 1 g. of plant material.

We studied the use of various substances, including growth stimulants, for wheat seed germination. The carried out investigations demonstrated the thing that sodium chloride is the most efficient preparation for this purpose. Thereat, one soaking in the agent solution at concentration 0.1 mol/l during 1 hour is sufficient to accelerate the germination process. The effect from this wheat treatment is brightly expressed in seedlings mass growth and water-solubles concentrations have maximum carbohydrates, whereas, herein, there is a notably smaller change of antioxidant activity observed. As a result of our researchwork, it was established that the obtained seedlings have the maximal amount of water-soluble antioxidants and water-soluble sugars on the fourth day.

In non-germinated wheat seeds there are no antioxidants and water-soluble sugars determined on the same methods.

Antioxidants preservability is an important factor for foodstuffs. The content of water soluble antioxidants decreased only by 20% in two months of preservation at room temperature in dried and milled seedlings. Based on the carried out investigations, a germination technology of seeds, which then were made part of culinary products ingredients, was developed.

As we believe, all the useful properties of germinated seeds can be used most completely when made part of culinary products ingredients, being not subjected to thermal treatment an hving limited validity terms 1/2 — 2 h.), of public catering enterprises. Similar research activities were realized by the authors of [4] that developed a number of recipes for various salads with partial replacement of some ingredients for fresh soya sprouts measured 10...20% from the mass of replaced ingredients. Recipes of jellied dishes with the addition of soya sprouts were also developed: jellied beef, fruit and berry jellies, fresh fruit and berry jellies — lemon, orange mandarin, jelly of fruit or berry extracts. It was established that 15, 30 and even 50% replacement of one of ingredients for soya considerably increases the products nutrition value without a decrease of organoleptic indices (taste, smell and composition).

Fig. 3. Change of antioxidant activity in germinated seed extracts

Seedlings are well combined with mushrooms and any vegetables: zucchini, Bulgarian pepper, cauliflower and other cabbage, all kinds of salad, tomatoes, cucumbers. The piquant taste can be added with garlic, onion, pepper, nuts. More Asian touches of taste can be added to dishes with germinated beans with soya sauce and ginger; more traditional will be the taste added with sunflower oil, lemon juice, and mayonnaise dressing [5].

When choosing groups of culinary products in which composition one can use seedlings, we were guided by preservation of maximum nutrients — flavonoids, vitamins, mineral substances, etc. — whose sources are seedlings.

In this connection, we chose the groups in which dishes were not subjected to thermal treatment: namely, cold dishes and snacks (h'odeouvres), sweet dishes and beverages.

The assortment of the developed products, content of main food ingredients and caloric value of dishes with germinated wheat seeds are presented in the table above. The chemical composition and caloric value of the developed products changes within a considerable range, which is determined by their recipes. However, anyway, introduction of germinated seeds in dishes recipes enriches them by proteins and digestible carbohydrates.

Table
Content of main food ingredients and caloric value of dishes with germinated wheat seeds.

Dish	Content, g			Caloric value, kcal
	proteins	lipids	carbohydrates	
Stuffed tomatoes with germinated seeds	8,69	14,98	4,59	188
"Marine miracle" salad	10,75	11,79	7,17	178
"Home-made" salad	9,55	8,57	7,42	145
Spring salad with germinated seeds	1,98	6,92	9,41	108
"Rice paradise" porridge	4,63	3,31	13,76	103
"Fruit fantasy" salad	2,79	0,87	12,75	70
"Banana caprice" mousse	2,17	15,12	36,28	290
"Cottage-cheese volcano" dessert	10,78	7,49	27,29	219
Milk shake with germinated seeds	3,56	5,51	12,36	113
"Tenderness" smoothies	2,73	0,86	17,99	90

Seedling-enriched products should be introduced in public catering enterprises with collective services for groups of people (schools, student canteens, sanatoriums, etc.), also in sports

bars and other enterprises where healthy lifestyle is practised in healthy eating habits for their visitors.

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CHANGES IN COMPOSITION OF EGG WHITE DURING STORAGE

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Abstract: *Hen eggs are an important source of nutrients, but their quality is highly affected by changes that may occur during storage. In this study are presented the results of the investigation of the change of the properties of eggs within 5 weeks of storage at room temperature and in the refrigerator. It can be observed an increased value of alkalinity of egg white and acidity of egg yolk. A migration of some components (phosphates, iron) occurs from yolk to white. The most optimal regime, which keeping quality of eggs during storage is maintenance in the refrigerator.*

Keywords: *freshness of eggs, alkalinity of egg white, acidity of egg yolk, content of phosphates and iron in egg white during maintenance*

Introduction

The modern poultry industry is not exactly satisfied with the traditional system assessment of quality of eggs, which are based mainly on visual inspection and ovoscopy [1,2]. Existence in practice of various batches of eggs impose a need to fast and objective estimation of the state of freshness, degree of bacterial infection, presence of livestock defects and states fatigue or altered of them. Currently the main criteria used for grading of shell eggs accepted by the EU Legislation are freshness of eggs. Because of profound changes that may occur during egg storage, the state of freshness is a key component of its quality. Also, the consumers may perceive variability in freshness as lack of quality. The changes that occur in egg during storage are various and affect physiological state and structure of the components. The protective membranes dry, the cuticle under shell egg and viteline membrane that covering the yolk are damaged. The oxygen penetrates the pores formed, which catalyze various biochemical reactions on egg albumen level. According to some authors [5,7], after yolk membrane damage processes of migration of compounds contained in the yolk to albumen are possible.

The aim of this experimental research was to estimate the dynamics of migration of phosphates and iron from egg yolk to egg white depending on the technological regime of storage eggs.

Materials and methods

Research has been conducted for food consumption hen eggs produced by hens cross *Leghorn* on poultry factory Valea Perjei, Taraclia. Measurements were performed at 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 weeks of storage of eggs. Comparative analysis was performed on eggs kept in a refrigerator (2 ± 4 °C) and eggs at room temperature (16 ± 18 °C). For each sample was used to determine average egg white/yolk obtained from 6 eggs with the same terms and conditions of storage. Alkalinity of the white, acidity of yolk was determined by titration [7]. Using spectroscopic methods was determined accumulation of phosphates in egg white [7] and iron in egg white [6]. Quantitative determination of phosphates was performed in reaction with molybdenum blue (phosphates concentration determined at $\lambda = 670$ nm), iron – with benzidine (concentration of Fe-benzidine complexone determined at $\lambda = 440$ nm).

Results

Changes of alkalinity of egg white. Alkaline qualities of the egg white are determined by the massive presence in the protein composition of basic amino acids (arginine, lysine) [7]. During storage alkalinity of egg white increased progressively (Tab.1). The phenomenon can be

explained primary, by increased proteolysis products and secondary, by losses of CO₂ through reactions and formation of degraded alkalinity the pores of the egg shell.

Table 1. Effect of temperature and storage time on alkalinity of egg white

Storage time, weeks	Alcalinity degree of egg white, X (°)	
	Refrigerated eggs	Eggs at a room temperature
0	11,2 ± 0,31	11,2± 0,31
1	14,7± 0,34	13,9± 0,35
2	14,4± 0,33	14,2± 0,32
3	13,5± 0,29	16,7± 0,37
4	14,2± 0,36	16,5± 0,30
5	16,4± 0,37	17,4± 0,38

Changes the pH of egg yolk. Acid reaction of egg yolk is due to the presence of acidic substances (fatty acids, lecithinphosphates, glycoposphates) [4,7]. In fresh eggs acidity of eggs yolk was 5,1 to 6,5 degree of acidity, while after 5 weeks of storage, eggs stored in the refrigerator have 7,9 degrees of total acidity and 9,2 - at room temperature. Acidification of yolk by storage can be explained by enzymatic and non-enzymatic hydrolysis. **Accumulation of phosphates in egg white.** In the composition of egg white phosphates are present in trace amounts, no more than 60-76 mg% . Unlike, significant sources of phosphates in egg yolk, about 400-550 mg%, are presented in simple and complex lipids (gliceriphosphates, lecithinphosphates) [1,4].

Experimental, accumulation of phosphates in egg white during storage can be demonstrated by color reaction – appearance of blue color at addition of molybdenum blue is a clear evidence

that egg whites gained a certain amount of phosphates. Quantitatively this phenomenon is studied with available calibration curve for the solution of 0,1M KH₂PO₄ maximum of absorption being at $\lambda = 540$ nm. Thus, was determined that level of phosphates in fresh egg white was 62,5 mg%. After 2 weeks of storage in a refrigerator as a results of migration of phosphates from the egg yolk increased to 72,3 mg% and after 5 week - 112.8 mg%. Consumption period of eggs as is shown in Hygienic rules is 3 weeks in refrigeration condition, during which the experimental egg white accumulated phosphates in an amount of 83,7 mg%. Keeping eggs at room temperature was observed an accelerated accumulation of phosphates in albumen, thus eggs of 5 weeks storage have slight signs of alteration, already containing 139,2 mg% of phosphates in albumen. (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of phosphate accumulation by storage

Accumulation of iron in the egg white by storage_ Fresh egg white contains a minimum amount of iron – 0,78 mg%, instead fresh egg yolk is extremely rich in iron - 7 mg%. The main containing iron compound of yolk is phosvitin, a highly phosphorylated protein [1,3]. Thus it is possible iron transfer to egg albumen from yolk during storage due to the yolk membrane deterioration. The gradient of iron ions concentration between structural components of the egg is formed by the difference of the values: 0,0081 mg Fe/ 1g albumen and respectively 0,412 mg Fe/ 1g yolk.

To estimate the accumulation of iron in the egg white during storage was studied optical properties of Fe-benzidine complexone. Experimentally was studied absorption spectrum of

Fe-benzidine complexone obtained by the treatment of egg white according to design proposed by the authors [6]. Absorption spectrum of the treated sample whites was recorded in the 200-650 nm range. From Fig.1 is easy to observe that spectrum has a band with a large absorption at $\lambda = 300$ nm, corresponding to hydrocarbon carbohydrate skeleton. Another band, with lower surface at $\lambda = 440$ nm, reflected the presence of Fe-benzidine complexone and is completely missing in fresh albumen samples, which almost contain minimum iron (Fig. 2). The appearance of this selective band than egg white treated samples being altered is a conformation of the fact that the yolk membrane deterioration causes a migration of iron ions from yolk to albumen, and a variation of its content in egg white.

Fig.2 Absorption spectrum of egg white sample, stored at room temperature for 5 weeks.

Iron ions that have been migrated to the egg white in storage conditions are fixed by the protein fraction – ovotransferin. While iron was fixed in ovotransferin molecule in reaction with benzidine results an oxidized, chromogenic component and color intensity response is used as an index of the amount of iron concentration fixed by ovotransferin [6]. In this experiment is important,

that egg white sample to be well treated with chloroform. In the interaction between benzidine and iron fixed by ovotransferin its necessary to produce a detectable absorbance at $\lambda = 440$ nm, even in the presence of low concentrations of iron, as is typical for the composition of native egg white.

Fig.3. The dynamics of iron accumulation in the egg white by storage

Dynamics of accumulation of iron ions in storage egg whites is shown in Fig.3. It was established that after 3 weeks of storage were exceeded natural background in eggs stored at room temperature (0,32 mg% opposite 0,17 mg% in fresh white eggs), for eggs storage as refrigerator – was not exceeded. The positive dynamics of accumulation of iron in white eggs, stored at room temperature (up to 0,54 mg% after 5 weeks of storage), confirms the transfer of iron from egg yolk to egg white during storage.

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Conclusion

Freshness of eggs is one of a main indicator for determining the quality of eggs. Profile of changes that occur in the egg white and yolk composition can be estimated by determining the value of the white alkalinity and acidity of yolk. Migration of egg yolk components to eggs white can now be estimate by determining the indices – the accumulation of phosphates and iron in the egg white. Regime of refrigeration is optimal to keep eggs, because ensure minimal changes in structure and composition of eggs.

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THE INFLUENCE OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS FROM MEMBRANE SEPTUM ON THE PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF THE WALNUT OIL-ENRICHED EMULSION

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Abstract: *In the present study it was evaluated the possibility to incorporate the walnut oil in food emulsions recipe. It was elaborated obtaining technology of mayonnaise type emulsions based on mixture of sunflower oil and walnut oil in combination with phenolic compounds from membrane septum extract. Therefore were obtained emulsions with 50% fat, containing different concentrations of walnut oil (25, 50, 75, and 100%). The microstructure of emulsions was determined using an optical microscope, of digital model «Motic DMB 5-5». The lipid oxidation was assessed by measuring peroxide value (PV), acid value (AV), conjugated dienes content (CD), and 2-thiobarbituric acid value (TBA). It was shown the feasibility of walnut oil utilization to increase the biological value and physical-chemical parameters of food emulsion as compared with the traditional recipe.*

Keywords: *food emulsion, walnut oil, membrane septum, primary and secondary oxidation products.*

1. Introduction

The oil-in-water (O/W) food emulsions are the basis of many food products and their properties define food quality to a great extent. As a consequence, interest in the theory and practice of food emulsions has been increasing. Scientific studies are oriented more and more toward different aspects of the characteristics, formation, behavior, and application of these food emulsions. Regarding oils, a wide variety of different types of oils have traditionally been used in food emulsions, including soybean, corn, canola, olive, safflower, and sunflower oils [6].

The trend has been to replace traditional oils with more health-promoting oils, such as polyunsaturated lipids. Walnut oil (*Junglas regia* L.) is one of these beneficial oils. Walnut oil is high-quality oil due to its important physical and biochemical properties. In addition, walnut oil has significant economical value and medicinal importance for human health because of its essential composition of polyunsaturated fatty acids, especially linoleic (18:2) and linolenic (18:3) acids, bioactive minor components, such as tocopherols and phytosterols and is appreciated as specialty oil also because of its characteristic flavor and aroma [10].

But on the other side high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids make walnut oil

prone to oxidation. A major goal in walnut production is to find an appropriate method to stabilize walnut lipids. The oxidative stabilization of walnut oil is imperative to determine the feasibility of bringing it into commercial production.

Interest in the development of processes for the production or extraction of bioactive compounds from by-products sources has increased in recent years due to the potential applications of these compounds in food, chemical, and pharmaceutical industries. In the present study walnut membrane septum as a potential alternative source of bioactive compounds for food emulsion stabilization are evaluated.

The purpose of this study is to develop a new kind of food emulsion with a high biological value, contributing to improve the nutritional status of the population. In this regard, the possibility to incorporate the walnut oil in food emulsions recipe was evaluated.

To decrease the intensity of possible oxidative transformations of the investigated emulsion, the task was posed to obtain walnut oil-enriched emulsion with increased antioxidant properties at the expense of incorporating into its composition natural phenolic compounds from membrane septum, namely, antioxidative components.

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2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

As components for obtaining experimental samples of food emulsions sunflower oil, walnut oil, sugar, mustard powder, milk powder, vinegar, salt, emulsifier and natural extract from walnut membrane septum were used. All foodstuff used correspond to requirements for quality of the specifications and technical documentation.

2.2. Technology of samples preparation

Ten experimental samples of food emulsions were prepared for researching which differ by the content of walnut oil and membrane septum extract. To obtain samples of food emulsions with a high biological value 25, 50, 75 and 100% of sunflower oil was replaced by walnut oil. The figure 1 shows the technological scheme for producing the stabilized walnut oil-enriched emulsion at the expense of membrane septum extract. The obtained emulsion samples were placed in sterile plastic food containers with sealable lids and stored for 24 hours at 4 °C, then corresponding analyses were carried out.

2.3. Chemicals

2-thiobarbituric acid (4,6-dihydroxy-2-mercaptopyrimidine) was obtained from Alfa Aesar. 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) as free radical form (90% purity) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol (99.9%), chloroform, 1-butanol, glacial acetic acid, potassium hydroxide, phenolphthalein, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and starch were supplied by Eco-Chimie (Chisinau, Moldova). All the chemicals used were of HPLC or analytical grade. Distilled water was used throughout.

2.4. Determination of the basic quality properties

Acidity of the food emulsion samples were determined by potassium hydroxide titration as described in AOCS Official Method Cd 3d-63 (AOCS, 1999) [1]. Peroxide value was determined according to AOCS Official Method Cd 8-53 (AOCS, 2003) [2]. Conjugated dienes were detected by a spectral method of analysis ($\lambda=232$ nm) according to the AOCS Official method Ti 1a 64 (AOCS, 1993) [3]. The formation of the secondary oxidation products accumulation in the investigated emulsion samples were characterized by the 2-thiobarbituric acid value in accordance with

AOCS Official Method Cd 19-90 (AOCS, 2009) [4].

2.5. Definition of a microstructure and the sizes of oil droplets

By using an optical microscope of digital model "Motic DMB 5-5" (China) the microstructure of food emulsions was determined. For this purpose a drop of the investigated sample of emulsion was placed on the subject glass, covered with its integumentary glass and then established in a microscope.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Variance analysis of the results was carried out by least square method with application of coefficient Student and Microsoft Office Excel program. Differences were considered statistically significant if probability was greater than 95% (p-value <0.05). All assays were performed by triplicate at room temperature 20 ± 1 °C. Experimental results are expressed as average \pm SD (standard deviation).

3. Results and discussion

Food emulsion represents difficult dispersed, stable fatty emulsion of direct type in which the disperse phase is distributed in the form of the smallest droplets in the dispersive medium, differentiated by an interface [9]. Actual trend of the oil industry is to produce food emulsion based on mixture of vegetable oils of different types according to their fatty acid composition. Walnut oil was chosen as a fortifier due to high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids and natural antioxidants.

Particular attention is paid to the possible impact of insertion ingredients on quality parameters on enriched products. As in technological process of obtaining food emulsion there is an interaction of various systems, a regrouping of making substances from products. Thus the disperse system finds certain structure properties.

The incorporation in composition of investigated samples of emulsion walnut oil was accompanied by a change of structure characteristics, such as perimeter, radius and area. The degree of change in these indicators depends on quantity of input walnut oil and the gradient speed of shift of a product. Results of researches of structure characteristics for compared samples of food emulsion are shown in table 1.

Fig. 1. The main technological processes of producing stabilized walnut oil-enriched emulsion.

Table 1. The main oil droplets parameters of compared food emulsions

No	Sample of food emulsion	Parameters of oil droplets		
		Perimeter, [μm]	Radius, [μm]	Area, [μm^2]
1	Mayonnaise sample (100% sunflower oil)	5.71 \pm 0.02	35.95 \pm 0.02	141.4 \pm 0.02
2	Mayonnaise sample (25% walnut oil)	7.85 \pm 0.03	49.32 \pm 0.03	272.23 \pm 0.03
3	Mayonnaise sample (50% walnut oil)	9.27 \pm 0.01	58.31 \pm 0.01	427.46 \pm 0.01
4	Mayonnaise sample (75% walnut oil)	12.44 \pm 0.03	78.24 \pm 0.03	770.06 \pm 0.03
5	Mayonnaise sample (100% walnut oil)	10.76 \pm 0.02	44.17 \pm 0.02	724.77 \pm 0.02

In compared samples of emulsions under the number 1 – 5 show the effect of input walnut oil (25, 50, 75 and 100%) on quality parameters of the microstructure of food emulsions compared with the control sample. It was notice that the most dense spherical and uniform arrangement of oil droplets is typical for samples of mayonnaise emulsions numbered 2 and 3, moreover, the oil droplets of this emulsions differ by the smallest sizes. Increasing the size of fat droplets in sample number 4 and 5 leads to a larger contact surface areas of spheres and, consequently, to reduce the viscosity of the food emulsion.

Walnut membrane septum is considered a source of bioactive compounds and have been widely used in traditional medicine. Antiradical and antibacterial activities have also been described for different *Juglans regia* cultivars. Walnut membrane septum is a by-product of the walnut production, being formed in large amounts. Probably due to its scarce utilization, this matrix is very little studied.

Walnut membrane septum extract was analyzed in our previous studies for total polyphenol content (TPC) and antioxidant activity. The TPC was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method. The antioxidant activity of the extracts was determined using 2,2 diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical DPPH•. Experimental results on the antioxidant activity of the bioactive compounds from walnut membrane septum allowed to make the assumption about possibility of their incorporation into food emulsions to prevent negative oxidation process [8].

Oxidative and hydrolytic decomposition is observed in the process of preparation food emulsion. The presence and depth of the process of oxidation and hydrolysis is characterized by the content of free fatty acids, i.e., the acid value (AV). The growth of the acid value or intensity in the formation of free fatty acids in the compared emulsion samples has a linear character (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of added walnut oil and membrane septum extract on the amount of acidity and peroxide values in compared mayonnaise samples

The presence and quantity of peroxides in food emulsions are known to determine the level of the oil storage stability. Figure 2 shows the dynamics of the accumulation of these compounds in the compared emulsion samples during preparation. As the presented data show, the summary rate of oxidative reactions that lead to the formation of peroxides in the course of emulsion preparation is lower for the group of food emulsion with membrane septum extract.

Figure 3 shows the change in the intensity of the accumulation of conjugated dienes and malondialdehydes (expressed by the amount of the 2-thiobarbituric acid value) in the compared food emulsions.

Fig. 3. Effect of added walnut oil and membrane septum extract on the amount of conjugated dienes content and 2-thiobarbituric acid value in compared mayonnaise samples

It was established that with increasing concentrations of walnut oil there had place the increase of the amount of primary and secondary products of lipid oxidation, such as peroxides and aldehydes.

When comparing the antioxidative properties of the membrane septum extract incorporated into the emulsion samples, one should note that the antioxidative components of the extracts exert the significant influence on inhibiting the processes of walnut oil-enriched emulsion oxidation. This regularity is also traced for the acidity and

peroxide values of the corresponding emulsion samples.

4. Conclusions

The effect of incorporated walnut oil on the structure characteristics of compared samples of food emulsions it is established that the sample containing walnut oil 25% is characterized by the most dense spherical and uniform arrangement of oil droplets of emulsion.

The composition of vegetable oils (sunflower and walnut) in a ratio of 3:1 used to create a food emulsion with a high biological value is the most optimal ratio of polyunsaturated fatty acids ω -3: ω -6, providing, in combination with phenolic compounds from membrane septum extract oxidation stability to the finished product.

This study demonstrates that natural extract such as walnut membrane septum could be used as alternative source of natural antioxidants in food industries, especially for food emulsion stabilization. The experimental results apparently indicated that walnut membrane septum extract exerts an effective influence on the processes of oil stabilization; i.e., they inhibit the intensity of the primary and secondary oxidation products accumulation.

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***ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGIES
AND EQUIPMENT FOR AGRICULTURE AND FOOD
INDUSTRY***

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